

VALKYRIES

D5.6 Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

Reference Number: D5.6

Ed/Rev: A/0

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Date: 31/03/2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

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Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	31/03/2023	All	Original D5.2 document

Content

1. Executive Summary	1
2. Identification	3
3. Introduction	4
3.1 Methodology	19
3.1.1 Structure criteria	20
3.1.2 ID Codification/Traceability.....	20
3.2 Exclusion criteria	21
3.3 Information source.....	21
3.4 Experts consultation.....	21
4. Required capabilities.....	22
4.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning	22
4.1.1 Crisis response planning.....	22
4.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage.....	23
4.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment	25
4.3 Command and control and support to operational decision-making.....	26
4.4 Common operational picture and warning.....	26
4.4.1 Common operational picture	27
4.4.2 Alert and warning.....	28
5. Identification of gaps.....	30
5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning	30
5.1.1 Crisis response planning.....	30
5.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage.....	34
5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment.....	43
5.2.1 Communications logistics.....	43
5.2.2 Others logistics	48
5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making	50
5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning	61
5.4.1 Common Operational Picture	61
5.4.2 Alert and warning.....	68
6. Opportunities	74
6.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning	74
6.1.1 Crisis response planning.....	74
6.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage.....	83
6.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment.....	91

6.2.1 Communications logistics.....	92
6.2.2 Others logistics	94
6.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making	96
6.4 Common Operational Picture and warning	104
6.4.1 Common Operational Picture	104
6.4.2 Alert and warning.....	110
7. Conclusions	117
7.1 General conclusions of WP5 gaps and opportunities	117
7.1.1 Classification of gaps and opportunities	117
7.1.2 Sources of the gaps	119
7.1.3 Types of gaps.....	120
7.1.4 Types of opportunities	121
7.2 Conclusions of T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning	121
7.2.1 Sources of the gaps	121
7.2.2 Type of gaps	122
7.2.3 Type of opportunities.....	124
7.3 Conclusions of T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment.....	126
7.3.1 Sources of the gaps	126
7.3.2 Type of gaps	127
7.3.3 Type of opportunities.....	128
7.4 Conclusions of T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making	130
7.4.1 Sources of the gaps	130
7.4.2 Type of gaps	130
7.4.3 Type of opportunities.....	131
7.5 Conclusions of T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning	133
7.5.1 Sources of the gaps	133
7.5.2 Type of gaps	133
7.5.3 Type of opportunities.....	136
8. Annex A – References and bibliography	140
8.1 Internal references.....	140
8.2 External references	140
9. Annex B – Glossary	145

Tables

Table 1 - D5.5 Base requirements	5
Table 2 - D5.5 Common requirements	19
Table 3 – ID codification structure for traceability	21
Table 4 – Gaps from crisis response planning	34
Table 5 – Gaps from reconnaissance and triage.....	43
Table 6 – Gaps from communication maintenance, logistics and deployment	48
Table 7 – Gaps from others maintenance, logistics and deployment	50
Table 8 – Gaps from command and control and support to operational decision-making	60
Table 9 – Gaps from Common Operational Picture	68
Table 10 – Gaps from alert and warning	73
Table 11 – Indicative standards related to terminology and symbology	75
Table 12 – Opportunities from crisis response planning.....	83
Table 13 – Opportunities from reconnaissance and triage	91
Table 14 – Opportunities from communications maintenance, logistics and deployment	94
Table 15 – Opportunities from others maintenance, logistics and deployment.....	96
Table 16 – Opportunities from command and control and support to operational decision-making	104
Table 17 – Opportunities from Common Operational Picture	110
Table 18 – Indicative standards relevant to early warning specifications and procedures.....	111
Table 19 – Opportunities from alert and warning.....	116
Table 20 - Classification of the GAPS of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES.....	118
Table 21 - Classification of the OPPORTUNITIES of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES.....	119
Table 22 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES.....	119
Table 23 - Type of GAP of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES	120
Table 24 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES	121
Table 25 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning.....	122
Table 26 - Type of GAP of the T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning	122
Table 27 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning.....	124
Table 28 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment ...	126
Table 29 - Type of GAP of the T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment.....	127
Table 30 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment	129
Table 31 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making	130
Table 32 - Type of GAP of the T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making	130
Table 33 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making	132
Table 34 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning	133
Table 35 - Type of GAP of the T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning	134
Table 36 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning	136
Table 37 - Glossary	146

Figures

Figure 1 - Military simbology examples. Source (Military Symbols, 2022; Kolev, 2022)	76
Figure 2 - Shape and colour of the categorized symbols. Source (Marinova, 2017)	76
Figure 3 - Emergency Response Preparedness (ERP) Cycle	79
Figure 4 - Fragment of logistic structure of data base MIP. Source (Burita, 2009)	108

1. Executive Summary

This document describes the opportunities for harmonisation in the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response in multi-casualty disasters.

The identification of these harmonisation opportunities has been based on the study and analysis of the required capabilities/needs and gaps in the field of crisis management in relation to:

- Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning
- Maintenance, logistics and deployment
- Command and control and operational decision support
- Common operational picture
- Warning and alerting

For this purpose, the sources used were the deliverable 5.5 itself, as well as the bibliography referenced therein, the professionals' own experience and the questionnaires submitted by experts and emergency services in the course of the work of WP5, Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses, of the Valkyries project.

The gaps and opportunities identified have been coded for traceability.

At the end of the document, conclusions have been drawn in each of the sections in relation to the source and type of gaps, as well as the type of opportunity, interrelating both concepts in order to have a more complete vision of the opportunities for harmonisation.

This deliverable D5.6 is the final version of draft D5.2. To make it easier to identify the changes made in this final version compared to the previous one, they have been highlighted in yellow.

In order to harmonise the deliverables, the following format changes have been made:

- The "provider" column has been removed from the gaps and opportunities tables.
- In the opportunity tables the commune "Gap ID" has been added with the related gaps.

Listed below, in order of appearance in deliverable D5.6, are the main changes in this document compared to draft version D5.2. Links to the corresponding text are available under the same heading. Spelling or grammatical corrections, as well as minor variations in relation to some very specific terms or content, are not included in this list of changes.

3. Introduction: (List of the objectives modified).

7. Conclusions: Main changes:

7.3 Conclusions of T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment

7.3.2 Type of gaps

7.3.2.2 Types of gaps related to first responders communications
(Added)

7.3.2.3 Types of gaps related to maintenance, logistics and
deployment (Added)

7.3.3 Type of opportunities

7.3.3.1 Types of opportunities related to first responders communications (Added)

7.3.3.2 Types of opportunities related to maintenance, logistics and deployment (Added)

7.4 Conclusions of T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making

7.4.2 Type of gaps

7.4.2.1 Type of gaps related to Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making (Added)

7.4.3 Type of opportunities

7.4.3.1 Type of opportunities related to Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making (Added)

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18.

Deliverable Id: D5.6

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D5.6

Name of lead participant: TASSICA

Name of Contributors: IND, SERMAS, ISEMI, PART, UMU, SSA, NOV, BDI, KEM, HESE, ARA, USN, AREU, HRT

Type: Report (R)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP5 Common practices, and operational procedures for first aid responses

Linked project tasks:

- T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning
- T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment
- T5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making
- T5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning

Action: Study

Status: First Release (updated from D5.2)

Document Layout: VALKYRIES official template

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. The document presents the identification and assessment of the regulatory, certification and standardization needs and gaps on the existing and emerging procedures for supporting first aid responses, emphasizing those covered by the working streams driven by T5.1, T5.2, T5.3, T5.4 and T5.5. This is an updated version from D5.2 document.

3. Introduction

VALKYRIES is a European H2020 project aimed at analysing, improving and developing infrastructures, protocols and tactics for standardisation and harmonisation of data exchange with the objective of increasing efficiency and interoperability in the response to incidents with multiple victims or disasters, especially in more complex or cross-border cases.

VALKYRIES will map, identify communities, analyse the regulatory and normalization issues in the targeted opportunities, and suggest roadmaps for their mitigation and prompting the adoption of the disruptive solutions on the first aid response markets.

This will be achieved by developing three core blocks with their corresponding working streams: Technologies and Equipment for first aid responders (KARA), Procedures and Operation for first aid responders (HERJA), and Collaboration and Training for first aid responders (EIR). At the early stage of the project, the committed end-users and institutions together with the Consortium and external advisors will prioritize the studied needs, selecting a subset of them for guiding a reference harmonization and integration of some of the targeted opportunities. This will result in the SIGRUN interconnected platform.

SIGRUN will reference harmonize and integrate some of the analysed opportunities towards delivering a cognitive communications and resource federation platform for C2 at first aid responses in MCI. Among others, SIGRUN will include tactical command and control systems and services; and a mobile application able to public alerting/warning and crowdsourcing a common operational picture.

The results and recommendations of VALKYRIES project are also manifested in the elaboration of deliverables.

This deliverable D5.6 builds on the information gathered in D5.5: Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters and, like this one, is the result of the work carried out in tasks T5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning, T5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment, T5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making and T5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning, which make up WP5 Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses of the VALKYRIES project.

Within the project, WP5 has as its main objective to provide a comprehensive information framework of EU common operational plans and procedures, and to deliver harmonisation guidelines and recommendations for operational practices and procedures to facilitate, guide and improve cooperation between actors in first aid response to mass casualty incidents and disasters

The objective of this deliverable D5.6, Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters, is to provide an identification and assessment of needs and gaps in regulation, certification and standardisation of existing and emerging procedures to support first aid responses, focusing on the cross-border, cross-sector and cross-hierarchical context, fulfilling the following established requirements:

BASE REQUIREMENTS

The following table lists the 2 base (mandatory) requirements related to deliverable D5.3, and their traceability to the Valkyries project objectives.

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_BASE_T5.1_2	P1	The regulatory and harmonization Gaps and opportunities SHOULD be identified	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_BASE_T5.1_7	P1	Collection and analysis of needs related to C2 from the perspective of responders.	VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	T5.1	Inspection

Table 1 - D5.5 Base requirements

COMMON REQUIREMENTS

The following table lists the 42 common (optional) requirements related to deliverable D5.3, and their traceability to the Valkyries project objectives.

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.1_2	P1	Emergency services SHOULD have specific action procedures to deal with incidents with multiple victims (disaster medical management plan)	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.1_3	P2	Organization and capacities of health systems	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.1_4	P2	Analysis of the event notification process that entails the activation of a response plan to a health crisis	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_7	P1	Data SHOULD be collected and analyzed continuously	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_8	P2	Medical communications and information management	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_13	P2	Effective coordination and communications are of critical importance in the distribution of disaster victims.	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.1_14	P2	Use of operating rooms for patients requiring immediate surgery	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_4	P2	In disasters, tents are often needed in which to care for victims. Emergency teams MAY have the capacity to deploy this type of infrastructure.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_5	P3	It may be necessary to relieve the first responders because the emergency drags on over time.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_6	P2	Capacity of an emergency team to increase its operational resources in case more resources are needed than those available in the ordinary device.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
			6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9		
REQ_COM_T5.2_7	P2	It MAY be necessary to supply medical material and medicines to assist victims.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_8	P1	It MUST be ensured that the first responders have the basic means necessary to act in the disaster area: fuel, supplies, transportation, rest areas...	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_9	P2	In disasters, a stable communications network may not be possible.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.1	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_4	P2	In disasters, tents are often needed in which to care for victims. Emergency teams MAY have the capacity to deploy this type of infrastructure.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_5	P3	It may be necessary to relieve the first responders because the emergency drags on over time.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
			6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9		
REQ_COM_T5.2_6	P2	Capacity of an emergency team to increase its operational resources in case more resources are needed than those available in the ordinary device.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_7	P2	It MAY be necessary to supply medical material and medicines to assist victims.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.2_8	P1	It MUST be ensured that the first responders have the basic means necessary to act in the disaster area: fuel, supplies, transportation, rest areas...	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.2_9	P2	In disasters, a stable communications network may not be possible.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.2	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_1	P2	User guide for operational decision making. Standarize activites procedures.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-	T5.3	Inspection

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
			7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9		
REQ_COM_T5.3_4	P2	Incident identification and validation MUST be supported by protocols and MAY be supported by tools that facilitate decision-making.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_6	P2	An effective operational communications network MUST be established within incident response planning to ensure communications with teams deployed on scene.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.3_8	P2	The basic actions for the containment of the damage caused by the incident MUST be initiated from the very first moment, to reduce the added risks for those affected and for the first responders.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_11	P2	An Emergency Response Coordination Center MUST be set up, bringing together all those responsible for the disaster command and control center. This center MUST have a unified command.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_15	P2	The command and control of the disaster response MUST be based on a communication network and on an adequate, effective and secure flow of information that facilitates informed decision-making and horizontal	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
		and vertical coordination.	VALK-OBJ-9		
REQ_COM_T5.3_16	P2	Tools SHOULD be made available to facilitate effective data collection and processing, as they are essential to the efficiency and effectiveness of disaster relief and response strategies.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_17	P2	The Incident Command MUST be aware of and attentive to what is happening on scene at a particular time, with particular emphasis on the effect of changes in the incident; in effect, know how the incident is evolving.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.3_19	P2	The Incident Command MUST track and know where first responders and other personal or resources are deployed at any time.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_21	P2	The Incident Command MUST be able to provide a summary of aggregated incident information in easy-to-issue, to transmit and to understand reports.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration
REQ_COM_T5.3_22	P2	The decision to terminate the emergency response to an incident MUST be based on protocolized criteria and ensure the orderly, safe, and efficient return of emergency resources to their original location and status.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	T5.3	Inspection Demonstration

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
			VALK-OBJ-9		
REQ_COM_T5.4_1	P1	The terms used in the COP MUST be defined and standardized	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_8	P2	The COP MUST show the updated information at all times.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_9	P2	The COP MAY indicate other possible risks in the area of operations (risk map).	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.4_10	P2	The COP MAY indicate elements of special vulnerability in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_11	P2	The COP MAY indicate logistics resources of interest previously registered in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_12	P2	Te COP SHOULD locate the hospitals of the health system in the area of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_14	P2	The COP MAY indicate the emergency response plan that has been activated, as well as the declared activation level.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8	T5.4	Inspection

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
			VALK-OBJ-9		
REQ_COM_T5.4_15	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the victims in the scenario of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_16	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of emergency vehicles in the operations scenario.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_17	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the first responders in the operations scenario.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

ID	Priority	Description	Traceability with VALKYRIES objectives	Related WP5 task	Verification Method
REQ_COM_T5.4_19	P2	The COP MUST indicate the location of the resources deployed to support the intervention of the emergency medical service on the scene of operations.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection
REQ_COM_T5.4_27	P2	Recommendations must be established regarding the emission of alerts and alarms through public address systems and other elementary resources in the context of the response to MCI and disasters.	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	T5.4	Inspection

Table 2 - D5.5 Common requirements

3.1 Methodology

The VALKYRIES project has developed a common methodology for the second deliverable of technical work packages (WP4, WP5 and WP6). It has shown the need to link deliverables so that ideas flow from the primitive state to finally become a real opportunity for project stakeholders.

In this way, no idea, gap or opportunity will go unanalysed, or its feasibility assessed. This methodology clarifies the inputs and outputs of each of the stages defined. Particularly, it is composed of three stages, based on the pre-standardisation map designed earlier in the project, presented as follows:

- State of the art, and pre-identification of gaps.
- Gap and communalities analysis, and harmonisation opportunities.

- Valkyries outputs.

According with this step about **harmonisation and opportunities**, there are many benefits of having a common working methodology for the different work packages, and one of them is to be able to work not only as a unit but also as a whole.

3.1.1 Structure criteria

The common structure of these technical deliverables has been composed by these chapters:

Required capabilities

This first chapter explains the capabilities required by the user in the emergency. This chapter serves as a link between the previous work about the landscape of the technical purpose of the project, the analysis of the existing state of the art, and the analysis of surveys shared with other first responders. Based on the study of these capabilities required by users for both topic and tasks of the project, different desired capabilities could differ from those currently available. This situation creates a potential gap that will be reflected in the next chapter.

Identification of Gap

This chapter is the continuation of the pre-identified gaps in the previous work at the landscape. In particular, this section presents problems or needs of the technical topic and that limit the actuation of first responders and the capabilities of technological solutions.

Thus, this chapter has two very different parts:

- Concept development. It presents in a detailed way the potential solutions derived from the previous gaps, the problems they cause and harmonisation necessities, among other aspects of interest.
- Summary and codification of the opportunities. It presents tables to summarise the opportunities detected.

Opportunities

This chapter is the output of this deliverable and the inputs for the work in the incoming months and deliverables. This section aims to determine if the previously identified gaps can be solved and, if so, how they could be solved.

As in the previous chapter, the present one has two distinct parts:

- Concept development. It presents in a detailed way the potential solutions derived from the previous gaps, the problems they cause and harmonisation necessities, among other aspects of interest.
- Summary and codification of the opportunities. It presents tables to summarise the opportunities detected.

3.1.2 ID Codification/Traceability

All the gaps and opportunities identified in the document has been codify in order to have a traceability.

The code is created as follows:

- The 1st part of the code identifies if it is a gap or an opportunity, indicated by a G or an OP.

- The 2nd part of the code is for the task of the project that had more relationship with the gap/opportunity. For this deliverable D5.2, in the case of those tasks divided into two distinct sub-tasks, these sub-tasks are identified by adding a second digit to this second part of the code, separating both digits by a dot.
- The 3rd part of the code is just a hyphen to divide and improve legibility.
- The 4th part of the code is for the item number. This number starts from 1 to n. Any change in the first three parts of the code starts a new coding of part 4 from 1 to n.

1 st part	2 nd part	3 rd part	4 th part
G=Gap OP= Opportunity	Task number. Subtask number	-	Item number (1..n)
Example			
G	5.2.1	-	1

Table 3 – ID codification structure for traceability

Traceability is crucial in this type of methodology both for readability and for establishing a link between different work packages and deliverables. Additionally, gaps and opportunities must be identified in a useful and handy way. Only following a structured nomenclature can the items be identified and referenced without investing too much effort.

At later stages, this codification also allows to create relations between gaps and opportunities.

3.2 Exclusion criteria

There are harmonization needs (gaps and opportunities) that although related to emergency and use cases are not part of the technical discussion.

Governance issues are outside the scope of the project. They are part of the political discussion. The project is not intended to work on these issues and therefore they are out of scope and do not appear within this deliverable.

3.3 Information source

The information collected and analysed in the report comes from different resources such as literature reviews, document analysis, professional experience, surveys, etc. Besides, the analysis of lessons learned from previous crisis management operations were carried out to identify needs/gaps and opportunities for improving technological aspects during emergency situations.

3.4 Experts consultation

Finally, the project researchers who have contributed to the tasks of Work Package 5 developed a questionnaire to facilitate the understanding of the complex European map of operational practices and procedures in MCI and disaster response.

This questionnaire has been distributed, in a first round of surveys, among the experts identified within the VALKYRIES project consortium partners, as well as among the experts of its External Advisory Board. In a second round, the survey will be extended to emergency services across Europe.

Its results, reflected in the previous deliverable D5.5, also serve as a fundamental basis for the identification of gaps and opportunities in this deliverable D5.6.

4. Required capabilities

This section presents the analysis of the capabilities that would be considered necessary at the present time in MCI and disaster response, in relation to the aspects studied in WP5: Common Practices, and operational procedures for First Aid Responses.

The definition of these required capabilities has taken into account:

- The base and common requirements collected in the deliverable VALKYRIES D2.1 Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases.
- The state of the art and the European and international landscape reflected in the deliverable VALKYRIES - D5.5 Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters.
- The responses of the experts to the WP5 survey.
- The own experience of the VALKYRIES researchers contributing to the WP5.

This section is essential to understand the expected functioning during emergencies and therefore to subsequently identify gaps and opportunities for harmonisation in relation to procedures for supporting first aid responses.

4.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning

In order to facilitate its approach and understanding, this task T5.1, Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning, has been divided into 2 sub-tasks focusing respectively on:

- Crisis response planning
- Reconnaissance and triage

4.1.1 Crisis response planning

Disasters, regardless of their origin, are becoming more frequent and their impact is also increasing. Disaster management often involves a wide range of organisations and institutions, of different nationalities and with different operational procedures. In order for this response system to function in an integrated manner, mechanisms must be in place to ensure coordination and interoperability between cross-sectoral, inter-hierarchical and even cross-border teams.

These mechanisms include crisis management plans or systems that allow for information exchange.

Planning is one of the pillars of crisis management. Emergency plans are the instruments that provide the organisational and functional framework and mechanisms for mobilising the necessary resources to protect people and property in the event of an emergency. They also set out how the different administrations involved in the management of a disaster should coordinate. Developing a comprehensive emergency response plan therefore means providing procedures with the necessary details covering emergency response organisation, communication and responsibilities to be observed by all personnel in responding to an emergency.

With thorough preparation for any emergency (planning, practising, evaluating and adjusting to the specific circumstances), an emergency can be managed comprehensively and this can only occur if all parties involved have been planning and coordinating together, and the plans and procedures provided have been practised, evaluated and improved.

The emergency services should have specific procedures in place for the management of multiple casualty incidents. Operational and procedural capabilities can be harmonised and improved at the European level, following a roadmap based on the set of best practice guidelines and procedures that have been published by the European Union to help Member States harmonise their systems and actors involved in disasters. It is these guidelines and procedures that Valkyries will use as a baseline to try to achieve interoperability between the different federated systems for the exchange of information.

It will be the SIGRUN system that will enable this interoperability by including functions and workflows/responsibilities that do not follow a common standard at European level, allowing information to converge to ensure an optimal level of operability.

On the other hand, it would be interesting to try to develop harmonising legislation to promote the establishment of unified cross-border response plans and procedures, as the heterogeneity in the structure and organisation of the different services makes interoperability between them difficult.

Planning requires a process of implementation and updating. Implementation involves the dissemination of the plan to both the affected population and the organisations that make up the action groups, the development of procedures for action, the education and training of all those involved in the response, as well as the provision of the necessary equipment.

The process of periodically reviewing and updating emergency plans is the responsibility of each local, regional and national institution. It is necessary for legislation to make them mandatory and enforceable.

On the other hand, it is vital to have an information system that allows for the exchange of data, allowing a common operational picture to be obtained, as well as common terminology and symbology. This will provide accurate information in real time, which is essential for decision-making. This exchange can be carried out through the SIGRUN system, which is able to allow the sharing of POP information between countries.

This sharing includes both the notification of the event that triggers the emergency plan and the continuous information needed to manage the incident as it progresses over time. Systematic models such as METHANE, which provide structure and clarity in the early stages of the management of any multi-agency or large-scale incident, facilitate harmonisation between countries.

In addition to this information, it is relevant for the improvement of crisis response that the lessons learned from the different institutions' experience in real events are shared in order to propose improvements in plans and procedures.

4.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage

Other relevant aspects of MCI and disaster management are recognition and triage. These processes include different activities including: observation, gathering, processing and exchange of information, assessment of the situation including forecasting, planning, decision making and

communication of decisions taken, implementation of decisions, information gathering and control measures ¹.

In MCIs and disasters, EMS is responsible for carrying out the various health actions (triage, health care and evacuation). These actions are well defined in this type of situation, but there is great variability in the different EMS in terms of structure and the functions assumed by each of the first responders at both national and international level.

It is therefore necessary to harmonise and standardise different aspects to ensure interoperability between services and traceability of victims, such as: training, procedures, information on victims and their labelling, the interrelation between the out-of-hospital and hospital environment and debriefing.

Harmonisation of training and competencies of emergency services professionals at EU level can be strengthened through the implementation of internationally recognised first aid curricula for first responders. The knowledge and training of professionals in the use of new technologies can also be enhanced to ensure that their use is internalised in stressful situations, which would be easier if the tools implemented for these situations were easy to integrate and use.

On the other hand, both national and international working groups should be encouraged to develop consensual agreements for the harmonisation of procedures through a common federated system.

This system, in addition to the procedures, should include the roles/workflows of the different systems used by the institutions that will converge in the SIGRUN system.

SIGRUN will support the files containing the victim's information once registered and tagged. Traceability of this data can be ensured by using tools with smartphones or tablets with which FRs are familiar. Common and low-cost technologies should be used, which are not complex in their interoperability between the different support systems.

The information can be classified in blocks that facilitate access to one or another data according to the profiles defined for access to the system, so that professionals only access the information considered necessary for decision-making in their field of action.

With regard to victim information, the basic information to be collected on each victim must be standardised in order to ensure traceability and continuity of care for those affected by a disaster, especially in cross-border disasters. Hence the relevance of defining a minimum set of data for each relevant aspect of incident management.

Triage procedures and means of labelling must also be standardised. In this regard, different coloured 'smart tags' can be used to indicate the status of victims, recording non-medical data, photos and, where permitted, medical data in blockchain-protected files.

Improving the ICT resources used by emergency services would enhance the diagnostic and therapeutic capacity of medical first responders at the scene, and e-health technologies can be used to improve real-time clinical information on victims.

¹ ISO 22320:2018. Security and resilience-Emergency management-Guidelines for incident management.

In MCIs and disasters, a large number of victims need to be transferred to a hospital. Evacuations should be carried out according to agreed criteria or recommendations to homogenise the allocation of the resource and the destination of the victims in order to achieve the greatest benefit for the majority.

It is the professional and scientific societies competent in emergency medicine in the EU that should issue consensus and recommendations on triage, on-scene care and evacuation of victims in an MCI or disaster situation, thus promoting quality standards in line with current scientific evidence.

On the other hand, the development of regulations should be promoted to encourage the existence of integrated operational plans and procedures at pre-hospital and hospital level in MCI and disasters, which would maximise the effectiveness of the response.

The analysis and evaluation of MCI and disaster response is an element of the disaster cycle. Debriefing and the extraction of lessons learned are the basis for the improvement of the response to this type of situation, which is why they should be carried out in a standardised and systematic way.

4.2 Maintenance, logistics and deployment

The main objective of emergency logistics is to save lives as quickly as possible, and response time is considered an important measure of the success of disaster relief and the chances of survival of the affected population.

Large-scale disasters can affect large geographical areas and large populations and cause severe damage. In large-scale disasters, several organisations and countries need to work together to fulfil emergency response tasks.

It is important to harmonise logistical resources in disaster response to speed up decision-making and avoid unnecessary delays.

Some emergency services have to use outdated ICT, which affects their operational methods in MCI and disasters, especially in cross-sectoral and cross-border events.

In some cases, there are difficulties in establishing cross-border response plans due to inconsistencies in procedures, tools, information and monitoring systems.

Professionals need to be trained in disaster and crisis management to maintain the capacity of services involved in early response to MCI and disasters.

It is crucial to maintain resource control and inter-sectoral coordination, build the chain of command and control, and promote experience through exercises and drills to evaluate and improve the plans that have been made.

The SIGRUN platform, which enables improved communication, information sharing and tactical C2 services for first responders, seems to be an appropriate solution to improve transferability and information sharing. SIGRUN's tactical command and control services for first responders will consist of three subsystems: The data centralisation consists of a central database to which all devices of the FR team that can record and centralise data will be securely connected. The command and control application communicates with the first responders. This application collects and analyses information from the data centralisation subsystem on events, victims and

medical care, units and personnel, risk management and disaster management, and security. Multilingual communication application for communication, messaging and voice.

4.3 Command and control and support to operational decision-making

Command and control is a critical management function during all phases of emergency response. The emergency response command structure should be established before the emergency occurs. So there is no confusion about who is responsible for specified task, who reports to whom, what steps are needed to be done immediately. These are the questions that need to be clarified before the response begins. Command and control usually consist of analysing, deciding, directing and coordinating the whole incident.

All these steps need to be ensured by Incident Commander, the person responsible for all activities linked to the incident. Incident Commander is simply said responsible for the management of incident operations at the incident site.

The Incident Commander must be aware of and attentive to what is happening on scene at a particular time, with particular emphasis on the effect of changes in the incident; in effect, know how the incident is evolving. Incident Commander should know where first responders and other personal or resources are deployed at any time. The incident scene must be organized into zones according to the level of risk and the operational objectives pursued in each zone.

This is possible by establishing Emergency Response Coordination Centre. This Centre must have adequate means to perform command and control functions, including communications, hardware, and software to facilitate coordination, communications and decision-making. Very important fact is that this Centre need to have a unified command.

An effective operational communications network involving all teams deployed on scene is needed to be established within incident response planning. Information flow should be ensured, based on a communication network and on an adequate, effective, and secure flow of information that facilitates informed decision making and horizontal and vertical coordination. Only with effective usage of information and knowledge the disaster response can be successful.

As Incident Commander is the person in charge of the incident, all decisions made, are required to be continually reviewed and monitored so that appropriate response to the incident is ensured. Coordinating phase also includes an effective system for detection, communication and provision of logistical needs of all the resources deployed on the scene. Reporting is classified as very important part and is highly required that will provide a summary of aggregated incident information, easy to transmit and understand for emergency services, policy makers, public.

The last stage of the MCI after termination the emergency response to an incident is based on protocolized criteria and ensures that emergency resources are returned to their original location and status, orderly, safe and in efficient way.

4.4 Common operational picture and warning

In order to facilitate its approach and understanding, this task T5.4, Common Operational Picture and warning, has been divided into 2 sub-tasks focusing respectively on:

- Common operational picture
- Alert and warning

4.4.1 Common operational picture

Responding to an MCI or disaster will involve multiple first responders from different emergency services, with different operating procedures, different command organisation, different technical terminologies and even speaking different languages. To make the right decisions, emergency response organisations must share accurate and relevant information in a timely and seamless manner, providing them with a common operating picture that allows them to understand what is happening at any given moment.

The current reality is that communications in this context are still based on radio network solutions with very limited data transmission capacity. It is necessary to favour advances in the exchange of information in MCI and disasters through the application of new technologies such as cloud computing, big data analytics, the Internet of Things, or through the development of system architectures such as SIGRUN that enable the integration and linking of information, rapid access, availability over time, updating of information and standardisation of information. Systems based on network-centric working logic must be employed. Better networks can lead to better information feeding, better information leads to better response by emergency organisations, better actions lead to better results.

But, at the same time, it is necessary to work on the social aspect of information exchange and interpretation at individual, organisational, inter-agency and cross-national levels.

It is also essential to work on legal interoperability in a collaborative disaster response. Authorities and laws must stimulate information exchange between organisations through the implementation of organisational policies and guidelines.

The usual information exchange in these scenarios is usually vertical between organisations to a command centre, and horizontal information exchange should be facilitated intra and inter-organisations. The information exchange process should be simplified, as fewer steps mean fewer possible points of failure.

There is a fundamental need to develop a common basis of the different expertise of emergency personnel, from which to understand how the different actors interpret each other's needs and coordination requirements and interact with each other. A key challenge is to determine a minimum data set to be communicated during disasters, and the communication key flows must be defined.

Information that is not relevant to the situational awareness wastes time and is best filtered out to avoid unwanted 'noise'. Representation of the relevant information and the environment in the form of a common operational picture (COP), is crucial in establishing situational awareness and understanding for first responders and other stakeholders.

A COP is considered as a geographical representation combined with data that delineates the evolution of an emergency along with the characteristics and progress of emergency response operations. The information adapted in terms of content and detail is merged into a common frame of reference and displayed on a screen, supporting the response organisations' understanding of the current situation overview. It could include predefined mechanisms that, depending on the characteristics and evolution of the incident, facilitate decision-making on the issuance of alarms and warnings, as well as the identification of institutional enablers that facilitate the issuance of such alarms and warnings. In addition to information on what is happening/has happened, disaster response would require prediction of the future state of

what will happen, based on computational models. It could even provide advanced analysis functions, such as disaster modelling and simulation capabilities.

Relevant information for the COP must be identified. Information must be organised and validated, easy to search and relevant to decision-makers. It would require knowledge of each other's modus operandi, such as information needs, objectives, capacities, processes and resources.

It should be governed by harmonised terminology, both in vocabulary and symbols and in the recording, analysis and exchange of information. A multilingual option is desirable to support semantic and terminological interoperability in cross-border areas. The graphical representations and colour codes used in the COP should be defined and standardised.

COP structures must be able to combine static and dynamic information that is known to be needed in different scenarios. A viewer should allow to select the layers of information to display at any time in the COP, alone or in combination. It should allow ad hoc dashboards to be generated to assist C2, and automatic reporting at any stage of the incident.

The COP must always show the updated information. All the information shown by the COP must correspond to the suitable information, from the different sources of information integrated in a federated system like SIGRUN, with an efficient and secure connectivity, automatic refreshing, etc.

It would incorporate dynamic data from different sources, such as reconnaissance and surveillance assets, emergency response teams, sensors, etc. It should have high levels of automaticity in relation to data collection, processing and dissemination, relieving first responders of these tasks as far as possible.

COP should have standardised mapping, with customizable digital maps that include hazards, vulnerable objects and risk analysis results related to the different potential types of events. It should include real-time information on accident scene, focus, weather, traffic conditions, hospital capabilities, access routes, vehicles contact points, evacuation routes, vehicles tracking, first responders tracking, zonation, C2 and healthcare facilities deployment, victims (identification, location, triage, dynamic clinical condition), etc.

4.4.2 Alert and warning

The purpose of alerts and warnings is to provide the necessary information to warn the public and effect the necessary actions that will lead to their safety and to deliver the messages to populations at risk of imminent threats with the goal of maximizing the probability that people take protective actions and minimize the delay in taking those actions. Early warning is one of the main elements of disaster risk reduction. It prevents the loss of life and reduces the economical and material impacts of disasters. To be effective, early warning systems must actively engage communities at risk, facilitate public education and awareness of such risks, effectively disseminate messages and alerts and ensure ongoing preparedness.

Effective incident response needs a structured and pre-planned public warning. Public warning is based on two functions: hazard monitoring and warning dissemination. It is also necessary to establish a mechanism for risk identification, hazard monitoring, decision-making, warning dissemination, and to evaluate and improve. EU Civil Protection Mechanism brings together a total of 33 countries: 27 EU members States and 6 participants States (Norway, Iceland, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia and Turkey) This EU Civil Protection shares operational

challenges and similar approaches to managing disaster, while the structure and composition of emergency services varies considerably from country to country. Under the mechanism, countries stand ready and prepare to help each other when national resources for disaster response are overwhelmed or need to be reinforced. The EU's early warning and information systems help the Emergency Response Coordination Centre monitor hazards and events worldwide. Examples of hazards that the Centre monitors are earthquakes and tsunamis, tropical cyclones, volcanoes, droughts, floods, and forest fires. Alerts allow the Emergency Response Coordination Centre to provide a comprehensive early assessment.

An Integrated Public Alert and Warning System should be designed to provide rapid, reliable and effective communication to the public in case of major emergencies such as natural disasters. The network is designed to integrate various systems into one modern network, and also update them to take into account latest forms of communication such as cellular telephony and SMS, satellite and cable television, digital signal and the web.

Common form to communicate disaster is important in all different EU countries, and even so more in cross border incident. Alert and warnings must be standardized for all stakeholders.

"High priority public warning" refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property and this practice is not widespread. A warning issued from the authorities about an incident does not directly stimulate public action.

A technological approach is the great advantage in the development of alerts and warning systems. Adequate upgrading of the technological resources of emergency services and emergency operations centres would help promote early warning and the appropriate issuance and dissemination of alerts. The countries' alerting capabilities, will need to evolve and progress as the capabilities of smartphones and other mobile broadband devices improve and newer technologies become available. This evolution will need to be informed by both technical research and social and behavioural science research. Public response to alerts is both a social science phenomenon (their goal is to change public behaviour) and a technical phenomenon (technology is required for their dissemination). It is also an activity closely coupled to the practice of emergency management, which takes place primarily at the state and local level in UE countries. Technologists (including a wide set of subdisciplines such as human-computer interaction, computer networking, or wireless communications), social science researchers, and emergency managers have had few opportunities for ongoing interactions to consider current knowledge or gaps in our understanding, as well as to collaborate on beginning to fill those gaps.

In Summary, this report reviews the results of the analysis of the existing state of the art, and the analysis of surveys shared with other first responders, considers new possibilities for realizing more effective alert and warning systems, explores how a more effective supranational/national and regional alert and warning system might be created and some of the gaps in our present knowledge, and advance the alert and warning capabilities.

5. Identification of gaps

For the purpose of this deliverable D5.6 and of the VALKYRIES project, a gap is defined as the difference between the level of functionality which is required and the level of capability which is or will be provided.

For its part, the World Health Organization² defines an evidence gap map as the thematic evidence collection for a particular topic which can be used to identify key gaps in the evidence base which might require new research.

Throughout this document, the main source from which each gap has been identified has been characterised. Thus, the following sources will be differentiated:

- LITERATURE review: D5.5 state of the art and landscape, and others including the comparison of the plans and procedures to be applied in the use cases.
- SURVEY: First and second rounds of questionnaires: needs perceived by surveyed experts, data analysis.
- PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE of the researchers in the consortium and the EAB.

The gaps will be presented structured according to the tasks/sub-tasks of the WP5 of the VALKYRIES project. For each task/sub-task, a table with the identification of the gaps and a brief summary of the gaps is shown first. Then, in the text, each of the listed gaps is discussed in more detail.

5.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning

As in previous sections of this D5.6, for ease of approach and understanding, this task T5.1 has been divided into 2 subtasks focusing respectively on:

- Common operational picture
- Alert and warning.

5.1.1 Crisis response planning

G5.1.1-1: Lack of standardisation of terms and symbols for a common interpretation of data and a common operational picture.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.1-2: Standardisation of terms and symbols for a common understanding of the situation.

Disasters, as a result of both natural and anthropogenic factors, are becoming increasingly frequent. In addition to their frequency, also their impact is becoming higher and more extreme, regarding a coordinated response from heterogeneous organisations coming from different countries with different response procedures and cultures. To this direction, it is very essential, for the organisations engaging in first response, to implement procedures and protocols that will enable and facilitate the accomplishment of a common operational picture and situational awareness.

One crucial aspect that needs to be addressed, especially in the occasions of multi-casualty incidents which require the collaboration and coordination between several different first responders' agencies, as well as between professional and volunteering organisations, is the

² World Health Organization. WHO Guidance on Research Methods for Health and Disaster Risk Management. 2021. <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/345591/9789240032286-eng.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

adoption of a common process for the interpretation of data and information that is exchanged between the stakeholders. This could be achieved through the adoption and implementation of a standardised common terminology and symbology among first responders of the EU Member States. According to Sakkas et al. (2020), common symbology and terminology is one crucial gap to be covered by ongoing and future standardisation activities.

G5.1.1-2: Following of Guidelines of EU Civil Protection.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.1-5: Facilitating EU's Civil Protection Guidelines through a common federated system.

EU Civil Protection has issued a set of Guidelines and Best Practices procedures to help the EU Member State to harmonize their systems and agents involved in disasters. Such Guidelines are also supported by tools, such as earth observation of different types of disasters (such as wild fires or floods) as well as statistical data and time series on recorded disasters.

Based on those, member states of EU should synchronize their plans and systems accordingly. But, as far as all of those Guidelines and Tools are quite generic and difficult to be embedded into common practices, they can be used mainly as an indicator of gaps and discrepancies between different operational systems deployed in each country.

G5.1.1-3: Lack of regulatory harmonisation between countries in disaster planning and response.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.1-1: Regulatory harmonisation.

The European Union's European Civil Protection Mechanism brings together a total of 33 countries that share similar operational challenges and approaches to disaster management. They all maintain a similar structure in their civil protection system with different administrative levels of management and consider both risk assessment and emergency planning and response as relevant. In terms of planning, civil protection plans at the European level are standardised at the national level. In contrast, there is no such standardisation at the level of operational procedures.

Different EU countries have emergency services that vary in both structure and composition. At the level of health systems, there are important differences, with different organisations at the level of out-of-hospital health response.

These differences in structure and organisation make it very difficult for procedures to be homogeneous, which makes interoperability between services very difficult.

Interoperability between agencies involved in MCI or cross-border disasters could be improved by harmonising the legislation on which plans and procedures are based, and to guarantee a minimum level of standardisation between neighbouring countries and to act as a safeguard for entities involved in MCI response.

G5.1.1-4: Inconsistency of crisis response plans.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.1-3: Adequate revision and updating of emergency plans.

Planning is one of the most important functions of management. Crisis planning is one of the tools of crisis management. It is understood as the purposeful activity of the management entity, which, in the intentions of the specific goal and based on the available information, serves to

use the executive components in time and space so that the tasks are fulfilled with optimal use of material and financial resources. Crisis plans are used for crisis planning. In crisis plans measures are purposefully developed to solve a possible crisis situation in certain professional, spatial and temporal dimension.

The tasks of crisis plans are binding for all participating entities. Crisis plans make it possible to harmonize the requirements of all components of the IRS with the energy, material, financial, technical and personnel possibilities of the economy of the entire republic, possibly also of regions or specific cities and towns, complexes and buildings.

Various crisis plans are developed through different involved emergency agencies of MCI. As it comes from professional experience of first responders, most of those plans have been once prepared or developed without any additional revision or update. There is a significant need for requirement stated in law for revision and updating crisis plans regularly. Most of crisis plans are outdated and do not reflect actual situation.

G5.1.1-5: Lack of dissemination of emergency plans.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.1-4: Adequate dissemination and training in relation to emergency plans.

Emergency plans are the instruments that provide the organisational and functional framework and mechanisms for mobilising the necessary resources to protect people and property in the event of an emergency. They also establish how the different administrations involved in the management of a disaster should be coordinated.

Once the plans have been drawn up, they need to be implemented to ensure their proper application and effectiveness.

G5.1.1-6: Rescue Plans Activation Gap.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.1-7: C2 activation through a common federated system / COP.

As far as in each country there are different criteria in terms of casualties or geographical impact of disasters that signal the activation of crisis response plans and C2 procedures there are different criteria in terms of casualties or geographical impact of disasters between countries, it is more likely that in cross-border incidents influencing unproportionally the involved countries, activation of the crisis response plan, data sharing and C2 coordination might not be possible if the less influenced country has not been alarmed.

This could result both to catastrophic results, if the incident (for example a wild fire or a heat wave) grows expanding to the less prepared country for crisis response and C2 actions.

G5.1.1-7: Roles definition Gaps.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.1-6: Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system.

Definition of roles and their workflows/responsibilities between different agent within a country or between countries are inconsistent, following non well-structured common standards or best practices. Based on such role/workflow setup, different supportive (IT or logistics) systems have been tuned offering a certain level of operability.

As it is completely difficult to almost impossible to re-engineer such organizational and procedures setup within the scope of Valkyries project or the SIGRUN system, such inconsistency/gap can lead to the opportunity of a smoother re-engineering approach of such workflows/roles/responsibilities/privileges accessing to systems by leaving them as it is in the federated IT systems, linking them through more simple and realistic approaches such as COP and data sharing, as applicable.

Identification of gaps			
Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.1-1	Lack of standardisation of terms and symbols for a common interpretation of data and a common operational picture	Literature	There is no standardised glossary of terms, semantic representations or symbols sufficiently comprehensive to serve at EU level as a reference for planning, development, communications or operational actions in relation to MCIs and disasters.
G5.1.1-2	Following of Guidelines of EU Civil Protection	Survey	Harmonization towards acceptance, preparation and activation of EU's Civil Protection Guidelines is not achievable due to G1 and G1 above
G5.1.1-3	Lack of regulatory harmonisation between countries in disaster planning and response	Survey	Lack of harmonization between the law of different territories in relation to MCI and disaster planning or response.
G5.1.1-4	Inconsistency of crisis response plans	Professional experience	In Mass Casualty Incidents are all crisis response plans inconsistent between all involved emergency agencies. Most of the emergency plans were created but have not been updated many years. Plans are outdated and do not reflect nowadays situation.
G5.1.1-5	Lack of dissemination of emergency plans	Survey	Lack of implementation of civil protection plans: lack of dissemination, education of the population, education and training of those involved and development of operational procedures for action groups.
G5.1.1-6	Rescue Plans Activation Gap	Literature	As cross-border incidents might influence the involved countries unproportionally to their criteria, the activation of Crisis Management Rescue Plans as per their criteria might not signal the need for C2 handling from both

Identification of gaps			
Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			countries' emergency operations centres
G5.1.1-7	Roles definition Gaps	Literature	Different "role definitions" and privileges accessing data are in place between different federated systems. Such systems are tuned to support operations, workflows and procedure from such roles accordingly. Their gaps might create huge problems in data exchange between federated systems if a centralized approach is in force, resulting to non-operational systems

Table 4 – Gaps from crisis response planning

5.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage

G5.1.2-1: Different EMS structure and composition.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-1: Harmonisation of emergency services structure.

There is a great variability in the EMS, not only in terms of their structure but also in the functions that each first responder assumes. This variability does not only exist between different countries, since in some cases within the same country each region has its own EMS.

This leads to a huge diversity of emergency plans, operating procedures and chains of command, making it difficult to discriminate those who are responsible for making decisions according to the type of incident in which they are been involved.

Some of these differences between regional EMS are based on geographical dispersion, population density or wealth. This propitiates a greater or lesser concentration of human and material resources, which means a difficult homogenization of plans and/or procedures.

G5.1.2-2: Ununified procedures.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-9: Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system.

Depending on the particular country or region of a country, the human resources involved in an incident, whether as an EMS first responder or as a member of support teams, are quite different. The responders are very diverse, often including doctors, nurses, emergency technicians, paramedics, first responders, civil defence and other volunteers, firefighters, police, army forces, etc.

In the case of non-health professionals, their roles are very similar in different countries, but there is significant variability among members of health response systems depending on the type of response.

This variability makes it difficult to establish common procedures between countries. This is compounded by the fact that MCIs are specific, infrequent incidents where first responders must act quickly and accurately.

The lack of unified procedures makes smooth cooperation difficult; the more countries involved, the more difficult the situation becomes.

Technology and the use of federated systems are a good option to facilitate the homogenisation of procedures.

G5.1.2-3: Different professional competencies among first responders.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-2: Homogenisation of professional competencies in emergencies.

The capacity to administer specific medical care at the disaster site varies according to the professional profiles deployed at the emergency site and the professional competencies established by law in each country, e.g., presence or absence of physicians.

Thus, emergency services in some countries operate essentially with paramedics supervised by medical staff, with a "dispatching" type of demand regulation system. In this type of system, patients are systematically and urgently transferred to a hospital for definitive assessment and further care.

In other countries, such as Spain, the patient receives the urgently needed advanced care at the scene, while ensuring adequate continuity of care. In these cases, the personnel attending at the scene are technical, nursing and medical staff, and the response to the demand for care is usually decided by medical regulations.

G5.1.2-4: Lack of first responder's knowledge and preparation.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-12: Improving the first responders training.

The lack of preparedness of responders sometimes results in inadequate knowledge of procedures, access, use of PPE and safety measures, etc., which compromises the disaster response.

The fact of using several applications and that these applications are not fully integrated makes agile incident management more difficult, especially in a stressful situation.

In addition, if the applications are not easy to use from a usability point of view, it is difficult to update the information at the time of the intervention and it is easier to use more conventional and less technological ways.

The industry has the technology, but it must be useful at the time of the intervention and the professionals must be sufficiently trained.

Drills, certifications and training help, but there is still a gap between the knowledge of first responders and industry.

G5.1.2-5: Lack of common training and certification.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-13: Standardization of first responders training and certification in Europe.

The need of integrating and coordinating emergency care among diverse agencies must be emphasized. Usually, firefighters have provided emergency medical care and are typically well-equipped. Firefighters provide more emergency medical care in more than one country.

Police officers and firefighters are frequently the first professional witnesses to an acute illness or injury, arriving before EMS professionals. It is critical that these public officers be trained in basic life support (BLS) skills, as well as that there be training and close cooperation among professionals on the scene for rescue from crashed vehicles and safety at the scene. In Belgium and France, where the two emergency systems are commonly intertwined, fire service frequently substitute ambulance services, so that the fire fighters primarily provide BLS.

There is consensus that all mobile units of these services should be equipped with, at least, an automated external defibrillator and first responders to have a common level of training. At the moment, only four countries equip their police and firefighting vehicles with this life-saving equipment.

G5.1.2-6: Non-standardised zoning.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-4: Standardisation of terminology and criteria.

Zoning is an essential aspect in the management of multi-casualty incidents in order to properly and efficiently organise the response to the accident at the scene. However, the definition of working zones differs between the different agencies involved in the emergency according to the specific needs of the institutions: security, fire and rescue, health care.

At the health management level, the zones are called rescue or salvage area, relief area and base area. Other agencies use the designations red, yellow and green or hot, warm or cold to establish zoning. In addition to the different nomenclature used, the perimeters of these areas and the actions taken in each area by the different agencies do not coincide, which can make coordination difficult.

G5.1.2-7: Ambulances tracking and recording.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-11: Improving vehicles tracking.

Emergencies require continuous communication between the coordination centre, multiple field teams and their respective devices to function properly in adverse conditions.

Most of the communication technologies already implemented and known (for example, satellite, 4G / 5G) could become unusable and difficult to recover due to the collateral consequences of the disaster itself.

Providing reliable, high-quality communications during an emergency is critical to protecting life and property by responding to the emergency in the most practical way and effectively coordinating first responders (FRs) and other stakeholders on operations, reconnaissance and assessment teams.

Emergencies are often escalating and evolving events that require high performance and flexibility from emergency communications systems, including message prioritization,

communications automation, rapid message delivery, audit trail communications, security, interoperability and other features. Inadequate emergency communication skills can be uncomfortable at best and disastrous at worst.

More precisely, in emergency communication systems, communication between individual rescuers is achieved through dedicated analogue or digital terrestrial radio systems that cover small geographical areas and are typically used to transmit voice signals over a relatively short range (one tenth of a kilometre).

In general, communications between first responders and EOC are generally managed by dedicated digital radio systems capable of covering the entire state. This system is used to transmit voice signals, first responder position coordinates (estimated by GPS), first responder position coordinates (estimated by GPS) and, in some cases, low resolution still images of the emergency area.

When the vehicle leaves the station, the device may leave several minutes of incorrect instructions or no instructions. When the hospital administration can get the information of the arrival of the ambulance well in time and can increase the chance of survival of the patient as the time required for setting up basic components is done well in advance. This system can also be used for various other vehicles used in emergency situations.

G5.1.2-8: Non-standardised victim registration and affiliation information.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-5: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

One of the actions carried out in the health response to multi-victim incidents is the registration and affiliation of victims.

All victims must be labelled when they are first triaged in order to be able to track them throughout the care process (traceability). Once labelled, the triaged victim arrives at the advanced medical post where a person with the function of registration and affiliation registers their data (age range, sex, triage card number, colour given in the first triage, etc.).

The information and procedure for recording and exchanging information is not unified, so traceability in cross-border incidents or those involving different agencies is not guaranteed.

G5.1.2-9: Different triage standards and practices in use within countries between different first responders.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-7: Standardisation of triage procedures and means of triage tagging in MCI.

Due to the complexity of this type of incident, the professionals who arrive first on the scene are not always the ones with the best skills to perform the first activities such as triage. To this we could add that depending on the place where the event takes place, the people in charge of performing these functions are not always the same (paramedics, nurses, doctors...). In some cases (e.g. depending on the availability of the incident site, the complexity of the situation, the risk, etc.) medical personnel are not the first on the scene or it is dangerous for them to arrive at the incident site, and other first responders are responsible for triage.

The triage phase of emergency management is critical to minimising casualties.

However, there are differences not only in who should perform triage but also in how it should be done. Triage methods/procedures vary and are not the same in every country. This offers room for improvement and harmonisation.

There are many systems in the literature that introduce Information and Communication Technologies to achieve this, most of the time at high cost or requiring impractical interaction with the system that field staff refuse to do. However, the trend is that triage procedures can be supported by common and very low-cost technologies with minimal complexity in their interoperability between different support systems.

Gaps in functions and workflows and incompatibilities of functions, which are common among all countries also in triage procedures, can be corrected by adapting a more flexible scheme with certain basic key points.

G5.1.2-10: Non-standardized victim priority tagging.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-6: Standardisation of triage procedures and means of triage tagging in MCI.

Healthcare at multi-casualty incidents begins with the first triage. The purpose of triage is to establish the priority with which victims should be treated at the forward medical post depending on their severity and chances of survival.

Triage is a systematic process that must fulfil a number of premises in order to achieve its objective. One of these premises is that victims must be labelled so that all responders can recognise which victims have already been triaged and can be transferred to the advanced medical post.

This labelling of victims can be done in various ways: using coloured ribbons, painting on the victim's skin, using triage tags, entering the information on portable devices, etc.

The alphanumeric or colour codes that make visible the triage priority of the victims are not completely unified in the different emergency services, which makes the interoperability of different services difficult.

G5.1.2-11: Victims clinical information.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-10: Improving real-time victim's clinical information.

Decisions regarding the prioritisation and on-site treatment of individual victims at the scene of an MCI or disaster depend primarily on the clinical condition of each patient.

It is therefore essential to know the vital signs of the victims, not only at a single point in time but throughout the time they remain at the scene, bearing in mind that the clinical condition of a patient can change rapidly from one moment to the next.

Continuously monitoring the victim's health signs, including transport time to the medical facility and making this historical data available to the medical services is therefore of great importance for the response services.

And yet, the ability of these emergency services to have relevant real-time information on the clinical status of victims is still very limited at the present time because of the overall limitation in real-time information sharing capabilities.

G5.1.2-12: Non-consensual criteria for determining means and destination of transfer.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-8: Establishment of consensus and recommendations.

The final link in the chain of care in the health management of a multi-casualty incident is the evacuation and transfer of patients to a hospital when necessary.

Patients must be transported in the appropriate mobile resource depending on whether or not they need medical assistance during their evacuation to hospital. The regulations of the countries establish different types of ambulances depending on the provision of material and personal resources, so that depending on the needs of the patient, the transfer in one type of ambulance or another will be appropriate.

On the other hand, it should not be forgotten that MCI are characterised by incidents in which care capacities are exceeded, so it is common to have to prioritise which patients should be transferred in the advanced resources available at any given time.

In this sense, there are no consensus recommendations for deciding the form of evacuation in the MCI, which must be timely and appropriate to guarantee the quality of care, but taking into account the real availability of resources in each case.

On the other hand, deciding on the destination hospital for the victims is a key point in the management of an MCI. It ensures that patients receive the definitive treatment they need for their injuries, and that hospitals receive only those patients they can actually treat.

There are even different proposals as to what would be the most efficient way of transporting patients from the disaster area to the hospitals. At the disaster site, rescue, triage and basic emergency treatment are carried out according to the conventional method. After these measures have been completed, the options considered are:

- **Scoop & run:** minimise on-site interventions and proceed to the immediate transfer of the victims to the nearest hospital or medical centre, starting with the most seriously injured, with clinical stabilisation manoeuvres being carried out during the transfer to the hospital.
- **Stay & play:** establish on scene an advanced medical post where clinical stabilisation measures are applied to victims in situ before transfer to hospital, evacuating immediately only those who cannot be stabilised in situ, e.g., because they need urgent surgery.

Even sometimes, for example in disasters with a greater extent of damage and casualties, an intermediate evacuation centre may be established to which casualties are evacuated from the scene in the first instance. From this point, the selection of hospital destinations for patients is determined by the doctors and healthcare providers at this centre, which can allow more time to organise longer transfers, and a better distribution of casualties to different hospitals.

G5.1.2-13: Limited involvement of many hospital facilities in MCI and disaster response planning.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-3: Integrated pre-hospital and hospital MCI plans and operational procedures.

The management of an MCI involves an adequate distribution of casualties among the hospital centres to avoid overcrowding. However, there may be situations in which this saturation is unavoidable: massive number of victims, distance of the hospitals from the scene, care capacities, etc. And a non-controllable aspect is that victims who have not been attended by the emergency services may arrive at the hospitals. There are incidents in which victims who are fending for themselves go to the nearest hospital by their own means, or there are even victims who are taken to hospital by members of the public.

These situations make it necessary for hospitals to be prepared to receive and manage large numbers of patients.

In many cases the involvement of hospitals in the response to external MCIs is passive, limited to upgrading their capabilities at the request of the command centre in charge of the incident.

Ideally, however, hospitals should plan their response to this type of situation, taking into account the need for mechanisms to expand equipment, staffing and refurbish spaces to handle more than the usual number of casualties.

G5.1.2-14: Ununified standards for debriefing and evaluation.

Related opportunity: OP5.1.2-14: Debriefing and evaluation standardization in MCI and disasters.

Debrief is defined as a critical examination of a completed operation or exercise in order to evaluate actions – definition according to D2.2 Terminology and Semantics of VALKYRIES project. 2 types of debriefings are specified: cold debriefing and hot debriefing. Cold debriefing is a session held after some period of time has passed after an exercise or incident, several issues arise and stay overlooked during a hot debrief. Hot debriefing is a discussion held immediately after an exercise or incident to identify the strengths and weaknesses of plans, policies and procedures. Time for debriefing session after each accident or intervention is important for noticing what has been working well during the operation and what are the weaknesses that need an improvement during future operations.

At EU level there is EU's Civil Protection Knowledge Network which aims to strengthen the EU Civil Protection Mechanism in the areas of prevention, preparedness, and response to disasters. Knowledge network activities are as follows: training program, civil protection exercises, exchange of experts program, lessons learnt program, scientific advice and innovation, workshops and conferences, partnership facilitation opportunities.

According to VALKYRIES D6.1 Landscape of emerging preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration opportunities for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters in Spain there is a practice to have a hot debriefing – follow-up is carried out in real time by the heads of the catastrophic department and meeting is organized to summarize the important points for further improvement. In Portugal, after a drill, formal debriefing is conducted. In Bulgaria and Greece debriefing principles in any emergency incidents in the EMS are divided into different categories, according to the type and the size of an incident. Taking answers from the WP5 1st round survey into consideration and based on professional experience of EMS in Slovakia there is no common debriefing and evaluation of the intervention within the components of the integrated rescue system but also of the medical rescue service. The operational center of the emergency medical service, as the submitter of reports from MCI has an internal mechanism created, the procedure for which it collects, processes, analyzes and evaluates the course of the

event. In the case of deficiencies at the internal level, corrections are carried out, and in the case of deficiencies in other components, the deficiencies are forwarded to a specific component of the integrated rescue system. The operation center of the emergency medical service has a summary report from the event, an evaluation report and a data report from the DIS. The above text describes various methods used in various EU countries.

Identification of gaps			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.2-1	Different EMS structure and composition	Professional experience	The structure and composition of the Emergency Services varies considerably from country to country or region to region, which is a factor favouring a great diversity in chains of command and operational procedures.
G5.1.2-2	Ununified procedures	Professional experience	In each country, different types of actors as first responders, military and civilians, are involved with completely different approach as per their logistics and/or their C2, following operational procedures completely different between countries. Thus, their harmonization on common procedures is difficult to impossible.
G5.1.2-3	Different professional competencies among first responders	Professional experience	The capacity to administer specific medical care at the scene of a disaster varies according to the professional profiles deployed at the scene of the emergency and the professional competencies established by law in each country, e.g., presence or absence of physicians.
G5.1.2-4	Lack of first responders knowledge and preparation	Literature	The lack of preparedness of responders sometimes results in inadequate knowledge of procedures, access, use of PPE and safety measures, etc., which compromises the disaster response.
G5.1.2-5	Lack of common training and certification	Survey	There is no common training and certification at first responder level (EMS & Fire Service) in first aid. In some European countries for example the fire brigade can give first aid interventions/manoeuvres etc while in others not.
G5.1.2-6	Non-standardised zoning	Professional experience	Zoning is essential for organising the response to the accident on the scene. However, the definition of working zones differs between different agencies, in each case generally according to the specific needs of the institutions: security, firefighting and rescue, health care.

Identification of gaps			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.1.2-7	Ambulances tracking and recording	Professional experience	The vehicles arrive from different areas, not all ambulances have a GPS system that speaks to each other.
G5.1.2-8	Non-standardised victim registration and affiliation information	Literature	Victim registration and affiliation: information and the procedure of registering and exchanging victim's information is not unified, and traceability is not guaranteed in cross-border incidents or where different agencies work together.
G5.1.2-9	Different triage standards and practices in use within countries between different first responders	Professional experience	Not harmonized procedures in first triage and evacuation. First responders are unclear who is responsible for this task. In many EU countries these procedures vary. Detailed triage and first medical support to victims or short triage and fast evacuation - this is also challenging issue. In some countries, trained firefighters, coast guards or volunteers provide first stage triage, prior to the handling of the victim to EMS, in others not. The harmonization in cross-border incidents is difficult to impossible, mainly for victims with ethnics or citizenship that differs to the country's agent that rescued.
G5.1.2-10	Non-standardised victim priority tagging	Professional experience	Victim tagging: tapes, triage cards, wearables... The alphanumeric or colour codes that make the priority of victims visible are not completely unified.
G5.1.2-11	Victim's clinical information	Professional experience	Lack of clinical information based on patient condition
G5.1.2-12	Non-consensual criteria for determining means and destination of transfer	Literature	Evacuation and transfer: There are no agreed recommendations for deciding the means of evacuation in MCI, which must be timely and appropriate to ensure quality care, but taking into account the real availability of resources in each case.
G5.1.2-13	Limited involvement of many hospital facilities in MCI and disaster	Professional experience	Evacuation and transfer: in many cases the involvement of hospitals in the response to external MCIs is somewhat passive, limited to updating their capabilities at the request of the command centre in charge of the incident.

Identification of gaps			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
	response planning		
G5.1.2-14	Ununified standards for debriefing and evaluation	Survey	Standards and procedures between emergency agencies for debriefing and evaluation are not unified and connected

Table 5 – Gaps from reconnaissance and triage

5.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment

Managing large-scale disasters is extremely complex and there are many obstacles to overcome. In the event of a large-scale disaster, an immediate emergency response is required to save lives and limit and manage the damage.

Major disasters can have a significant impact on large populations as well as on different geographical areas. Therefore, emergency logistical responses are extremely complex and difficult. They include organising rescue operations and large-scale evacuations, deploying numerous resources, distributing these resources in a complicated way in a short time, etc. Moreover, these tasks are interrelated and cannot be done separately without considering how they affect each other. In addition, there are factors that are difficult to quantify, such as an unforeseen increase in local demand or damage to transport infrastructure.

For ease of approach and understanding, this section related to task T5.1 has been divided into 2 subsections focusing respectively on:

- Communications logistics
- Others logistics.

5.2.1 Communications logistics

G5.2.1-1: Communication needs.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-1: Improving communications.

The first urgent requirement is to establish a communication network for data collection and, more importantly, for the reliable exchange of information in real time between the actors in the emergency in all areas of the disaster management mission, such as prevention, protection, mitigation, response, and recovery. Normally, all pre-existing communication networks are down during a crisis, and the various responders are using different types of equipment. Rapid construction of a dependable, simply adaptable, resilient, interoperable, affordable, and secure network is necessary due to the urgency of the situation. At every level of a disaster, including the command centre and the rescue crew, wireless networks offer a promising communication infrastructure. Due to the sensitive, urgent requirement for information sharing in the chaotic spatial setting, security considerations are crucial.

G5.2.1-2: Outdated technology and system.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-6: Technological updating of emergency services.

Ensuring high-quality and reliable communications during an emergency is critical for responding to the emergency in the most viable way, saving lives and property through effectively coordinating first responders (FRs) with the remaining stakeholders in the operational, informational, and evaluative teams. Emergencies place demands on communication processes that are unique and very stringent. Emergencies often involve escalating and evolving events that demand high performance and flexibility from the emergency communication systems, such as message prioritization, automation of communication, fast message delivery, security, interoperability, and other capabilities.

In general, the identification of an emergency is announced by reporting an emergency situation addressed to the Emergency Operational Centre, which includes firefighters, police forces, ambulances, rescue services, mountain rescue services, marine and mine rescue services. Outdated technology and system are an issue maybe not in all countries within EU, but in some of them, definitely. Coming out from professional experience applications which are used by first responders are composed of various modules. In some cases, first responder's units do not use the same software applications. Modules need regular updates and should be interconnected. Hardware equipment (tablets, laptops, etc.) is outdated and more difficult to be used for interventions.

G5.2.1-3: Lack of portability.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-5: Improving portability.

Interoperability means different things to different users and under different circumstances. Ideally, systems should be able to efficiently exchange data without any loss of meaning or content, but in practice this is very difficult.

The lack of portability forces users of one service to learn the other service's application, or for the application and hardware system to integrate with the larger system. All command and control systems communicate with other systems using standard message sets. The "standard" message sets are not truly standard and not particularly efficient for transmitting all types of information. Many of the message standards were developed before multimedia applications became integrated into command and control systems. Each command and control system selected from several standard message sets, which meant that each command and control system use a different set. Interoperability through messages design limits interoperability for two reasons:

- Users are limited by message content,
- The information is only available when it is sent.

G5.2.1-4: Excessive use of radio communication.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-3: Technological updating of emergency services.

Radio networks are widely used for the different agencies who are part of emergency systems. These networks allowed the transmission of the information through voice and data, although occasionally this data can be transmitted only in a reduced way. In a MCI there is a big increase in the dispatch of messages related to the incident plus the usual activity of those networks thus

provoking an exponential increase of the communication flows. In this context key messages for the development of the incident could be lost and also the transmission of relevant information to the incident could be impossible or even cause severe mistakes for those involved in the specific MCI or in other events that are part of the normal activity of the emergency service including those related to cross-communications.

The availability of the possibility of digital data transmission is a main condition for the operation of COP and C2. Existing radio equipment will probably not meet the requirements for digital data exchange. It is necessary to look for a more universal and at the same time affordable solution.

- Option existing cellular network (GSM)
- Variant specialized cellular network (Terrestrial Trunked Radio, TETRA), connection with OP5.3-2 C2 self-adaptive network environment.
- Variant satellite communication terminals.

With each of the options, the question of protecting information from malicious access remains open.

In either embodiment, the essential digital data may be transmitted in alphanumeric form and in a format that allows both automated processing by a software system and human perception. An example of such a digital data distribution system is the AdatP-3 adopted by NATO armies, a standard for alliance use STANAG 5500. (Formatted Message Exchange in a Multinational Environment, [https://www.sto.nato.int/publications/STO %20Meeting%20Proceedings/RTO-MP-IST-055/MP-IST-055-02.pdf](https://www.sto.nato.int/publications/STO%20Meeting%20Proceedings/RTO-MP-IST-055/MP-IST-055-02.pdf), accessed Aug 2022; Information Exchange in Support of C2-Interoperability, <https://apps.dtic.mil/sti/pdfs/ADP010865.pdf>, accessed Aug 2022).

It is also linked to G5.2.1-6, G5.3.1-12.

G5.2.1-5: Use of non-optimal alternative communication channels in MCI.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-4: ICT technological updating of emergency services.

In the EU environment, emergency services routinely use radio networks with voice information transmission for communications, mainly operational but also to a large extent tactical or even strategic.

Although these solutions are secure and extensively tested in these contexts, and although they are capable of transmitting information simultaneously to groups and even data, they have very limited data transmission capacity. They are often insufficient to provide all the information needed to build a common operational picture to understand the dynamics of the disaster and make the best decisions at any given time.

Given these limitations, and as a complement to them, emergency services also use mobile and fixed telephone networks for both strategic and operational communications.

However, these networks have significant limitations in the exchange of information, which is vital between the different agencies involved in MCI or disaster management.

Disaster managers should share their tools and information as necessary.

G5.2.1-6: Usage of different software within emergency services.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.2-2: Homogenisation of logistical resources in disaster response.

Different and not unified software used for emergency service – first responders – cause that the communication between operator within system can lead to either misunderstanding or losing important information about incident (about victims, affected area, injured people, damages, rescue operations, etc.). Incident commander is the person in charge of the whole incident and communicates with the EOC and also with other commanders on site (medical commander, security commander, search and rescue commander, logistic commander). Since the software they use is not fully compatible, there is a real possibility that Incident Commander communicated hardly with all involved persons and agencies in MCI.

For example when we summarize Use case 2 (Cross-border response to the disaster containing the spreading of toxic substances on the simulated border between Slovakia and Italy) at Slovak site FRs communicate via CoordCom (for EOC), GINA (for FRs) and also internal software in radio stations, at Italian site FRs communicate via Beta 80 – Emma. This clearly identifies inconsistency at cross-border but also at national level. There is a huge space for improvement in this field. As it is well known, change of software or hardware in any kind of environment, is associated with high financial costs.

G5.2.1-7: Limited use of e-health options in MCI and disasters.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-6: Technological e-health updating of emergency services.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) defines eHealth as the cost-effective and safe use of information and communication technologies in support of health and health-related fields, including medical care, health monitoring and health education, knowledge and research.

As reported by Norris T et al³, although e-health technologies such as cloud computing, big data analytics or the internet of things, which are currently revolutionising the standard healthcare is beginning to deploy regarding disaster management, there is little systematic use of e-health tools in disaster medicine. Moreover, first responders are rarely trained in these technologies, let alone become proficient in their use.

G5.2.1-8: Operating procedures conditioned by obsolete ICTs.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-2: Technological updating of emergency services.

The operational procedures of the emergency services for MCI and disaster management include a section on communications. These procedures should establish which communications channels will be used in these cases, who should use them and how. In many cases, these communications systems are obsolete and out of date, which is a constraint on the procedures themselves. This situation forces services to devote excessive effort and resources to these purposes to the detriment of the effectiveness of victim care.

³ Norris T, Gonzalez J, Parry D, Scott R, Dugdale J, Khazanchi D. (2018). The Role of e-Health in Disasters: A Strategy for Education, Training and Integration in Disaster Medicine. Journal of the International Society for Telemedicine and eHealth. 6. 10.29086/JISfTeH.6.e2. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331126806_The_Role_of_e-Health_in_Disasters_A_Strategy_for_Education_Training_and_Integration_in_Disaster_Medicine

G5.2.1-9: Recording information sometimes make it difficult for first responders to do their job.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.1-7: Simple and usable solutions that make the first responder's job easier.

The command-and-control system that records information from an MCI or disaster must be fed by the various responders, each at their own level of action.

The way in which information is entered into the system determines its effectiveness. In cases where information must be entered by voice or manual data entry, this task is more laborious, placing a significant burden on first responders. It also limits the fluidity and even the accuracy of the data entered.

It is therefore necessary to adopt simple and usable solutions that make it easier for first responders to enter the data deemed necessary into the C2 system without this action affecting their other actions.

Identification of gaps			
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.1-1	Communication needs	Survey	Experiencing communication difficulties between the other various technical actors
G5.2.1-2	Outdated technology and system	Professional experience	In common - most emergency agencies (Firefighters, EMS,...) face the problem that technology and systems are outdated
G5.2.1-3	Lack of portability	Literature	The lack of portability force users of one service to learn the other service's application, or for the application and hardware system to integrate with the larger system
G5.2.1-4	Excessive use of radio communication	Professional experience	Radio networks with voice information transmission are widely used, but have limited data transmission capacity, which is insufficient to build a common operational picture for disaster assessment and decision-making. In general the first responder are provided with radio communication, which means that they become saturated and errors can be made in the transmission of message

Identification of gaps			
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.1-5	Use of non-optimal alternative communication channels in MCI	Literature	Given the limitations of radio networks, the alternative use of mobile and fixed telephone networks for strategic and operational communications makes it difficult to exchange information with other responders in MCI or disasters.
G5.2.1-6	Usage of different software within emergency services	Professional experience	Not all emergency services use the same software - therefore the communication between operators within the system could lead to losing some important information about the whole incident or particular part of it.
G5.2.1-7	Limited use of e-health options in MCI and disasters	Literature	Limited use of e-health technologies, which are currently revolutionising standard healthcare, in MCI and disaster response.
G5.2.1-8	Operating procedures conditioned by obsolete ICTs	Professional experience	The obsolete communication systems available to some emergency services condition their own operational procedures, forcing them to devote excessive efforts and resources to these purposes, to the detriment of the effectiveness of victim care.
G5.2.1-9	Recording information sometimes make it difficult for first responders to do their job.	Literature	The need to enter information into the C2 system by voice or by manual typing of data places a significant burden on first responders and limits the fluidity and even accuracy of the data.

Table 6 – Gaps from communication maintenance, logistics and deployment

5.2.2 Others logistics

G5.2.2-1: Lack of standardisation of logistical procedures.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.2-3: Establishment of consensus and recommendations.

Logistics is the only way to manage a supply chain of emergency items efficiently to cope with catastrophic events. Unfortunately, there are no standard models for using supply chain management techniques to provide aid and assistance to people affected by disasters.

Supply chain management planning is mainly carried out in the preparedness and response phases of an emergency, with the development of immediate response procedures, the design

and installation of emergency response systems, and the development and implementation of emergency preparedness and response plans.

G5.2.2-2: Lack of inter-agency logistics procedures.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.2-1: Establish cross-border operational plans and procedures.

At the EU level there are recommendations and guidelines to properly set up logistics in MCI and disasters. These guidelines allow individual countries to draft and implement their logistics, maintenance and deployment procedures.

The survey conducted in the development of Work Package 5 of the Valkyries project shows that there is a high degree of implementation of procedures, including standardisation of procedures, but there are no unified inter-agency maintenance, logistics and deployment procedures for crisis response.

G5.2.2-3: Insufficient logistics management tools at the national level.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.2-4: Improve national disaster planning and response logistics tools.

There is a good interlinkage of EU and UN-managed logistics, but there are shortcomings in the tools to support pre-disaster logistics planning in individual countries.

New technologies can be used to improve logistics in disasters. Organisations can improve decision-making, increase the speed of relief operations and achieve better coordination of relief activities by taking a number of actions. These actions include establishing a communication mechanism in remote geographic areas without internet or telephone networks, implementing up-to-date information or monitoring systems, and using humanitarian logistics software that can provide real-time information on the supply chain.

There are four main developments to consider in this regard: barcodes, AMS laser cards, radio frequency tags and internet satellite services.

G5.2.2-4: Variability in logistics resources for disaster response.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.2-2: Homogenisation of logistical resources in disaster response.

The capabilities of different countries and agencies to cope logistically with MCIs or disasters are heterogeneous.

There is much variability in the availability of deployment support elements as highlighted in the survey conducted in the development of Work Package 5. The availability of elements such as communications vehicles, logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tagging systems, personal protective equipment needed for specific risk incidents or facilities to establish an advanced medical post is not predominant.

On the other hand, the survey conducted shows that there are items for which there are procedures in stock in relation to MCIs or disasters. These items are lists of medical supplies, sanitary equipment, medicines, food and water, petrol, electrical power and power supplies or communication equipment to be used at the scene.

G5.2.2-5: Insufficient and non-standardised training in logistics applied to MCI and disasters.

Related opportunity: OP5.2.2-5: Strengthen logistics expertise.

In order to maintain the level of capacity of services involved in first response to MCI and disasters, it is necessary for staff to be trained in disaster and crisis management.

It is important to maintain control of resources, coordination between different areas, that the chain of command and control is defined and that experience is promoted through exercises and drills to verify and improve the plans developed.

The EU is trying to achieve standardised formal education, but so far it is a challenge.

The questionnaire developed during this work package highlights the need for training in logistics, maintenance and deployment, with the need to create and maintain a coordinated level of specialised training for each country.

Identification of gaps			
Others maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.2.2-1	Lack of standardisation of logistical procedures	Professional experience	Logistics and health deployment procedures are not standardised in MCI or disasters.
G5.2.2-2	Lack of inter-agency logistics procedures	Survey	There are no unified inter-agency crisis procedures for logistics, maintenance and deployment.
G5.2.2-3	Insufficient logistics management tools at the national level	Literature	There is a good interlocking of logistics managed by the EU and the UN, but there are deficiencies in the tools to support pre-disaster logistics planning in the different countries.
G5.2.2-4	Variability in logistics resources for disaster response.	Survey	The availability of certain deployment support elements such as communications and logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tags, PPE or facilities to set up an advanced medical post is inconsistent.
G5.2.2-5	Insufficient and non-standardised training in logistics applied to MCI and disasters	Survey	Despite EU recommendations for standardised formal education in humanitarian logistics, specialised training needs to be coordinated for each country.

Table 7 – Gaps from others maintenance, logistics and deployment

5.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making

G5.3.1-1: Not a unique C2 emergency operations centre operating in all countries.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-16: Hybrid Digital Twins as a C2 tool.

In most cases, different C2 non-compatible emergency operations centres operate even within the same country to support/manage police, health or firefighters/first responders through their supportive IT and communication systems.

As so, different "operational view" is available to each C2, resulting to mismanagement or not proper execution of the rescue plan. The same stands for cross-border incidents.

Such lack of common view is related with:

- The different origin or background of each agent: some are military oriented whilst others are not.
- The differences in time synchronization between supportive systems.
- The gaps of tactical (sharable) information between systems.
- The different logistics and support system each agent is using in its FR operations.
- Different symbols, colours and other standards indicating crucial/non-crucial information as defined between different agents.
- Different training of FR based on the capabilities of each C2 of the agent.

As so, there is not really a common operational picture, COP, within a country. The same stands in cross-border incidents where there is no common view of COP related to critical-tactical information that needs to be exchanged in order to help/synchronize FRs in cross-border incidents.

G5.3.1-2: Different crisis emergency operations centre locations.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-5: Define criteria for C2 facilities location.

Crisis Emergency Operations Centres (EOC) for both medical and non-medical organisations participating in an emergency actuation are commonly placed in different locations. These places can be far apart, especially in incidents that have a considerable geographical extension, such as a forest fire.

This distance introduces difficulties for establishing an effective communication between intervening organisations, where technical adversities such as constrained communication resources could difficult or even disrupt the decision-making management tasks provided by command post leaders.

Based on that, there is a need for defining robust solutions that ensure that communication is stable and allow an effective emergency management.

G5.3.1-3: Lack of integration of certain emergency services in the emergency operations centre.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-3: Integration of all emergency services into a single emergency operations centre.

In the EU, Member States are committed to ensuring that emergency communications to the single European emergency number 112 are answered and handled in a way that is most appropriate to the national organisation of emergency systems and within the technological possibilities of the networks. The European Parliament's resolution (5 July 2011) on universal service and the 112 emergency number already highlighted the importance of better coordination between emergency agencies, both at national, cross-border and EU level, to

achieve the highest level of efficiency and, to this end, calls on the Commission to support and coordinate with Member States' administrations to explore ways to improve interoperability between their systems.

The report *Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union* (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2008)⁴ investigated the formal role of EMS in the national crisis management system, analysing whether EMS is an integral part of the top level of each state's Incident Command and Control (MCI) structure.

Less than half of the countries incorporated a specific representative of this essential emergency function at their highest level of decision-making, despite the fact that most of these countries have a legal and structural framework in crisis management and response that assigns a specific role to EMS in the national or sub-national Crisis Response Plan.

The survey conducted in the development of Work Package 5 of the Valkyries project confirms that the availability of emergency coordination centres in the EU territories for emergency response is almost constant, but that it does not always effectively cover all agencies and levels involved in emergency response, which becomes particularly important when the emergency and response are more complex, such as in the case of MCIs or disasters. Coordination of different institutions and between different regions is therefore one of the major problems when managing incidents of a certain magnitude.

G5.3.1-4: Municipality supportive agents excluded from C2.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-4: Municipality supportive agents engagement.

In most cases, Municipalities or Cities are engaged incidents as supportive/ logistics/deployment of first aid to non-casualties assistance based on specific civil protection plans issued and authorized by their Administrative Authority. In order to fulfil this role, municipalities or cities have different deployment or logistics standards and technological/telecommunication capabilities to use. In some cases, their assets or resources are under the command of other agents (such as Fire Department or Police or EMS accordingly) whilst in most cases there is no synchronization with neighbouring municipalities or cities that can provide FR support.

The opportunity of SIGRUN is it include Municipalities or Cities as agents with their own COP, provided by SIGRUN accessibility as per G5.3.1.1, assuming that they can log as agents with their available supportive systems.

G5.3.1-5: Heterogeneous emergency systems in different territories.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-6: Harmonisation of procedures.

EMS covers a broad range of health services such as primary care personnel and facilities, first aid posts, volunteer organizations, private medical services etc.

The *Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union* report (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2008)⁵ showed that EU countries have a similar crisis management system but the

⁴ Davoli E et al. *Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union: Report*. WHO Regional Office for Europe. 2008. https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0016/114406/E92038.pdf

⁵ Davoli E et al. *Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union: Report*. WHO Regional Office for Europe. 2008. https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0016/114406/E92038.pdf

structure and composition of their EMSs are different, with command or operational coordination roles differing more or less substantially from each other. Evidence of the value of different emergency delivery models, such as tiered levels of response, economic effectiveness of type of EMS system, and deployment of different types of health-care providers, is either non-existent or inconclusive.

In addition, firefighters have traditionally provided emergency medical care outside the hospital. In Belgium and France, where the two emergency systems are often intertwined, firefighters routinely replace ambulance services, so that first responders largely provide BLS.

The heterogeneity in the organisation of out-of-hospital medical emergency care hinders the homogeneity of procedures, inter-institutional dialogue and the effective exchange of information between agencies or territories, more accentuated when dealing with highly complex emergencies such as MCIs or disasters or with cross-border involvement.

G5.3.1-6: Different criteria for assigning roles in different territories.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-1: Harmonisation of emergency services command competencies among the different EU countries.

Civil Protection recommendations on planning establish in a more or less homogeneous way the tasks to be attended to and the roles to be established to ensure an adequate response to the disaster. But these roles are not always assigned to the same services in the different plans.

As noted in the report Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2008)⁶, although rescue and first-line medical care to victims is the primary objective of all emergency services in a disaster, the role of EMS in the EU appears marginalized in the coordination and command framework.

G5.3.1-7: Linear plans and positive control not thriving in complex situations.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-2: C2 self-adaptive network environment. Current C2 systems are not flexible in multidisciplinary environments and are very susceptible to changes due to complex situations.

Typically, each first responder has its own C2 system, the C2 systems themselves are not integrated and information is not shared across applications.

As a matter of fact, not having the data digitized and not being able to share the information makes the operation very difficult.

Linear plans and positive control do not thrive in complex situations and systems must be adapted and operational to reflect this complexity.

G5.3.1-8: Difference in overall incident command in the emergency operations centre.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-7: Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.

⁶ Davoli E et al. Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union: Report. WHO Regional Office for Europe. 2008. https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0016/114406/E92038.pdf

Civil protection tasks have traditionally been the responsibility of states, and within states, in many cases, of regions or decentralised institutions, often posing problems of coordination and efficient use of resources.

The ultimate national authority for MCI or disaster response, as shown by the results included in deliverable D5.1 of the Valkyries project, varies in the different EU Member States. Civil Protection (administratively dependent on a state or sub-state entity) or fire brigades generally are responsible for the overall command of the disaster response.

On some occasions when national security is compromised, this overall command may shift to other agencies of the Ministry of the Interior, Defence or law enforcement agencies.

The growing realisation that a large number of disasters do not respect state borders and therefore need to be addressed in a more comprehensive manner has led to some steps being taken in recent years towards coordination and the development of cross-border cooperation arrangements in this field.

G5.3.1-9: Difference in overall incident command at the scene.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-7: Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.

Following on from the analysis of the results of the surveys conducted in the course of Work Package 5 of the Valkyries project regarding the allocation of different command and control functions in crisis response in EU Member States, it is clear that there is great variability in relation to which agency has overall command at the scene of an IMC or disaster response: Fire Brigade, Security Forces, Civil Protection....

G5.3.1-10: Difference in hazard control and zoning command.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-7: Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.

Along the same lines as discussed for gaps G5.3.1-8 and G5.3.1-9, the results of the surveys conducted in the course of Work Package 5 of the Valkyries project concerning the allocation of the different command and control functions in crisis response in the EU Member States show that the agency responsible for hazard control and zoning may be firefighters, civil protection or even police, depending on different plans and territories.

G5.3.1-11: Difference in rescue command.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-7: Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.

Following on from the analysis carried out in the description of gaps G5.3.1-8, G5.3.1-9 and G5.3.1-10, the surveys carried out in the course of Valkyries work package 5 on the allocation of different command and control functions in EU crisis response also show that there is variability in who has overall on-scene rescue command in response to an MCI or disaster: it can be firefighters, EMS, or even some police units (e.g., mountain group of the Guardia Civil in Spain).

G5.3.1-12: Complexity of C2 information flows.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-8: Simplify information flow.

C2 information used by the entities can be different depending on the functions and needs each C2 system is designed to provide and to support. The C2 information flow is also related to each C2 system, however despite the technical differences, a generic sequence is usually applied defined as OODA: 1) OBSERVE - Data gathering 2) ORIENT - data analysis and generating situational intelligence and awareness 3) DECIDE - Decision making processes, generating actions scenario, assessment of capacity and capability resources; 4) ACT – assign actions and responsibilities. The gap is that each entity holds different processes, and the information flow supporting each of these phases of OODA, may be based on different principles thus making the process integration complex. Therefore, the C2 information shared should be simple and procedure independent, allowing each entity to manage their processes independently.

On the other hand, communications solutions in multi-casualty incident response are currently still primarily based on radio network solutions with voice information transmission. Although they are capable of transmitting information simultaneously to groups and even data, they have very limited data transmission capacity with little networking capability.

The classic command and control model is highly vertical and hierarchical. In order to pass through all instances of the chain deployed on site and reach the emergency operations centres, the operational procedures for the transmission of both operational and command and control information is highly complex in these contexts.

In addition to being an overload of effort that detracts from other tasks such as damage control or assistance to those affected, they are insufficient to provide all the information necessary to build a common operational picture that allows for understanding the dynamics of the disaster and making the best decisions at any given moment, causing slowdowns and a greater likelihood of errors.

G5.3.1-13: Legacy C2 applications.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-10: Technological updating of emergency services.

Organisations tend to coexist with technology that has been acquired or developed long time ago, since their functionality is often enough for their daily usage. In this sense, most C2 applications become obsolete as they do not tend to be updated to bring their functionality up to date, the technologies in which they have been developed, or even to provide support for newer versions, as it is the case of the software libraries required for their usage. Based on that, these applications typically present an important lack of interoperability and extensibility capabilities.

G5.3.1-14: Interoperability C2.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-11: Facilitating C2 interoperability through a common federated system.

Interoperability is defined as the ability of systems, personnel, and equipment to provide and receive functionality, data, information, and/or services to and from other systems, personnel, and equipment, between both public and private agencies, departments, and other organizations, in a manner enabling them to operate effectively together.

The European IDIRA project⁷, Interoperability of data and procedures in large-scale multinational disaster response actions, noted that there is a lack of disaster management procedures, tools and systems in the European Union that fully take into account the specific characteristics and requirements for large-scale international cooperation in MCI or disaster situations. In these situations, many diverse emergency response organisations need to collaborate across technological systems, organisational boundaries and cultural and language barriers. They do not have the same prior knowledge and come at different times. Technologies and procedures currently used in multinational disaster response and previous EU-funded projects have provided many solutions for individual aspects, but there is not yet a concept available to support the whole process.

G5.3.1-15: Communication delays among the interveners.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-12: Improving communications.

Due to the differences between the technologies currently used by the different FRs, in some cases it is not possible to make a direct translation between them. For this purpose, a person is usually employed whose purpose is to carry out this information transfer. Because of this, the information exchange time is limited to that person's capacity for information transmission. This slowing down of the information exchange makes it impossible to create a system for obtaining information in real time.

G5.3.1-16: Lost Communications and their logs.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-13: Blockchain "logbooks".

In a federated environment the exploitation of the data for post mission analysis and auditing as well as to ensure proper coordination during operations, the system status and exchanged data should be logged. The lack of a common log function renders the federation system with lack of trust and difficulties to ensure data logged consistency, replicability and reliability. A decentralize log facility and backups enables the store and maintenance of the systems log. Such function should also enable a high level of security and data protection.

As there is not any existing common logging system of communications, messages or transactions between operators of the same C2, it is likely that crucial data can be lost, especially in cases where auditing is required to support victim cases in courts. For this purpose, the blockchain supported logging mechanism of transactions and metadata in the SIGRUN core system, is the best opportunity to resolve a lot of problems related with security, transparency of logged information. This function needs to support "store and forward" mechanisms, in case communications are lost.

G5.3.1-17: Time synchronization gap.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-14: Facilitating synchronisation through a common federated system.

In a federated approach, the different systems and applications used remain independent from the others. Each entity is responsible for the data produced. In order to have a time coherency

⁷ IDIRA EU project. Interoperability of data and procedures in large-scale multinational disaster response actions. 2015. https://cordis.europa.eu/docs/results/261/261726/final1-idira_project_summary_final_report_public_part_2015-10-09.pdf

between of data generated by each source and that the data consumer can clearly establish the data timeline, the reference time cannot be independent. So, there is gap as each entity and its application have their own time reference which may be different from the other federated entities time reference, leading to information inconsistency, procedures and processes not correctly sequenced.

G5.3.1-18: Lack of C2 education and training.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-9: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

Joint workflows between the FRs' C2 systems are not standardised. Currently, FRs are specialised in the use of specific C2 systems for their operations, which differ from one agency to another.

FR training systems for the use of new systems or technologies are a step forward in improving effectiveness in real use cases.

However, there are currently no training systems for FRs to facilitate this task, nor are there methodologies to educate FRs who are not familiar with the technologies used. Therefore, when implementing a new system, the transition and learning time is long.

G5.3.1-19: Very limited capacity for ex-post analysis in C2.

Related opportunity: OP5.3-15: Facilitating research through a common federated system.

Limited capacities and lack of interoperability between procedures, technologies and platforms for information exchange between emergency services not only compromise adequate situational awareness and thus adequate decision-making in emergency response. Problems in recording, storing and interpreting relevant data throughout the disaster response also condition the possibilities for learning from the analysis of information.

The information that is currently recorded in relation to command and control decisions or operational actions is very limited, and that which is recorded in real time does not generally associate data that would make it possible to determine the justification, origin, timing, etc. This makes it practically impossible to carry out a complete objective analysis of the incidents in order to obtain useful and contrasted information.

Identification of gaps			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-1	Not a unique C2 emergency operations centre operating in all countries	Professional experience	In most cases, different C2 non-compatible emergency operations centres operate even within the same country to support/manage police, health or firefighters/first responders. As so, different "operational view" is available to each C2, resulting to mismanagement or not proper execution of the rescue plan. The same stands for cross-border incidents

Identification of gaps			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-2	Different crisis emergency operations centre locations	Survey	For Medical and non-medical organizations the crisis emergency operations centres (EOC) are located in different places. It could be an issue because currently there are limited resources in terms of communication and may difficult decision-making management task by Command Post Leaders.
G5.3.1-3	Lack of integration of certain emergency services in the emergency operations centre.	Survey	In some countries, emergency operations centres do not integrate all emergency services, which can delay the provision of incident information and make coordination between services difficult.
G5.3.1-4	Municipality supportive agents excluded from C2	Professional experience	During disasters, municipalities or cities are engaged in first respond agents, mainly as logistics or supporting agents. In some countries they are included with such roles in emergency plans, in others not. There is a gap that need to be faced as municipality's local C2s usually are not included or communicate properly with C2
G5.3.1-5	Heterogeneous emergency systems in different territories	Literature	EU countries have a similar crisis management system but the structure and composition of their EMSs are different, with command or operational coordination roles differing more or less substantially from each other. This hampers the homogeneity of procedures, inter-agency dialogue and the effective exchange of information.
G5.3.1-6	Different criteria for assigning roles in different territories	Literature	Civil Protection recommendations on planning establish in a more or less homogeneous way the tasks to be attended to and the roles to

Identification of gaps			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
			be established to ensure an adequate response to the disaster. But these roles are not always assigned to the same services in the different plans.
G5.3.1-7	Linear plans and positive control not thriving in complex situations	Literature	Current C2 Systems are not flexible in multidisciplinary environments and highly susceptible to changes due to complex situations.
G5.3.1-8	Difference in overall incident command in the emergency operations centre.	Survey	There are differences regarding overall incident command at the emergency operations centre in the response to an MCI or disaster: it may be firefighters or civil protection.
G5.3.1-9	Difference in overall incident command at the scene.	Survey	There is a lot of variability in relation to which agency has overall on-scene command in the response to an MCI or disaster.
G5.3.1-10	Difference in hazard control and zoning command	Survey	The agency responsible for hazard control and zoning may be firefighters, civil protection or even police, depending on different plans and territories.
G5.3.1-11	Difference in rescue command	Survey	There is variability in who has overall on-scene rescue command in response to an MCI or disaster: it can be firefighters, EMS, or even some police units (e.g. mountain group of the Guardia Civil in Spain).
G5.3.1-12	Complexity of C2 information flows	Professional experience	The flow of both operational and command and control information with the current systems that support it is often too complex, leading to slowdowns and increased likelihood of errors.
G5.3.1-13	Legacy C2 applications	Survey	In common - outdated technology and systems

Identification of gaps			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.3.1-14	Interoperability C2	Survey	Interoperability issues. Integrated informational and GIS systems that will interact with all stakeholders are not configured and deployed.
G5.3.1-15	Communication delays among the interveners.	Literature	There are delays among the interveners in the process of information acquisition, communication and decision-making.
G5.3.1-16	Lost Communications and their logs	Professional experience	As there is not any existing common logging system of communications, messages or transactions between operators of the same C2, it is likely that crucial data can be lost, especially in cases where auditing is required to support victim cases in courts.
G5.3.1-17	Time synchronization gap	Professional experience	Logging of events or transactions with no time synchronization might create problems in auditing procedures
G5.3.1-18	Lack of C2 education and training	Professional experience	Joint workflows between C2 systems are not standardised and often require the support of training programmes, which are often insufficient.
G5.3.1-19	Very limited capacity for ex-post analysis in C2	Literature	The information that is currently recorded in relation to command and control decisions or operational actions is very limited, and that which is recorded in real time does not generally associate data that would make it possible to determine the justification, origin, timing, etc. This makes it practically impossible to carry out a complete objective analysis of the incidents in order to obtain useful and contrasted information.

Table 8 – Gaps from command and control and support to operational decision-making

5.4 Common Operational Picture and warning

As in previous sections of this D5.6, for ease of approach and understanding, this task T5.4 has been divided into 2 subtasks focusing respectively on:

- Common operational picture.
- Alert and warning.

5.4.1 Common Operational Picture

G5.4.1-1: Legal constraints to interoperability.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-1: Regulatory harmonisation

The ability of organisations to access, obtain, maintain and apply information and knowledge in common with other organisations is a key capability required for disaster and emergency response, analysis and management.

Despite its importance, this capability is constrained by a number of technical, organisational, cultural and legislative barriers that substantially limit interoperability between technologies and information sharing platforms in C2, and which are generally difficult for individual agencies to address.

There is a legal dimension to the exchange of information that stems from the need to protect the privacy and confidentiality of those affected, and which substantially conditions the exchange of information between organisations involved in the disaster response.

Different jurisdictions and different countries are likely to have different legislation, and even different interpretations of the same laws, on privacy and data protection

G5.4.1-2: Insufficient awareness of information exchange between agencies and territories.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-2: Fostering a culture of information exchange

Different organisations participating in an emergency have limitations in establishing effective communication with other participants. This may be due to political reasons or factors associated with the organisational culture. Apart from these reasons, it is essential to ensure that these organisations can transmit relevant information to other services intervening in the situation in order to ensure the success of the operations, decrease its complexity or avoid unnecessary risks based on a lack of contextual information.

In 2003, Ahmad Dahlan AR et al⁸ concluded in their paper The government information sharing in natural disaster management and risk reduction that, despite its importance, government information sharing capacity is not common to governments due to various technical, organisational, cultural and other barriers that are generally difficult for individual agencies to address.

⁸ Ahmad Dahlan AR, Dahan HM, Saman YM. The government information sharing (GIS) in natural disaster management and risk reduction - The success factors. 2013 5th International Conference on Information and Communication Technology for the Muslim World, ICT4M 2013. 1-7. 10.1109/ICT4M.2013.6518927. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/261305546_The_government_information_sharing_GIS_in_natural_disaster_management_and_risk_reduction_-_The_success_factors#fullTextFileContent

In a 2021 publication by Gontariuk M et al⁹ called The European Union and Public Health Emergencies: Expert views on the management of the first wave of the COVID-19 pandemic and suggestions for future emergencies, the findings indicate that the political challenges underlying EU decision-making in relation to health emergencies hindered an aligned response

G5.4.1-3: Need to better understand the needs of other emergency services.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-2: Fostering a culture of information exchange

To make the right decisions, emergency response organisations must necessarily share accurate and relevant information in a timely and seamless manner, providing them with a common operating picture that allows them to understand what is happening at any given time.

Deciding exactly what information is or is not shared and with whom is a challenge. Actors know their own information needs and will share them with other emergency response agencies, but it is a difficult task to capture all the critical data and at the same time know and adequately meet the needs of other agencies.

There is a need to develop a common knowledge base of the different competencies of emergency personnel, from which to understand how different responders interpret each other's needs and coordination requirements and interact with each other.

G5.4.1-4: Differing information needs for decision making.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-4: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

In 2019, Seen-Tveit K et al¹⁰ found that the security group and the rescue-firefighter group shared information of more varied categories and had a higher frequency of messages between each other than the other actors. This seems to indicate that these two disaster action groups are providing all involved agencies with common information needs, which is natural in complex scenarios involving mass casualties.

The medical group had a lower frequency of message exchange with the other groups. This could perhaps be explained by the fact that it is more focused on victim assistance (triage, stabilisation and evacuation), and that this type of information is not typically information that needs to be shared by the other action groups in order to carry out their objectives.

Due to the heterogeneity of the data obtained by the different organizations, comparison between them can be complicated in some cases. Because of this, creating a decision support system that displays information homogeneously from data captured from different organizations is complicated and costly.

⁹ Gontariuk M, Krafft T, Rehbock C, Townend D, Van der Auwermeulen L, Pilot E. The European Union and Public Health Emergencies: Expert Opinions on the Management of the First Wave of the COVID-19 Pandemic and Suggestions for Future Emergencies. *Frontiers in Public Health*. vol 9. 2021.
<https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpubh.2021.698995>

¹⁰ Steen-Tveit K et al. Analysis of Common Operational Picture and Situational Awareness during Multiple Emergency Response Scenarios. *WiPe Paper – Command and Control Studies. Proceedings of the 16th ISCRAM Conference*. València, Spain, May 2019.
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333449089_Analysis_of_Common_Operational_Picture_and_Situational_Awareness_during_Multiple_Emergency_Response_Scenarios

G5.4.1-5: No consensus on the basic information to be exchanged between agencies or territories.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-4: Standardisation of information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

Organisations are aware of the importance of information sharing for the success of their own organisation and for the effectiveness of the response as a whole.

Nowadays, there is no agreement on the information to be shared between agencies or territories. The identification of relevant information, how to exchange data or how to analyse data remains an open challenge. Additionally, there are no standards indicating the specific procedures for information sharing between the representatives of different agencies. This situation gets aggravated when information needs to be exchanged between different countries in emergency settings.

G5.4.1-6: No standardised information exchange processes between agencies or territories.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-4: Standardisation of information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

In terms of operational processes, the lack of an explicit mechanism of information exchange (including monitoring, control, communication, checking of work procedures, and sharing and integrating information, tasks and responsibilities) causes collaborative procedural problems.

Nowadays, there are no standards indicating how to exchange information between different emergency organisations at the EU level. Based on that, first responders only have a partial view of the situations, which derives in errors during the actuations and delays due to misinformation.

G5.4.1-7: Limited situational awareness.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-5: C2 applications.

Situational awareness is related to the phase two of the OODA cycle. Because each C2 application have different purposes the awareness each application generates is also different, which may lead to limited global situational awareness. Another limitation of the situational awareness is related to the restriction on sharing some data between entities and between countries. The possibility to exchange situational and tactical data, establishing tactical object and condition could reduce this gap, however there is no simple way to overcome this limitation as establish a global set of data sharing rules. Smart contracts could help overcoming this limitation. Nevertheless, the absence of specific data which may not be shared could, theoretically, lead to situational awareness inconsistency between different entities, and a second part of this gap is to find ways to detect inconsistencies of different C2 situational awareness without violating the data sharing restriction.

G5.4.1-8: Provide a shared data base of situational information/awareness is needed.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-10: Creating a unified COP for MCI and disasters

Most of the proposed systems are fed by data captured by the different FRs, however, these data are not currently stored in any system that allows them to be obtained quickly by any of the partners involved. In this way, the information can be classified according to its relevance, avoiding the exchange of unnecessary information that slows down the operation of the system.

G5.4.1-9: Unselective information overload.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-4: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

Situational awareness, SA, is related to how individuals and teams know and understand what is going on around them. Good SA provides a firm basis for effective decision-making.

To include all available information but does not prioritise the relevant elements to be shared will lead to information overload, i.e., the dissemination of redundant and irrelevant information. Humans have a limited capacity to retain the information available for processing, which is called working memory. Thus, information that is not relevant is even an obstacle that can hinder the development of situational awareness, create simplified mental models and slow down C2 decision-making during disaster response.

G5.4.1-10: Different weather prediction systems between countries.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-9: Facilitating a COP through a common federated system

Weather prediction and current weather parameters, influencing both the C2 decisions and the deployment of help to non-victims, are applicable between countries, following in some cases completely different models and algorithms. As so critical information (as for example ground humidity, ground temperature, burning material, sea currents etc.) is not available from all weather services. As a result, problems might be created in operational decision making

As so, in cross border incidents such incompatibility has to be resolved.

G5.4.1-11: Mission assessments by technological deployments.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-6: Improving Mission assessments by technological deployments.

C2 Commanders decision-making relies on briefing suggestions by rest of the participants. There are no technological capabilities in order to increase procedures decision-making according to entire joint schemes of manoeuvre.

Tools are needed that allow a more digitised view and understanding of the situation, with dynamic and interactive visualisation options, as well as tools that facilitate planning, monitoring and analysis of missions through the use of digital maps, models and virtual representations.

This should not replace manual exercises and more informal information exchange, which is often productive and necessary, but can be complemented by the use of technologies that make it faster and more comprehensive.

They also allow for the simulation of certain scenarios and the identification of certain risks and opportunities that might have taken longer to detect and validate with other methods. In this sense, there's a clear technological gap.

G5.4.1-12: Advanced visualization techniques required.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-7: Improving visualization techniques in MCI and disasters

The visualization of the data obtained in an indicator, either raw or graphically, can be very useful to know the current status of a mission. This information can be used for decision making or resource reallocation, however, currently there is no system available that allows this data

graphing. Because of this, the study of these data to make a conclusion is complicated, which significantly slows down the progress of this.

G5.4.1-13: On-the-fly generated data representations when requested by users required.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-8: On-the-fly generated data representations using advanced, cognitive loop enhancing techniques

To achieve an adequate COP, the different actors and disciplines must have at their disposal tools that update the information live and do so in a visually simple and understandable way (dendrograms, stream graphs, hive plots...). Information visualization is the process of representing data in a visual and meaningful way so that a user can better understand it. In this sense, there's a clear technological gap because getting elements, of whatever nature, to receive a 'digital translation' would be a great advantage since, if combined with appropriate programming, it would allow the status of these elements and their distance from the final expectations to be observed. This would greatly reduce working time and allow efforts to be devoted to other tasks that cannot be given over to technology. For example, vehicle positions or weather data can be monitored as they change. The best tools can also handle huge sets of data. In fact, the very best can even handle multiple sets of data in a single visualization.

G5.4.1-14: High risk exposure of first responders.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-11: Pay special attention to the safety of first responders.

When a major disaster strikes, emergency services must act quickly and effectively. Because the security conditions during a large-scale crisis are unknown and unpredictable, it is difficult to fully ensure the safety of first responders.

As evidenced in disasters such as the 9/11 attack on the Twin Towers in New York, inadequate situational awareness can severely expose first responders deployed to the disaster site to a higher than acceptable level of risk, resulting in serious injury or even death.

G5.4.1-15: On scene volunteers rescuers command and COP.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.1-3: Taking volunteers into account

Volunteers supporting emergency incidents cannot communicate and exchange information and data with the information system of the authorities. Thus, the command and control centre cannot have information about the status of the volunteers involved in the incident.

In every emergency incident, the authorities involved (fire service, police, ambulance service) communicate with each other and/or are coordinated by the respective coordination center. The coordination center, through its information system, implemented uniformly or separately for each service, has the ability to monitor the resources (vehicles, personnel, etc.) in the field and coordinate them remotely.

However, there are many times when voluntary organizations contribute to the work of the authorities both with personnel and with various means (e.g., vehicles, boats). However, the resources provided by the volunteers do not appear in the center's system. As a result, in large-scale incidents the common operational picture is incomplete.

Different forces assist in various locations with varying resources. Communication with the command centre may be limited or non-existent for certain aiding first response units. As a

result, not only does the risk of faulty or no information, for the forces in the field increase, but the efficient utilization of resources also decreases.

Consequently, the gap identified between volunteers and professionals who operate in the field is related to the common operational picture that the headquarters or central coordinator obtains. However, this does not imply that their collaborative cooperation in the area does not yield the desired outcomes possible.

Identification of gaps			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.1-1	Legal constraints to interoperability	Professional experience	There are legal barriers that substantially constrain interoperability between technologies and information exchange platforms in C2.
G5.4.1-2	Insufficient awareness of information exchange between agencies and territories	Survey	Lack of collaboration between agencies of different administrative dependencies, due to political factors or those associated with the organisational culture.
G5.4.1-3	Need to better understand the needs of other emergency services	Professional experience	There is a need to develop a common knowledge base of the different expertise of emergency personnel, from which to understand how the different responders interpret each other's needs and coordination requirements and interact with each other.
G5.4.1-4	Differing information needs for decision making	Literature	The EMS first responders shares less information with other responders in MCI and disaster response. Security and firefighters have common information needs.
G5.4.1-5	No consensus on the basic information to be exchanged between agencies or territories.	Literature	There are no common criteria for identifying relevant information, for information exchange or for data analysis in C2. There is no consensus on the basic information that needs to be shared among emergency commanders for decision-making.
G5.4.1-6	No standardised information exchange processes between agencies or territories	Professional experience	In general terms, there are no standardised specific information-sharing procedures between the commanders of different agencies or different countries in disaster response.

Identification of gaps			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.1-7	Limited situational awareness	Literature	Limited knowledge of the situation and its scope sometimes leads to delays in sending the necessary emergency teams. Inadequate systems for recording, storing and interpreting data of relevance to C2, leading to delays in decision-making.
G5.4.1-8	Provide a shared data base of situational information/awareness is needed.	Literature	An adequate COP should provide the relevant information shared by all stakeholders, without exceeding the amount of information presented, as for some users it may be irrelevant or lead to over-information.
G5.4.1-9	Unselective information overload	Literature	Information overload complicates decision-making in MCI and disaster response and creates simplified mental models.
G5.4.1-10	Different weather prediction systems between countries	Professional experience	Weather prediction, influencing both the C2 decisions and the deployment of help to non-victims, are applicable between countries, following in some cases completely different models and algorithms. So critical information (as for example ground humidity, ground temperature, burning material, sea currents etc.) is not available from all weather services, problems might be created in operational decision making. As so, in cross border incidents such incompatibility has to be resolved.
G5.4.1-11	Mission assessments by technological deployments	Literature	C2 Commanders decision-making relies on briefing suggestions by rest of the participants. There are no technological capabilities in order to increase procedures decision-making according to entire joint schemes of manoeuvre.
G5.4.1-12	Advanced visualization techniques required	Literature	Currently, tools that allow for a common visualisation of the emergency are scarce and those that do exist offer information through techniques that can be greatly improved.

Identification of gaps			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.1-13	On-the-fly generated data representations when requested by users required.	Professional experience	To achieve an adequate COP, the different actors and disciplines must have at their disposal tools that update the information live and do so in a visually simple and understandable way.
G5.4.1-14	High risk exposure of first responders	Professional experience	Inadequate situational awareness often exposes first responders deployed to the scene of an incident or disaster to a higher than acceptable level of risk, sometimes resulting in serious injury or death.
G5.4.1-15	On scene volunteers rescuers command and COP	Professional experience	Volunteers supporting emergency incidents cannot communicate and exchange information and data with the information system of the authorities. Thus, the incident command and the emergency operations centre, cannot have information about the status of the volunteers being involved in the incident.

Table 9 – Gaps from Common Operational Picture

5.4.2 Alert and warning

G5.4.2-1: Lack of a common approach in public early warning of disasters.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-1: Defining a common approach to disaster early warning.

Since disasters are becoming more frequent and have large impact on the society, one crucial aspect that has to be addressed is the timely and prompt issue of warnings and alerts to the public. Especially, taking into consideration that large masses of people are aggregated into disaster-susceptible areas, these warnings must simultaneously reach millions of people. Sakkas et al. (2020) have documented the need for standardisation towards this domain, expressed by first responders.

Some serious steps to resolve this specific issue have already been taken with the use of the 24/7-operating 112 European emergency service line. 112 is used for a plethora of situations e.g., for reporting an emergency, for issuing alerts, early warnings and evacuation routes, among others. However, there are still pending technical issues regarding the miss-receipt of the 112 emergency messages by the entirety of the vulnerable and exposed population, whereas, on the other hand, people far from the dangerous zone, do receive these messages. Another path that could be explored is also the use of social media for the issue of alerts. Taking into account that the vast majority of the population uses social media as a primary source of information, this solution could be even more effective. Nevertheless, at this point, elderly people, who are not confident in using smart phones and PCs should be considered.

G5.4.2-2: No standardized alerting procedure in National level.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-3: Standardization of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe.

According to the answers from the questionnaire, there is no standardized procedure at the National level for some countries of the alerting. Thus, can be easily identified a gap in the standardization across EU.

The first round of distribution of the questionnaire, in the 5th section, regarding the alert and warning of citizens, there is a gap at the national level in the standardization of their warning process. More specifically, the answers show that Spain and Italy do not have a Standardized Crisis Alert and Warning Procedure at a national level. In addition to this, it seems that in both two countries the responsibility for activating the process is held by different agencies.

This gap can be accommodated in a shared presumption with the following gap G5.4.2-3

G5.4.2-3: Technical and procedural issues in alert and warning.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-4: Standardization of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe.

There is no homogeneity in relation to procedures, techniques and content related to alerts and early warning systems. A standard method should be developed to collect and relay instantaneously and automatically all types of hazard warnings and reports locally, regionally, and nationally for input into a wide variety of dissemination systems.

An Integrated Public Alert and Warning System is designed to provide rapid, reliable and effective communication to the public in case of major emergencies such as natural disasters. The network is designed to integrate various systems into one modern network, and also update them to take into account latest forms of communication such as cellular telephony and SMS, satellite and cable television, digital signal and the web.

Common form to communicate disaster is important in all different EU countries, and even so more in cross border incident. Alert and warnings must be standardized for all stakeholders.

In addition, the effectiveness of the warnings must be improved, as well as monitoring alerts and warning systems.

G5.4.2-4: No definition of "High priority public warnings".

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-2: Identifying "high priority public warnings".

Documents and guides have been published in order to describe the technique for identifying "high priority public warnings". This refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property. A warning issued from the authorities about an incident does not directly stimulate public action. Instead, it involves an intervening process of perception formation and interpretation that is affected by a number of factors including risk perception, warning style and a variety of social factors. The research indicates that individuals consider these impacts and then act, rather than engaging in action that result in social chaos,

looting, panic, immobilisation due to emotional shock or, conversely, docile obedience to authority. Recipients of warning messages rarely respond to the initial message. In fact, disbelief of the first message is common and this instigates attempts to confirm the threat from other sources and to gather further information. This response process is termed 'milling' and is particularly likely when the disaster is unexpected and the level of emergency preparedness is low.

G5.4.2-5: Different command competencies in alerts.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-3: Standardization of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe.

Public Warning Systems are systems which authorities may use to notify citizens regarding imminent or developing major emergencies and disasters.

The European Electronic Communications Code (EECC), states that the definition of public warning and the sending of the alert falls under civil protection, which is a national competence.

There are often national and regional laws on the responsibility of issuing warning messages to the general public. Many of these are based on jurisdiction and boundaries, which are territory or competences based.

Thus, the interviews conducted in the course of the WP5 work show differences in which agency is responsible for warning and alerting the population (Civil Protection, Firefighters, or even Specific agencies in relation to specific hazards such as radiological or seismic incidents, etc.)

G5.4.2-6: Outdated warning systems.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-5: Technological upgrading of warning systems.

In 2018, article 110 of the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC)¹¹ made it mandatory for all the Member States of the European Union to deploy a Public Warning system using telephone networks to alert everyone located in a specific area of an ongoing crisis or upcoming disaster. Article 110 states that Member States shall ensure that, when public warning systems regarding imminent or developing major emergencies and disasters are in place, public warnings are transmitted by providers of mobile number-based interpersonal communication services to end-users concerned.

EECC Article 110 indicates that Member States may determine that public warnings be transmitted through other different publicly available electronic communications services and other than broadcasting services, or through internet access service or a mobile application relying on an internet access service, provided that the effectiveness of the public warning system is equivalent in terms of coverage and capacity to reach end-users including those only temporarily present in the area concerned, taking utmost account of BEREC (Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications) guidelines¹².

¹¹ Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L1972>

¹² Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications (BEREC). Guidelines on how to assess the effectiveness of public warning systems transmitted by different means. 2020.

But these same BEREC guidelines, published in 2020, point out that there is a wide diversity of practices in Europe regarding Public Warning Systems, and many of them based on, legacy resources. The technologies deployed are: sirens in 16 Member States; TV, radio or social media alerts in 14 Member States; specific applications in 5 Member States; SMS alert in 6 Member States and Cell Broadcast in 4 Member States.

G5.4.2-7: Cross Border Alarms and Warnings gap.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-6: Hybrid Digital Twins as an alert and warning harmonization tool.

Issued Alarms or Warnings in cross-border incidents are not available. This could create problems in their handling with obvious consequences on the effectiveness of FR C2 commands accordingly, or public awareness.

G5.4.2-8: Fight against misinformation and rumours or fake news.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-7: Creating and supporting initiatives that fight against misinformation in disasters.

Communication management in crisis situations is key in an interconnected society. Currently, the main route of communication of emergencies are social networks, representing both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the great presence of hoaxes and false/fake news. Rumours and misinformation have been identified as a significant threat to the utility of social media and other online tools during disaster events. Many emergency responders cite misinformation on social media as a major concern and a barrier to adopting social media in their work.

G5.4.2-9: No follow up of alarms and warnings issued.

Related opportunity: OP5.4.2-8: Social media analysis of citizen's behaviour.

Issued Alarms or Warnings by appropriate authorities are distributed through different telecommunication or physical channels targeting specific audience for awareness or instructions. So far, all existing systems do not follow the response of the public following such alarms and warnings.

As this gap create huge opportunities for future related projects that can be designed to resolve the issue properly supported by available technologies (but not existing applications), SIGRUN opportunity through the Valkyries project is limited to the design of a minimum set of APIs analysing the correspondence of the public through specific social media monitoring providing APIs for such analysing functionality. Such response has to be manually evaluated (at present) and reported to the Valkyries COP for proper distribution to federated systems and agents.

Identification of gaps			
Alert and warning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.2-1	Lack of a common approach in public early warning of disasters	Literature	The vast majority of the society resides in areas that are prone to different types of natural hazards e.g., earthquakes, floods, tsunamis. There is not a common approach in alerting the citizens of disaster-susceptible areas before disasters occur.
G5.4.2-2	No standardized alerting procedure in National level	Survey	According to the answers from the questionnaire, there is no a standardized procedure at the National level for some countries of the alerting. Thus can be easily identified a gap in the standardization across EU.
G5.4.2-3	Technical and procedural issues in alert and warning	Literature	There is no homogeneity in relation to procedures, techniques and content related to warnings and early warning systems. Technical standards play an important role in communication systems. Common form to communicate disaster is important in all different countries, and even so more in cross border incident. Alert and warnings must be standardized for all stakeholders.
G5.4.2-4	No definition of "High priority public warnings"	Literature	"High priority public warnings" refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. The identification of these messages is crucial to give those affected better options to preserve life and protect property, and this practice is not widespread.
G5.4.2-5	Different command competencies in alerts	Survey	There is no homogeneity in terms of the agencies responsible for warning and alerting the population (Civil Protection, fire brigade).

Identification of gaps			
Alert and warning			
ID	Gap name	Type of input	Justification
G5.4.2-6	Outdated warning systems	Literature	In many cases, the technological resources to promote early warning and the appropriate issuing and dissemination of warnings are not up to date.
G5.4.2-7	Cross Border Alarms and Warnings gap	Professional experience	Issued Alarms or Warnings in cross-border incidents are not available. This could create problems in their handling.
G5.4.2-8	Fight against misinformation and rumours or fake news	Literature	Communication management in crisis situations is key in an interconnected society. Rumours and misinformation have been identified as a significant threat to the utility of social media and other online tools during disaster events.
G5.4.2-9	No follow-up of alarms and warnings issued	Professional experience	There is no mechanism available to monitor citizen's reactions after accepting Alarms or Warnings. As so, plans "assuming" their reaction might result to not desirable conditions

Table 10 – Gaps from alert and warning

6. Opportunities

For the purposes of this deliverable D5.6 and of this project, and following the criteria of the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO)¹³, we can define OPPORTUNITY as the occurrence that would have a favourable impact, or as the situation from which an organization can derive benefit.

Not in all cases has it been possible to formulate an opportunity for each identified gap. There are several reasons for this, including, for example, the following:

- Political problems.
- Government structure.
- Language problems.
- The technique is not developed.
- It is outside of the project scope

The gaps will be presented structured according to the tasks/sub-tasks of the WP5 of the VALKYRIES project. For each task/sub-task, a table with the identification of the opportunities and a brief summary of the gaps is shown first. Then, in the text, each of the listed opportunities is discussed in more detail.

6.1 Reconnaissance, triage and crisis response planning

As in previous sections of this deliverable D5.6, for ease of opportunities approach and understanding, this task T5.2 has been divided into 2 subsections focusing respectively on:

- Crisis response planning
- Reconnaissance and triage

6.1.1 Crisis response planning

OP5.1.1-1: Regulatory harmonisation.

Related gap: G5.1.1-3: Lack of regulatory harmonisation between countries in disaster planning and response.

To promote the establishment of unified cross-border response plans and procedures, EU countries should seek to develop harmonising legislation.

It is also important to put in place systematic models to facilitate harmonisation between countries, such as the METHANE system, which provides structure and clarity in the early stages of managing any multi-agency or large-scale incident.

OP5.1.1-2: Standardisation of terms and symbols for a common understanding of the situation.

Related gap: G5.1.1-1: Lack of standardisation of terms and symbols.

¹³ International Organization for Standardization. ISO 31073:2022(en) Risk management — Vocabulary. 2022. <https://www.iso.org/standard/79637.html>

A variety of standards related to disaster management terminology and symbology exists. In the following table, indicative standards and pre-standards (CEN Workshop Agreements) are mentioned.

Standardisation Body	Standard
CEN	EN 17173:2020 European CBRNE glossary
	EN 1846-1:2011 Firefighting and rescue service vehicles – Part 1: Nomenclature and designation
	CEN/TR 17512:2020 Personal protective equipment – Smart garments – Terms and definitions
CEN/CLC	CWA 17335:2018 Terminologies in crisis and disaster management
ISO	ISO 22300:2018 Security and resilience – Vocabulary
	ISO/TR 22351:2015 Societal security – Emergency management – Message structure for exchange of information
	ISO 22324:2015 Societal security – Emergency management – Guidelines for colour-coded alerts
ASTM	ASTM E2771-11 (2019) Standard Terminology for Homeland Security Applications
ITU-T	E.102: Terms and definitions for disaster relief systems, network resilience and recovery

Table 11 – Indicative standards related to terminology and symbology

It is known that standardized solutions for structuring military symbols MIL-STD-2525 and STANAG APP6 (APP-6 - Military symbols for land-based systems, https://www.alternatewars.com/BBOW/NATO_Symbols/APP-6.pdf).

An example of a hierarchical representation of groups of symbols to represent military units as well as defining Areas of Interest (AoI), with sources (Military Symbols in JavaScript, <https://github.com/spatialillusions/milsymbol>, MIT License, accessed January 2022; Alexander Kolev, Command and control in the nearby of the geographical environment, monograph under edition, Intel Entrance, Sofia, 2022, in Bulgarian language) is shown in the following figure:

Figure 1 - Military symbology examples. Source (Military Symbols, 2022; Kolev, 2022)

From sources available in the public domain, there are known attempts to lay the foundations for creating a symbology for graphical representation of objects and situations for Crisis Mapping and Disaster Management (Ana Kuveždić Divjak, Almin Đapo and Boško Pribičević, Cartographic Symbology for Crisis Mapping: A Comparative Study, <https://www.mdpi.com/2220-9964/9/3/142/htm>, accessed July 2022; Silvia T. Marinova, New Map Symbol System for Disaster Management, Proceedings of the International Cartographic Association, 1, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.5194/ica-proc-1-74-2017> | © Authors 2017. CC BY 4.0 License, <https://www.proc-int-cartogr-assoc.net/1/74/2018/ica-proc-1-74-2018.pdf>, accessed July 2022). The following figures show fragments of the concept of taxonomy and representation of specialized symbology:

Figure 2 - Shape and colour of the categorized symbols. Source (Marinova, 2017)

The above standards could be used as opportunities for the harmonisation of this important aspect of disaster management. But an important question arises: Since a variety of standards exists, why is the issue of terminology considered as a gap by the first responders?

Tsaloukidis et al. (2022) conducted research related, among others, to standardisation and the adoption of standards in their operational procedures. The results of this research highlighted the fact that, to a significant extent, first responders either do not use or are not aware of using standards in their operations. On the other hand, they prefer to implement widely adopted guidelines issued by organisations with a wide outreach. Moreover, they seem reluctant to change the way they are used to operate. This is a general issue that has to be addressed in the future i.e., effective ways for the increase of awareness and adoption of standards by first responders' organisations. The adoption of standards in general, not just in terms of common terminology and symbology, could be considered as a standalone gap.

OP5.1.1-3: Adequate revision and updating of emergency plans.

Related gap: G5.1.1-4: Inconsistency of crisis response plans.

By having comprehensive preparation for any emergency (planning, practicing, evaluating and adjusting to specific circumstances) an emergency can be managed comprehensively, and this can happen only if all involved parties have been planning and coordinating together and plans and planned procedures have been practised, evaluated and improved.

Developing a comprehensive emergency response plan means to provide procedures with necessary details covering the emergency response organisation, communication and responsibilities that are to be observed by all personnel in responding to an emergency.

The crisis emergency plan aims to ensure various preventive measures and mitigation actions that need to be undertaken in the event of any incident, accident or disaster are properly planned and designed. By following the planned and designed emergency plan, the measures provided can prevent the increasing severity of any incident, reducing injury and minimising damage and loss to property.

Process of revision and regular updating of emergency plans is under responsibility of each either local, regional and national institution. In most EU countries emergency plans were once created, but no more reviewed or updated. There is a necessity for making emergency plans to face actual situation, update them according to the needs of population. This process should be stated in law of each EU country, which should ensure that all responsible agencies will follow this issue.

In every emergency plan one of the most pertinent elements in assuring effective emergency response as needed.

Element to be considered in an emergency plan documentation, include but are not limited to the following:

- Objective,
- Responsibility and authority,
- Plan distribution, revision and updates,
- Equipment and supply of emergency tools,
- Data and information allocation,

- Risk and hazard assessment,
- Procedures (communication protocols, evacuation procedures, chain of command, emergency operations centres, community warning or alarm system, medical triage, command post, etc.)
- Returning to normal operation (recovery),
- Training.

OP5.1.1-4: Adequate dissemination and training in relation to emergency plans.

Related gap: G5.1.1-5: Lack of dissemination of emergency plans.

Good emergency planning is not effective if it is not accompanied by a process of implementation and updating. Implementation implies the dissemination of the plan to both the affected population and the organisations that make up the action groups, the development of procedures for action, the education and training of all those involved in the response, as well as the provision of the necessary equipment.

It is therefore essential to ensure that the implementation process set out in each emergency plan is followed, disseminating the plan to all the organisations and agencies involved in the plan, as well as to the population potentially affected by the emergency, using all available means.

This implementation process should be proceduralised and would involve a series of actions such as:

- The distribution or dissemination of the plan to all agencies involved in the plan
- The development of procedures by the services that make up the action groups, so that action plans are available for those situations that can be foreseen
- The training and qualification of those involved, so that all personnel included in the organisation have the minimum training required to carry out their functions adequately. This training, which should be continuous, should include courses, exercises and drills.
- The provision of equipment and verification of the adequacy of the infrastructures of each organisation involved.
- Prior information of the population, which is considered one of the basic principles of emergency response management.

Citizens should be informed and made aware in the same way as other emergencies such as traffic accidents. Since use case emergencies cause a large number of people to be affected.

As it happens with quality plans within companies, the commitment of the members of the emergency and the population must be achieved through engagement with the emergency plans. Only in this way, they embrace the emergency plans and understand that they are for the common good.

The common citizen does not know what to do in an emergency situation and in this way, it is difficult to get their collaboration. It is necessary a continuous training and not a punctual one when an emergency occurs so that the general population knows clear and concise instructions on how to proceed.

OP5.1.1-5: Facilitating EU's Civil Protection Guidelines through a common federated system.

Related gap: G5.1.1-2: Following of Guidelines of EU Civil Protection.

EU Civil Protection has issued a set of Guidelines and Best Practices procedures to help the EU Member State to harmonize their systems and agents involved in disasters. Such Guidelines are also supported by tools, such as earth observation of different types of disasters (such as wild fires or floods) as well as statistical data and time series on recorded disasters.

Based on those, member states of EU should synchronize their plans and systems accordingly. But, as far as all of those Guidelines and Tools are quite generic and difficult to be embedded into common practices, they can be used mainly as an indicator of gaps and discrepancies between different operational systems deployed in each country.

To fill the gap, the main opportunity in the Valkyries project is to use EU/Civil Protection guidelines and tools as the base line and try to achieve interoperability between different federated systems "as it is" through exchange of information on COPs between countries.

The other opportunity then relays to the Political and Administrator officers responsible to evaluate the performance of their systems after disasters, with "lessons learned" through experiences shared in drills or real FR cross-order situations. Then they can handle their change management in organizational or procedural standards and plans accordingly.

Following the above, the schema that needs to be followed is the following:

Figure 3 - Emergency Response Preparedness (ERP) Cycle¹⁴

¹⁴ Emergency Response Preparedness (ERP). Draft For Field Testing. Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC): IASC UN agencies, International Federation of the Red Cross and NGOs. 2015.

Where:

RISK ANALYSIS AND MONITORING

A clear and common understanding of the risks which may trigger a crisis significant enough to require a coordinated humanitarian response is fundamental to the entire ERP process. Analysis informs the planning while monitoring ensures that the process is responsive to emerging risks. The risk analysis process identifies the hazards that could trigger a crisis and ranks them by impact and likelihood. The risk ranking determines whether thresholds are low, medium, or high. Development of a contingency plan is recommended when risk thresholds are determined to be medium or above. In parallel, risk monitoring should be undertaken using indicators identified as part of the risk analysis process. Monitoring provides early warning of emerging risks which in turn allows for early action, such as tailoring the contingency plan and where possible taking action that could mitigate the impact of the emerging risk.

MINIMUM PREPAREDNESS ACTIONS (MPA)

Minimum Preparedness Actions are a set of activities that every Member State Civil Protection Mechanism must implement in order to establish a minimum level of emergency preparedness within the country. The MPAs are not risk or scenario-specific and usually do not require significant additional resources to accomplish. Minimum Preparedness Actions include risk monitoring, establishment of coordination and management arrangements, preparing for joint needs assessments, monitoring, information management, and establishing operational capacity and arrangements to deliver critical relief assistance and protection. Implementing MPAs will make a fundamental difference to eventual response and provide flexibility to respond to different types of emergencies. Although risk analysis is undertaken by most plans as part of preparedness, very few put in place risk monitoring, which results in a lack of early warning and most importantly early action. The MPAs are a reversed engineered approach – they look at what the core elements of a successful response are and then work backwards to identify what preparedness actions are needed to achieve those positive response outcomes.

ADVANCED PREPAREDNESS

Actions and Contingency Planning Advanced Preparedness Actions (APAs) and Contingency Planning (CP) are two sets of complementary activities that should be initiated together to plan for specific risks when risk analysis and monitoring indicate moderate or high risk. Advanced Preparedness Actions are designed to advance readiness to respond to specific risks. Unlike the MPAs, the APAs are risk-specific.

- The Emergency Response Preparedness (ERP) approach should be practical. It should focus on needs; what we have and how to bridge the gaps. It looks at how we might reach affected people with assistance. In other words, the ERP is a process of asking and answering a set of critical operational questions.
- The ERP should be flexible. Plans should prioritise actions in light of capacity within the country to undertake preparedness.
- Risk analysis and monitoring are key to dynamic and responsive preparedness.

https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/system/files/iasc_emergency_response_preparedness_guidelines_july_2015_draft_for_field_testing.pdf

- Simulations and other such tools should regularly be applied to ensure the emergency readiness of plans and systems to carry out the action plans developed through the ERP process. In this way problems can be anticipated, sources for relief items can be identified in advance and roles and responsibilities of different actors can be better understood. The chances of good coordination will be greatly improved.
- The ERP should be participatory. Planning is most effective when all those who will be required to work together are engaged in the process from the start.

Strategic leadership by the Humanitarian Coordinator, HC, and strong commitment from heads of Agency at country level to making staff and resources available to support the process are vital to the success of an ERP. The success of the ERP process depends on each and every member of the Humanitarian Country Team, HCT. place. The APA checklist has to include essential preparedness actions that complement and support the contingency planning process. A contingency plan sets out the initial response strategy and operational plan to meet the humanitarian needs during the first three to four weeks of an emergency. A contingency plan addresses what could happen and what might be needed; actions to take and resources required and gaps to be bridged.

OP5.1.1-6: Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system.

Related gap: G5.1.1-7: Roles definition Gaps.

To fill the role/workflow gap between agents within a country or between different countries in cross-border incidents, the opportunity is to leave the operational procedures and the supported role definitions "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization path from "lesson learning" following their practice in cross-border incidents as the core of such change management.

Thus, the SIGRUN system has to define only

- Roles and workflows only for the people responsible to operate/parametrize/support the SIGRUN core modules only
- Adopt "lessons learned" from such data and practices/valuation sharing
- Provide recommendations that can be followed by all involved participants based on the G5.1.1.2.

Common role definitions and workflows will be included only for the support of the Core of SIGRUN system.

OP5.1.1-7: C2 activation through a common federated system / COP.

Related gap: G5.1.1-6: Rescue Plans Activation Gap.

Gaps have been pointed out in relation to the fact that different criteria for activating crisis response plans and C2 coordination between different countries could lead to a delay in transferring the alert to those countries that might initially be affected to a lesser extent. This would lead to a delay in the activation of the crisis response plan, in the sharing of data and in the start of C2 coordination.

This could lead to catastrophic results, if the incident spreads to the country least prepared for crisis response and C2 actions.

This gap can be resolved using the technological opportunity of the SIGRUN system to share tactical information between different countries, prior to the activation of C2s and crisis response plans in both countries.

Opportunities			
Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.1-1	G5.1.1-3	Regulatory harmonisation	In order to promote the establishment of unified cross-border response plans and procedures, EU countries should seek to develop legislation to harmonise them.
OP5.1.1-2	G5.1.1-1	Standardisation of terms and symbols for a common understanding of the situation	In multi casualty incidents, in which the coordination and collaboration of different first responders agencies are required, it is crucial that data and information exchanged through the various systems should be interpreted in the same way by first responders. Apart from semantics that are used in systems, it is essential for FRs among the EU Member States to adopt a common terminology and symbology. This could lead to better collaborations and to the accomplishment of a common operational picture and situational awareness. Moreover, common signals and symbols could be used in social media for early warning.
OP5.1.1-3	G5.1.1-4	Adequate revision and updating of emergency plans.	Developing, updating, revising and publishing crisis management plans on regular basis. This should be stated in the specific law.
OP5.1.1-4	G5.1.1-5	Adequate dissemination and training in relation to emergency plans.	Good emergency planning is not effective if it is not accompanied by an adequate dissemination plan that includes the potentially affected population and training for all those involved in the response.
OP5.1.1-5	G5.1.1-2	Facilitating EU's Civil Protection Guidelines through a common federated system	A federated system could facilitate harmonization towards acceptance, preparation and activation of EU's Civil Protection Guidelines.
OP5.1.1-6	G5.1.1-7	Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system	Leave the operational procedures and the supported role definitions "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization from "lesson learning" following their practice in cross-border incidents as the core of such change management. Common role definitions and

Opportunities			
Crisis response planning			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			workflows will be included only for the support of the Core of SIGRUN system.
OP5.1.1-7	G5.1.1-6	C2 activation through a common federated system / COP	Signalling of the need to activate C2 through the COP exchange/sharing of the Valkyries / SIGRUN system

Table 12 – Opportunities from crisis response planning

6.1.2 Reconnaissance and triage

OP5.1.2-1: Harmonisation of emergency services structure.

Related gap: G5.1.2-1: Different EMS structure and composition.

To establish either national or international working groups, formed by experts and heads of different agencies and/or administrations, gaining this way a greater support in the agreements adopted.

To establish national plans with common strategies for all regions and other specific for each region taking into account their peculiarities, such as the availability of resources, population density or geographical dispersion. It could be approached as a commitment to guarantee a minimum of requirements. Subsequently, these plans could be raised to a supranational level, to harmonize procedures within the EU environment.

To create accurate records in which those responsible for each region are identified and tagged with their equivalents from other nations, so they could be properly required in case of an incident with clearly established duties.

To establish policies for disseminating the unified emergency plans and/or procedures through different channels, making the information accessible in order to make it easier for all professionals to know who is responsible for each process, the tasks or the priority in which they must be carried out, etc.

OP5.1.2-2: Homogenisation of professional competencies in emergencies.

Related gap: G5.1.2-3: Different professional competencies among first responders.

To harmonise and standardise the training and competencies of emergency services professionals at EU level.

It would be desirable and effective in incident a homogenisation of professional competences in the emergencies. There are different professional competences among first responders, between organisations and between countries. The professional competencies are established by law in each country Eg. In some countries, paramedics have competencies that would not be possible in other countries.

For manage emergencies with this feature it is necessary a homogenisation of the professional competences. The competences of each first responder should be clear independently of their country of origin or actuation.

Only with this homogenisation, will the emergency leader systematically know and have a quick overview about the resources in accordance with their competencies and how they can participate in the incident.

OP5.1.2-3: Integrated pre-hospital and hospital MCI plans and operational procedures.

Related gap: G5.1.2-13: Limited involvement of many hospital facilities in MCI and disaster response planning.

Promote the creation of legislation that encourages the development and integration of joint EMS and hospital MCI response plans, with both EMS and hospitals taking a more proactive role in these plans to maximise the effectiveness of the response.

Hospitals have a passive response at the request of the centre in charge of the emergency, this method of management is not efficient. In this way the hospital is not encouraged to anticipate the emergency and adapt to the emergency conditions. They do not have the active capacity to modify their equipment, staffing and refurbish spaces. To solve the emergency in a more efficient way and to serve more patients.

So that would be desired, a legislation that encourage the integration of joint EMS-hospital with the MCI response plans. If both work together as two active roles, the effectiveness of the response will be maximised.

OP5.1.2-4: Standardisation of terminology and criteria.

Related gap: G5.1.2-6: Non-standardised zoning.

Standardisation of terminology and harmonisation of criteria for zoning in MCI response would make it easier for different agencies or regions to work together.

Zoning is paramount in an emergency management but differs between countries and agencies. This causes problems for coordination and emergency management especially for coordination between organisations.

Zoning is used to carry out the emergency and, for example, to know which a safe location. If MCI conditions change, it must be coordinated and known to all members of the emergency. This communication and coordination must be done quickly and effectively not only to carry out the emergency but also to ensure the integrity of the first responders.

The technical needs of the actors are different, but even so, terminology and criteria for zoning in an MCI can be harmonised.

OP5.1.2-5: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

Related gap: G5.1.2-8: Non-standardised victim registration and affiliation information.

Standardisation of the basic information to be collected in relation to each victim is fundamental to guarantee traceability and continuity of care for those affected in a disaster, even more so in cross-border disasters.

Triage labels are simple, useful and efficient. But they present several problems when it comes to MCI between different countries. For instance, when a victim is tagged by first responders in one country and then moved to another country, there are problems with the original label. Some problems about it are around language, criteria, taxonomy and categorisation.

Useful and clear instructions for a first responder in one country may not be useful in another and the traceability of the patient may be lost.

So that it would be desirable, the use of mobile devices for triage. They will be useful for the digitisation of data, ensuring interoperability between countries, security and traceability of data.

In addition, a minimum set of data would be of interest, which should be provided and given by the organisations. These data would have the same nature and would be fully interoperable.

OP5.1.2-6: Standardisation of means of triage tagging in MCI.

Related gap: G5.1.2-10: Non-standardised victim priority tagging.

In order to standardise the means of triage tagging in MCI, "smart" coloured wristbands (equipped with readable electronic identification) can be used in the first triage/identification of the victim, record the data in a secure blockchain structure and allow other responders handling the victim to record other data, before handling the victim in a hospital.

However, some very simple actions in terms of cost and complexity of implementation have shown a significant impact in relation to the standardisation of triage processes, labelling, and recording of information and clinical documentation of victims.

For example, in Spain, different civilian and military emergency services, with different structures and operating procedures, have adopted the same triage card (TASSICA-2 triage tag)¹⁵ which, being known and shared by all of them, facilitates the interpretation of the priority assigned to a victim by the triage tagging, favouring interoperability between services in MCIs, even when a victim is initially assisted by one service and then ends up being attended by a different one.

OP5.1.2-7: Standardisation of triage procedures in MCI.

Related gap: G5.1.2-9: Different triage standards and practices in use within countries between different first responders.

Standardisation of triage procedures can be based on a more flexible scheme using the following basic key points:

The first stage of triage can be initiated by any FR by tagging and recording the victim in a SIGRUN file (highly recommended to be secured with blockchain technologies) with non-medical information and photos as well as medical information, as applicable/allowed by each agent. Colour standards can be used to indicate the initial status of the victim.

¹⁵ Montarelo A et al. Tarjeta de Triage Tassica 2: evaluación práctica de su funcionalidad operativa en incidentes con múltiples víctimas. Puesta al día en urgencias, emergencias y catástrofes (2010). 10 (3) 123-132. ISSN 1576-0316.

Different coloured "smart tags" can be used to indicate the status of victims, recording non-medical data, photos and, where allowed, medical data in blockchain-protected files.

Victim tracking when handled between different agents (it is from volunteers or firefighters to EMS personnel) can be done using suitable FR smartphones or tablets to read the tag and update the recorded information with manual input data or automated data (such as GPS positioning of the victim at that moment, time, FR ID etc.).

Access to the victim's electronic medical records or medical history during this first phase of triage should be limited to designated functions only (such as FR doctors or paramedics).

Any data linkage relevant to the victim during this phase should be linked to the victim's identification (here the unique tag number).

After treatment of the victim by the last hospital to support the victim on a second medical level, the internal triage systems of each hospital are activated, while the tag and the collected records/information will remain active until a predefined criterion.

Thus, triage procedures can be supported by common and very low-cost technologies with minimal complexity in their interoperability between the different supporting systems.

C2s (either a central one or a dedicated one per agent) will have an accurate and complete view of the status of the victims and the last position recorded

No "loss of victims" is possible.

Access to health-related data is secured in blockchain registries, so permissions/privileges of different FRs with different roles can follow local rules, practices and training support.

Following the above, linked federated systems handling sensitive medical/health information related to individual victims could share it with other actors within a country or across countries according to existing (or future) criteria.

In addition, the range of professionals who can act as first responders with basic triage skills in this type of incident could be broadened, and the necessary markings could be established in a unified way so that those responsible for the intervention, including the triage manager, can be identified at a glance. This should be clearly specified in the common procedures.

Following on from OP5.1.2-6 Standardisation of means of triage tagging in MCI, the experience in Spain with the TASSICA-2 triage tags¹⁶ has shown a favourable impact in several respects related to Standardisation of triage procedures in MCI:

- TASSICA-2 triage tag guides the first responder through the triage and victim care process, helping to reduce stress and the need for rote efforts during the intervention.
- It facilitates uniformity of criteria when setting triage priorities.
- It ensures that the patient's clinical information accompanies the patient at all times throughout the care chain, containing clinical information from the entire care process received at the scene.

¹⁶ Montarelo A et al. Tarjeta de Triage Tassica 2: evaluación práctica de su funcionalidad operativa en incidentes con múltiples víctimas. Puesta al día en urgencias, emergencias y catástrofes (2010). 10 (3) 123-132. ISSN 1576-0316.

- It also ensures patient traceability, identifying the patient with a unique individual code and leaving a record of the intervention carried out on the patient at each step of the care chain.
- Usable and resistant in the most extreme conditions: it is made of material that is resistant to liquids (water, blood, grease, NBC decontamination), tear-resistant, and can be used with all common means of writing (ball pen, marker pen, pencil...).
- It is an elementary resource that is not dependent on technological factors for its use, which makes it a reliable and safe resource even in the most adverse circumstances.

OP5.1.2-8: Establishment of consensus and recommendations.

Related gap: G5.1.2-12: Non-consensual criteria for determining means and destination of transfer.

Professional and scientific societies competent in emergency medicine in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations on triage, on-scene care and evacuation of victims in an MCI or disaster situation, thereby promoting quality standards in line with current scientific evidence.

OP5.1.2-9: Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system.

Related gap: G5.1.2-2: Ununified procedures.

To fill the role/workflow gap between agents involved in first stage triage within a country or between different countries in cross-border incidents, the opportunity is to leave the operational procedures and the supported role definitions "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization path from "lesson learning" following their practice in cross-border incidents as the core of such change management.

Such opportunity has to be supported from a different more flexible triage system, as analysed in the Gap section accordingly.

On the other hand, to develop national and supranational documents, in which the different activities and tasks described in the procedures and the professionals responsible for them are clearly identified and codified. This could help to establish equivalences between professionals from different nations. In case of a cross-border MCI, it would be helpful to identify the category of the homonymous professionals, thus harmonizing the interventions in the incident.

OP5.1.2-10: Improving real-time victims clinical information.

Related gap: G5.1.2-11: Victims clinical information.

The ability of the emergency services to have relevant real-time information on the clinical status of victims in a MCI or disaster is still very limited at the present time because of the overall limitation in real-time information sharing capabilities. Some opportunities are proposed regarding this gap:

Development of an intelligent system that triggers a warning when the patient's data changes in a deteriorating direction (ACS - *Cardio-Circulatory Arrest, e.g., so that the patient must be intubated), and that can attract the attention of medical staff.

User-friendly solution to fill a PC digital "medical record" with data (via smartphone or tablet) and either transmit it in real time when connected, or keep it in memory and send it as soon as it is found.

OP5.1.2-11: Improving vehicles tracking.

Related gap: G5.1.2-7: Ambulances tracking and recording.

Not all the vehicles arriving from different areas to the scene of a MCI or disaster have a GPS system that speaks to each other. Recording the arrival and determine which is the entry point, the person who recognises it, the transmission of information to SIGRUN could facilitate its management and use.

OP5.1.2-12: Improving the first responders training.

Related gap: G5.1.2-4: Lack of first responders knowledge and preparation.

There are different triage standards and practices in use within EU countries among different first responders. Opportunities could include:

Address studies of first responders integrating lessons learned from previous disasters to improve procedures.

Regarding tools, analyse how to improve existing tools and design and adapt future applications to facilitate use and management by first responders, improving both integration and usability.

OP5.1.2-13: Standardization of first responders training and certification in Europe.

Related gap: G5.1.2-5: Lack of common training and certification.

There is no common training and certification at first responder level (EMS & Fire Service) in first aid in the UE countries.

We suggest internationally recognized first aid curricula for first responders such as firefighters, volunteers, and police based on this gap.

In this way, effective coordination and response will be achieved to avoid delays in case of medical emergencies. Improving access to all emergency medical services systems in Europe.

OP5.1.2-14: Debriefing and evaluation standardization in MCI and disasters.

Related gap: G5.1.2-14: Ununified standards for debriefing and evaluation.

Most incidents or disasters occur on an infrequent basis. The main aim of debriefings is to give all involved people the opportunity to communicate what they experienced and identify lessons learned. In addition, all existing plans, trainings, logistical needs and mitigation strategies can be revised and modified to reflect these lessons learned thereby improving the organization's ability to respond to very similar incidents or disasters in future.

Debriefings should ensure:

- Identification of strengths and weaknesses of the intervention,
- By existing policies, systems, competencies and facilities, if the potential for further improvement is revealed, they are developed to their maximum,
- Good/best practices are identified and incorporated,

- Risks are identified and addressed through risk management processes,
- First responders and other involved people of the incident or disaster response become more connected and have a better understanding of each other's work, roles and responsibilities.

As it was mentioned in gap analysis part, there is a hot and cold debriefing. Looking at the debriefing in various agencies and in a cross-sectorial or cross-national aspect, debriefings are missing or unappreciated part of the incident or disaster.

This issue can be solved by mandatory cold and hot debriefing sessions.

Hot debriefings held immediately after the incident or disaster response and may be held simultaneously within an organisation, each unit or service or agency may organize own hot debrief to identify local issues.

Cold debriefings can be either organizational or multi-agency sessions. Those sessions are important to be held few weeks after intervention, to identify strengths or weaknesses and ideas for future learning and improvement. There is a need to organize organizational debriefings, for example in Slovakia and also in other EU countries, debriefings upon one service or agency are common. The problem is multi-agency debriefings, which in some countries are not as common or are simply completely missing.

Opportunities			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.2-1	G5.1.2-1	Harmonisation of emergency services structure	Greater homogeneity in the structure and composition of the emergency services would favour greater homogeneity in the organisation of the chain of command and operational procedures. Given that this goal is almost impossible, harmonisation between the commanders of the emergency services working together would be the priority.
OP5.1.2-2	G5.1.2-3	Homogenisation of professional competencies in emergencies	It would be desirable to move towards homogenisation of training and competencies for emergency services professionals at EU level.
OP5.1.2-3	G5.1.2-13	Integrated pre-hospital and hospital MCI plans and operational procedures.	Legislation to encourage the development and integration of joint EMS-hospital MCI response plans, with EMS and hospitals taking a more proactive role to maximise the effectiveness of the response.
OP5.1.2-4	G5.1.2-6	Standardisation of terminology and criteria.	Standardisation of terminology and harmonisation of criteria for zoning in MCI response would make it easier for different agencies or regions to work together.

Opportunities			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.1.2-5	G5.1.2-8	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the basic information to be collected in relation to each victim is fundamental to guarantee traceability and continuity of care for those affected in a disaster, even more so in cross-border disasters. Of great interest is the use of reliable mobile applications that, while guiding the first responder in their work, allow for easy recording and sharing of relevant victim information.
OP5.1.2-6	G5.1.2-10	Standardisation of means of triage tagging in MCI.	Use "clever" coloured wristbands (equipped with electronic readable id) in first triage/victim identification, log the data in secured blockchain structure and allow other rescuers handling the victim to record more data, prior to the handling of the victim in a hospital.
OP5.1.2-7	G5.1.2-9	Standardisation of triage procedures in MCI.	Standardisation in the triage, coding and tagging of disaster victims is essential to ensure traceability and continuity of care for those affected, especially in disasters where different agencies or countries have to work together. In the simplest or most difficult conditions, standardising the triage priority codes, the tagging and the victim information recording (e.g. via a standardised triage tag, via a mobile application or via a wearable) has proven to be a simple way to support the interoperability of first responders.
OP5.1.2-8	G5.1.2-12	Establishment of consensus and recommendations	Professional and scientific societies competent in emergency medicine in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations on triage, on-scene care and evacuation of victims in an MCI or disaster situation, thereby promoting quality standards in line with current scientific evidence.
OP5.1.2-9	G5.1.2-2	Facilitating harmonisation through a common federated system	Leave the operational procedures "as it is" and tuned in different federated systems linked into SIGRUN and allow their evolution/adaptation towards an optimum harmonization from "lesson learning" following their practice in

Opportunities			
Reconnaissance and triage			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			cross-border incidents as the core of such change management.
OP5.1.2-10	G5.1.2-11	Improving real-time victims' clinical information	Accessing to different parameters could help in choosing the patient's destination
OP5.1.2-11	G5.1.2-7	Improving vehicles tracking	Acquire the arrival and set which is the entry point, the person who detects it, transmitting information to SIGRUN to facilitate its management and use
OP5.1.2-12	G5.1.2-4	Improving the first responders training	Approach studies of first responders by integrating lessons learned from past disasters.
OP5.1.2-13	G5.1.2-5	Standardization of first responders training and certification in Europe	First responders (EMS, FRS) should have standardised common training and knowledge in order to have a quality level of rescue.
OP5.1.2-14	G5.1.2-14	Debriefing and evaluation standardization in MCI and disasters	Debriefings after each incident, drill, operation are essential. Debriefings shall be well structured and should describe each operation which was made during intervention, because many issues raise only after the operation. Step-by-step approach and clear identification of the roles of first responders. IRS and First responders (EMS, FRS, Police...) should use a common debriefing and evaluation after the intervention. Common trainings for First responders - practice cooperation and make procedures more efficient. It is necessary to set processes, responsibilities of each First responder and uniform evaluation.

Table 13 – Opportunities from reconnaissance and triage

6.2 Maintenance, logistics and Deployment

As in previous sections of this deliverable D5.6, for ease of opportunities approach and understanding, this task T5.2 has been divided into 2 subtasks focusing respectively on:

- Communications logistics

- Other logistics

6.2.1 Communications logistics

OP5.2.1-1: Improving communications.

Related gap: G5.2.1-1: Communication needs.

For proper emergency management, the commanders of the different action groups need to know in real time the minimum information necessary for decision-making. It is therefore necessary to have a communications system that guarantees the exchange of information in real time.

OP5.2.1-2: Technological updating of emergency services.

Related gaps: G5.2.1-8: Operating procedures conditioned by obsolete ICTs, G5.2.1-6: Usage of different software within emergency services.

Emergency services use outdated ICTs that condition their operational procedures in MCI and disasters. In addition, different services use different software that can be integrated. Updating these ICT resources would greatly simplify operations in these types of incidents, allowing procedures to be modified to be more efficient and would improve interoperability, especially in cross-sectoral and cross-border incidents.

OP5.2.1-3: Technological updating of emergency services.

Related gap: G5.2.1-4: Excessive use of radio communication.

In general the FR are provided with radio communication, which means that they become saturated and errors can be made in the transmission of messages. Opportunities could include:

To establish exclusive communication channels only for being used in these MCI. Also determine when those who are involved in a MCI should use this specific channels.

To establish the specific uses of each communication channel so all the first responders know specifically which is the most appropriate for each task or moment.

To establish which is the key information that should be transmitted in these channels and which is not adequate just to avoid an excessive communication flow in these networks.

Afterwards all this information should be properly integrated in a national and/or supranational common procedure.

OP5.2.1-4: ICT technological updating of emergency services.

Related gap: G5.2.1-5: Use of non-optimal alternative communication channels in MCI.

Upgrading the ICT assets used by emergency services would reduce the use of alternative communication resources outside common channels. This would encourage the development of adequate common situational awareness.

OP5.2.1-5: Improving portability.

Related gap: G5.2.1-3: Lack of portability.

SIGRUN platform, which will provide advanced communications, information sharing and tactical C2 services for the first (first-aid) responders, seems to be a good solution for improving

portability and for sharing all types of information. SIGRUN application as tactical command and control services for first responders will be composed of 3 subsystems: 1) Data Centralization consisting of central database, to which all the devices of the FR teams with the capacity to record and centralize data will be securely connected. 2) Command and Control Application connects with the first one. This application will collect and interpret from Data Centralization subsystem various information: about incidents, victims and healthcare, units and staff, risk management and civil protection, security. 3) Application for Communication, Messaging and Voice where multilingual communication between all participants will run by means of messages and/or by voice, through the different devices integrated into the platform. All communications from any source, location or language are recorded.

OP5.2.1-6: Technological e-health updating of emergency services.

Related gaps: G5.2.1-7: Limited use of e-health options in MCI and disasters, G5.2.1-2: Outdated technology and system.

Upgrading the ICT resources used by the emergency services would increase the diagnostic and therapeutic capabilities of the first medical responders on the scene.

E-health technologies such as cloud computing, big data analytics or the Internet of Things, which are revolutionising standard healthcare, could be applied in such situations.

OP5.2.1-7: Simple and usable solutions that make the first responder's job easier.

Related gap: G5.2.1-9: Recording information sometimes make it difficult for first responders to do their job.

Digitalisation solutions for EMS intervention in MCI and disasters must also address as an important objective the recording of automatic or sensor-based data and in general the simplification of the work of first responders in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual.

In this sense, there are mobile applications (such as TASSICA MCI) that allow the first responder to use their mobile phone or tablet as a guide in their actions in an MCI or disaster, as a screen for recording and centralising information, as a screen for consulting relevant information for their purposes and even as a means of communication with their chain of command. And all this without any additional effort, but rather by making their tasks easier.

Opportunities			
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.1-1	G5.2.1-1	Improving communications	Real-time sharing of acquired information necessary
OP5.2.1-2	G5.2.1-8	Technological updating of emergency services	Updating the ICT resources used by the emergency services would greatly simplify current operational procedures, make them more efficient, and improve interoperability between agencies and territories.

Opportunities			
Communications maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.1-3	G5.2.1-4	Technological updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT resources used by emergency services transferring information by digital data or another communication system would simplify communication procedures, make them more efficient by fostering the development of a common situational awareness, and improve interoperability between agencies and territories.
OP5.2.1-4	G5.2.1-5	ICT technological updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT assets used by the emergency services would reduce the use of alternative communications resources outside common channels, thus promoting the development of appropriate common situational awareness.
OP5.2.1-5	G5.2.1-3	Improving portability	Interoperability could be achieved if systems could interface using formatted messages, e-mail, or import/export functions
OP5.2.1-6	G5.2.1-7	Technological e-health updating of emergency services	Upgrading the ICT resources used by the emergency services would increase the diagnostic and therapeutic capabilities of the first medical responders on the scene.
OP5.2.1-7	G5.2.1-9	Simple and usable solutions that make the first responder's job easier.	Digitalisation solutions for EMS intervention in MCI and disasters must also address as an important objective the recording of automatic or sensor-based data and in general the simplification of the work of first responders in these situations, which are even more demanding and stressful than usual.

Table 14 – Opportunities from communications maintenance, logistics and deployment

6.2.2 Others logistics

OP5.2.2-1: Establish cross-border operational plans and procedures.

Related gap: G5.2.2-2: Lack of inter-agency logistics procedures.

In addition to the development of cross-border collaborative plans, EU countries should seek the development of unified procedures among the services involved regarding the planning and logistical response to an MCI or disaster affecting several countries.

OP5.2.2-2: Homogenisation of logistical resources in disaster response.

Related gap: G5.2.2-4: Variability in logistics resources for disaster response.

Standardisation in deployment support elements, such as communications and logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tags, PPE or facilities to establish an advanced medical post, would favour logistical

OP5.2.2-3: Establishment of consensus and recommendations.

Related gap: G5.2.2-1: Lack of standardisation of logistical procedures.

Professional societies competent in emergency response in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations regarding the planning and logistical response of emergency services to an MCI or disaster.

OP5.2.2-4: Improve national disaster planning and response logistics tools.

Related gap: G5.2.2-3: Insufficient logistics management tools at the national level.

Progress needs to be made in the use of technological tools and national information systems to ensure that logistical preparedness and response to national and cross-border incidents is effective.

Technological tools should be put in place to ensure communications with remote or isolated areas, information and monitoring systems and use of software.

OP5.2.2-5: Strengthen logistics expertise.

Related gap: G5.2.2-5: Insufficient and non-standardised training in logistics applied to MCI and disasters.

It is advisable to develop specialised formal education, homogenised across EU countries, to provide logistics training for emergency services professionals involved in these aspects of disaster response.

Opportunities			
Others maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.2.2-1	G5.2.2-2	Establish cross-border operational plans and procedures.	In addition to the development of cross-border collaborative plans, EU countries should seek the development of unified procedures among the services involved regarding the planning and logistical response to an MCI or disaster affecting several countries.
OP5.2.2-2	G5.2.2-4	Homogenisation of logistical resources in disaster response.	Standardisation in deployment support elements, such as communications and logistics vehicles, signalling elements, triage tags, PPE or facilities to establish an advanced medical post, would favour logistical interoperability between agencies and territories in MCI or disaster response.
OP5.2.2-3	G5.2.2-1	Establishment of consensus and recommendations	Professional societies competent in emergency response in the EU should issue consensus and recommendations regarding

Opportunities			
Others maintenance, logistics and deployment			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			the planning and logistical response of emergency services to an MCI or disaster.
OP5.2.2-4	G5.2.2-3	Improve national disaster planning and response logistics tools.	Progress needs to be made in the use of technological tools and national information systems to ensure that logistical preparedness and response to national and cross-border incidents is effective.
OP5.2.2-5	G5.2.2-5	Strengthen logistics expertise	It is advisable to develop specialised formal education, homogenised across EU countries, to provide logistics training for emergency services professionals involved in these aspects of disaster response.

Table 15 – Opportunities from others maintenance, logistics and deployment

6.3 Command and Control and support to operational decision-making

OP5.3-1: Harmonisation of emergency services command competencies among the different EU countries.

Related gap: G5.3.1-6: Different criteria for assigning roles in different territories.

As noted in the report Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2008)¹⁷, it would be desirable to move towards homogenisation in the distribution of competencies between emergency services within the EU. The EMS system needs to strengthen its definitive position in disaster preparedness and response mechanisms in many countries.

In the meantime, there is a need to promote the highest degree of harmonisation to facilitate interoperability between disaster management mechanisms in different countries.

OP5.3-2: C2 self-adaptive network environment.

Related gap: G5.3.1-7: Linear plans and positive control not thriving in complex situations.

C2 networks must be effective in multiple situations, providing communications in optimal, as well as highly contested environment. C2 networks need to be agile and effective, given the unpredictability of potential threats. Moreover, the different C2 networks need to be designed to provide reliable communications between all systems involved. Current C2 networks are not developed in a self-adaptive network environment so the different models of Complex Adaptive

¹⁷ Davoli E et al. Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union: Report. WHO Regional Office for Europe. 2008. https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0016/114406/E92038.pdf

Systems (CAS) cannot be applied. But, as far as possible, it is desirable that C2 systems interact like a complex adaptive system that is interconnected and learns from experience.

OP5.3-3: Integration of all emergency services into a single emergency operations centre.

Related gap: G5.3.1-3: Lack of integration of certain emergency services in the emergency operations centre.

Mannaionii A et al¹⁸ published in 2020 a study on how to assess the quality of national and international interoperability in crisis management. According to their proposed methodology, the basic requirement for assessing interoperability in emergency management between agencies and territories is that emergency managers share an emergency operations centre (EOC). This interoperability will logically be enriched to the extent that they also share communications, information and a common Incident Command Post at the scene.

In the future, it is possible that technology will make it possible for such an EOC to be functional, virtual, with no loss of efficiency with respect to the physical sharing of the EOC.

But at the present time, the fact remains that, in order to ensure unity of action in the C2 of the emergency, it is necessary that all services involved in the response can be integrated into a single EOC.

OP5.3-4: Municipality supportive agents engagement.

Related gap: G5.3.1-4: Municipality supportive agents excluded from C2.

In most cases, Municipalities or Cities are engaged in MCI as supportive/ logistics/deployment of first aid to non-casualties assistance based on specific civil protection plans issued and authorized by their Administrative Authority.

The opportunity of SIGRUN is it include Municipalities or Cities as agents with their own COP, provided by SIGRUN accessibility as per G5.3.1.1, assuming that they can log as agents with their available supportive systems

OP5.3-5: Define criteria for C2 facilities location.

Related gap: G5.3.1-2: Different crisis emergency operations centre locations.

As there is no common agreement on the best place to deploy the different posts participating in the emergency, such as EOC, Incident Command Post (ICP) and the Advanced Medical Post (AMP), there is an opportunity for regulations and guidelines in this direction. Particularly, these regulations should consider the scope and nature of the incident, the technologies used (and thus their communication coverage) and the types of first responders participating, among others. In this sense, there is an opportunity for EU members to improve current management of emergency situations with a considerable geographical coverage.

¹⁸ Mannaioni A, Saint Jonsson A, Schaller P, Monet J P. International crisis management, how to evaluate the quality of interoperability? Definition of a national and international methodology, some study cases. 2020. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339843600_International_crisis_management_how_to_evaluate_the_quality_of_interoperability_Definition_of_a_national_and_international_methodology_some_study_cases

OP5.3-6: Harmonisation of procedures.

Related gap: G5.3.1-5: Heterogeneous emergency systems in different territories.

As can be seen from the report Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2008)¹⁹, the standardisation of the structure and functioning of the emergency services due to the legal, socio-economic and geographical particularities of the different Member States, and the weight of the historical development of the services in each of them, is an impossible task in the short to medium term. This is all the more so given that there are Member States where responsibilities for the organisation and management of emergency response are delegated to sub-national authorities.

It is therefore necessary to work on those aspects that favour interoperability between emergency systems and services, from the definition of competencies to the development of common operational procedures or at least their harmonisation between organisations, as well as the determination of the minimum set of data that needs to be recorded and exchanged between commanders to ensure the coordination and effectiveness of MCI or disaster response.

A common operational procedure is a set of standardised and specific actions established within or between organisations to respond to a variety of hazards, threats or incidents. They aim to achieve efficiency, quality results and uniformity of performance, while reducing miscommunication and non-compliance.

OP5.3-7: Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.

Related gaps: G5.3.1-8: Difference in overall incident command in the emergency operations centre, G5.3.1-9: Difference in overall incident command at the scene, G5.3.1-10: Difference in hazard control and zoning command, G5.3.1-11: Difference in rescue command.

In 2020, Monet JP et al²⁰ pointed out the need to enhance the current EU Civil Protection Mechanism (EUCPM) system by defining a harmonised EU Command and Control (C2) System (framework adapted to the size of the territory and the severity of the new challenges, an integrated, robust and unique ad hoc European Command System, interoperable with UNOCHA equipment and INSARAG standards, and other systems compliant with ICS, NATO, WHO and ISO 223202).

They propose elements of a "new governance in operations" for European civil protection. Their proposal for the organisation of the command framework is along the lines of the US ICS model:

¹⁹ Davoli E et al. Emergency Medical Services Systems in the European Union: Report. WHO Regional Office for Europe. 2008. https://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0016/114406/E92038.pdf

²⁰ Monet JP, Pierre S, Pirone S, Castellnou M, Dumas M, Lamris C. Civil Protection in Europe: Towards a Unified Command System? Lessons Learned, Studies and Ideas About Change Management Sté phane Poyau Landes Fire department. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349467144_Civil_Protection_in_Europe_Towards_a_Unified_Command_System_Lessons_Learned_Studies_and_Ideas_About_Change_Management_Sté_phane_Poyau_Landes_Fire_department

- Overall command of the response would be provided by an IC (Incident Commander) supported by officers from the other groups involved in the response, liaison officers, etc.
- The scene would be divided into sectors.
- Field command would be held by a Head of the Incident Command Post (or Head of the Field Command Post), with an organisation underneath in functional sections.

This proposal for a harmonised C2 system, which is very much oriented towards the vertical centralised systems of earlier times, should probably be revised with a more modern and up-to-date vision, but it is certain that the homogenisation of an EU command procedure for major incidents could provide and establish a necessary interoperable framework of command art, adaptable at state and European level."

OP5.3-8: Simplify information flow.

Related gap: G5.3.1-12: Complexity of C2 information flows.

Due to the difficulties of collecting and disseminating information from first responders to EOCs with the communication technologies mostly used by emergency services today, the risk that decisions taken by commanders will be late or inadequate is high.

Operational procedures for information exchange should be simplified, relying on the new opportunities offered by communication technologies, as fewer steps mean fewer possible points of failure.

In addition, another key opportunity lies in determining the minimum data sets that need to be communicated during disasters. Deciding what information is relevant and what is not is an extremely difficult but critical task for the exchange of information between institutions.

OP5.3-9: Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

Related gap: G5.3.1-18: Lack of C2 education and training.

Even though EU Civil Protection Mechanism provides a sound broad framework for common practices between countries for C2 organization and deployment, practices and workflows reported relay mainly on local procedures, which in most cases are a mixture of Civil and military practices. As a result, workflows within different C2s were reported as poorly standardized and, in most cases, as needed to be supported by more robust training programmes to the engaged personnel of agencies involved in planning or deployment of C2 resources. Communications standardization and flow of information has been reported as one of the major challenges to improve.

It is possible to homogenize the techniques and data exchanged at the European Union level in order to make the training and education of FRs easier. In this way, the exchange of information between them, as well as the adaptation to the techniques and elements used by another organization, could be instantaneous.

OP5.3-10: Technological updating of emergency services.

Related gap: G5.3.1-13: Legacy C2 applications.

To overcome these limitations, in which C2 applications cannot extend their functionality or interconnect to other applications, there is a need for defining an implementation plan within organisations intervening in emergency situations. A first option could be to purchase new equipment or acquire new C2 applications with updated functionality. Moreover, another option could be to analyse the capabilities of current systems and evaluate which actions could be beneficial to improve current systems, without replacing them if this is not needed.

OP5.3-11: Facilitating C2 interoperability through a common federated system.

Related gap: G5.3.1-14: Interoperability C2.

Traditional C2 applications are centralised applications that allow limited interoperability and operate with a centralized governance model. These applications need to be reoriented towards a federated model that allows for greater interoperability. In such a way that the governance model divides power between a central unit and the other constituent units acting as a whole.

C2 system interoperability is a key capability of a federated concept has the different C3 system must be able to exchange data, and keep the function operationally coherency within the federation. In order have different entities and applications successfully exchanging data and functioning in a fully coordinated way, a common operating reference frame can be used to overcome the inconsistencies of language, taxonomies, units, status, protocols, procedures etc. The differences must also be addressed in a common communication protocol, so that the messages are properly exchanged.

In a federated system each organization remain independent on their procedures, data ownership and analysis, sharing in a common frame the data contents. This is also applied to the GIS data, where each application holds their GIS structure. Nevertheless, to exchange GIS data or maps, a reference GIS frame is required, so that the world model, gis protocols and data in the map are understood by everyone.

The common data content framework commented above is a working solution for organizing interoperability. Special consideration for maintenance and exchange of GIS data is possible to be based on electronic file formats and exchange protocols from the Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL, Geospatial Data Abstraction Library, <https://gdal.org/>, accessed February 2022) . Geographical environment description data can be open-source, with usage of the most popular formats as GeoTIFF for bitmap representation and ShapeFile for vector representation. In cases where terrain height representation (Digital Terrain Elevation Data) is required, a possible source is the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission, SRTM (<https://srtm.csi.cgiar.org/srtmdata/>). Representation of crisis situations and visualization of organizational elements of Civil Protection actions can be presented in KML and GML file formats.

Moving on to a common platform for visualization of a geographically defined environment is an additional solution that can be resorted. This is solution in case when significant difficulties are found in reconciling separate COP and C2 systems. In this direction, a good experimented solution is to install a geo-server component, for example MapServer (McKenna, Jeff, MapServer open source web mapping, <https://mapserver.org/>, accessed February 2022) and a Web based client part working with an application of the OpenLayers software library (<https://openlayers.org/>). The application of the MapServer enables the use of the Web Map Service (WMS, Web Map Service. Open Geospatial Consortium.

<http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wms>, accessed March 2009) and Web Feature Service (WFS, Web Feature Service. Open Geospatial Consortium. <http://www.opengeospatial.org/standards/wfs>, accessed March 2009).

OP5.3-12: Improving communications.

Related gap: G5.3.1-15: Communication delays among the interveners.

There are two ways to improve the response time of an information collection system. On the one hand, improving the technology, as such, for a new one that offers better capabilities, among these, the improvement of the data transmission speed, something that directly affects the system. On the other hand, the main drawback when it comes to sharing information is the heterogeneity that exists between them when it comes to integrating them all. Because of this, it is necessary to design a system capable of obtaining information from all the legacy systems currently in use, agnostic to the technology they implement.

OP5.3-13: Blockchain "logbooks".

Related gap: G5.3.1-16: Lost Communications and their logs.

As there is not any existing common logging system of communications, messages or transactions between operators of the same C2, it is likely that crucial data can be lost, especially in cases where auditing is required to support victim cases in courts.

Log all messages metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks", as already designed in WP2/D2.3 provides a simple, low cost and robust mechanism of securing the log/time stamp of crucial tactical data, transactions and all metafile data exchanged through the SIGRUN system.

OP5.3-14: Facilitating synchronisation through a common federated system.

Related gap: G5.3.1-17: Time synchronization gap.

In a federated system, logging of events or transactions with no time synchronization might create problems in auditing procedures

Our proposed federated system SIGRUN can resolve this issue as well with the opportunity to synchronized different "federated" clocks with the blockchain logging time stamp mechanism.

Logging all messages' metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks" synchronizes the clocks of the federated systems with a central one provided by SIGRUN.

OP5.3-15: Facilitating research through a common federated system.

Related gap: G5.3.1-19: Very limited capacity for ex-post analysis in C2.

A federated system, as proposed by this project with SIGRUN, in addition to assisting in the real-time management of the disaster, would allow the recording of detailed information regarding the sequence of events, decision-making, interventions and their effects. This information would subsequently facilitate an objective analysis and, therefore, the evaluation of procedures, the identification of areas for improvement, greater knowledge of the behaviour of these disasters, etc.

OP5.3-16: Hybrid Digital Twins as a C2 tool.

Related gap: G5.3.1-1: Not a unique C2 emergency operations centre operating in all countries.

Using Indra's Hybrid Digital TWINS as the tool to gather and map all digitized tactical (sharable) information between different federated systems to SIGRUN, resolves many issues related with the lack of real Common Operational Picture, COP, between C2s of different agents within the same country or between countries in cross-border incidents (according to bi-lateral agreements in force).

Such COP sharing is performed by exchanging SIGRUN COPs accordingly.

Opportunities			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.3-1	G5.3.1-6	Harmonisation of emergency services command competencies among the different EU countries.	It would be desirable to move towards homogenisation in the distribution of competencies between emergency services within the EU. In the meantime, it is necessary to favour the highest degree of harmonisation to facilitate interoperability between disaster management mechanisms in different countries.
OP5.3-2	G5.3.1-7	C2 self-adaptive network environment	Resilient and self-adaptive network environment due to high complexity response of the task.
OP5.3-3	G5.3.1-3	Integration of all emergency services into a single emergency operations centre.	In order to ensure unity of action in the C2 of the emergency, it is necessary that all services involved in the response can be integrated into a single emergency operations centre.
OP5.3-4	G5.3.1-4	Municipality supportive agents engagement	Use the same track and trace technologies and devises to municipalities' assets in order to truck their availability and status in COP
OP5.3-5	G5.3.1-2	Define criteria for C2 facilities location	Establish criteria for the location of CEOC, Incident Command Post ICP and the Advanced Medical Post AMP, based on the communications coverage and scope of the incident.
OP5.3-6	G5.3.1-5	Harmonization of procedures	Harmonisation of operational competencies and procedures, determination of the minimum dataset and establishment of basic interoperability standards.

Opportunities			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.3-7	G5.3.1-8	Harmonisation of the emergency command and control system between EU countries.	Definition of an EU harmonised Control and Command System (C2S) framework adapted to the breadth of the territory and the severity of the new challenges.
OP5.3-8	G5.3.1-12	Simplify information flow	Simplify the information exchange process. Fewer steps, fewer errors.
OP5.3-9	G5.3.1-18	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU could facilitate the definition of joint workflows between C2 systems and the design of specific training programmes.
OP5.3-10	G5.3.1-13	Technological updating of emergency services	Identify systems that do not allow for the integration of needs for emergency services. Propose an action plan for the purchase of new equipment.
OP5.3-11	G5.3.1-14	Facilitating C2 interoperability through a common federated system	To be able to share information between systems in a supranational environment.
OP5.3-12	G5.3.1-15	Improving communications	Communications improvements in terms of data sharing. Real-time is a must for MCI.
OP5.3-13	G5.3.1-16	Blockchain "logbooks"	Log all messages metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks"
OP5.3-14	G5.3.1-17	Facilitating synchronisation through a common federated system	Log all messages metadata and transactions from federated systems in blockchain "logbooks" synchronizing the clocks of the federated systems with a central one provided by SIGRUN
OP5.3-15	G5.3.1-19	Facilitating research through a common federated system	The recording of data, in addition to assisting in the real-time management of the emergency, provides a posteriori data that describe in detail the sequence of events in a real incident, allowing an objective analysis and thus the evaluation of procedures, the identification of

Opportunities			
Command and control and support to operational decision-making			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			areas for improvement, greater knowledge of the behaviour of these disasters, etc.
OP5.3-16	G5.3.1-1	Hybrid Digital Twins as a C2 tool	Map all digitized data into Hybrid Digital Twins of SIGRUN system and transfer a copy to all involved C2s (within a country or between countries) following permission criteria

Table 16 – Opportunities from command and control and support to operational decision-making

6.4 Common Operational Picture and warning

As in previous sections of this D5.6, for ease of opportunities approach and understanding, this task T5.4 has been divided into 2 subtasks focusing respectively on:

- Common operational picture.
- Alert and warning.

6.4.1 Common Operational Picture

The following table lists the opportunities identified in relation to the Common Operational Picture COP, a brief justification of the gap, and finally the Valkyries researcher who provided it in each case.

Following the table, these opportunities will be addressed and developed individually.

OP5.4.1-1: Regulatory harmonisation.

Related gap: G5.4.1-1: Legal constraints to interoperability.

The development of information exchange capabilities between agencies or countries is a challenging task that requires coordination at governmental level, explicit policies and strategies and concrete implementation frameworks, as well as political commitment to develop a legislative framework that favours interoperability between agencies, especially governmental ones.

To foster interoperability between cross-border C2 information exchange technologies and platforms, EU countries should seek to develop legislation to encourage harmonisation: the ability to integrate strategic data in a standard format needs to be stimulated and improved to increase the use of information from different data sources. And it is not only possible to share information, but also to create synergies in the use of technological resources between organisations.

OP5.4.1-2: Fostering a culture of information exchange.

Related gaps: G5.4.1-2: Insufficient awareness of information exchange between agencies and territories, G5.4.1-3: Need to better understand the needs of other emergency services.

As there is an insufficient information exchange between agencies participating in emergency scenarios, there is a clear opportunity for improvement. In this sense, collaboration is key and, thus, new regulations and guidelines should be explored to ensure that, in these specific situations, information flows to interested parties.

It is necessary to work on the individual, organisational and political culture to foster an attitude committed to the need to share all relevant information that allows for maintaining adequate situational awareness in disaster response. A culture of information sharing between institutions would facilitate the exchange of research results, organisational learning, and adaptation and improvisation.

Additionally, there is room for technological solutions that allow an effective communication between these organisations. These solutions must also comply with data regulations such as the GDPR, respecting the privacy of the information. Additionally, these data could be shared during particular durations, easing their implantation by first responder agencies.

OP5.4.1-3: Taking volunteers into account.

Related gap: G5.4.1-15: On scene volunteers rescuers command and COP.

COP of the available data from the volunteers in a common system for the effective utilization of the volunteer human resources.

The opportunity arising from the gap identified in G5.4.1-15 is the integration of recognized and officially registered volunteers into the operational processes of the authorities. In this way, the volunteers will be able to be used more effectively by the central coordinator. For volunteers to have a smooth and safe entry into the operational procedures of the authorities, common training at the national or even European level will be required, as discussed in the corresponding chapter of D6.2 for T6.5, on volunteers and civil protection.

In conclusion, the recognition and participation of the volunteers complement the common operational picture of the coordination center and therefore the management of resources for the completion of the operation will be easier, more efficient, more economical and finally more flexible.

OP5.4.1-4: Standardisation of information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.

Related gaps: G5.4.1-5: No consensus on the basic information to be exchanged between agencies or territories, G5.4.1-4: Differing information needs for decision making, G5.4.1-6: No standardised information exchange processes between agencies or territories, G5.4.1-9: Unselective information overload.

Based on the previous limitations, there is an opportunity for EU standards and regulations indicating the information that needs to be exchanged between agencies or territories in emergency scenarios, as well as the mechanisms for this exchange. This is of the utmost importance to provide a unified operational context between agencies to allow the coordination in cross-border situations.

Deciding what information is relevant is a critical task and standardising the basic information to be exchanged between disaster managers is essential for the interoperability of emergency services and decision support systems. In the same vein, the Valkyries project is working on the

establishment of a minimum data set to facilitate the tasks of developers of information exchange systems between institutions.

OP5.4.1-5: C2 applications.

Related gap: G5.4.1-7: Limited situational awareness.

The fact that different agencies and institutions with their own C2 centres are involved in an emergency is a reality, which is why applications must be developed that allow for their coordination without undermining the authority of each of them in their own field. The first step is for these agencies to be proactive and collaborative, establishing what common information they wish to share and what means they are willing to use to maintain transparent and collaborative communication. There is a clear technological opportunity to facilitate the centralisation of decisions and hence their speed and consistency, although it cannot be assumed that traditional C2 solutions will disappear either, as in particularly complex or particular situations, command will have to be handed over to the more experienced or a solution will have to be reached through less technological methods.

OP5.4.1-6: Improving Mission assessments by technological deployments.

Related gap: G5.4.1-11: Mission assessments by technological deployments.

Apart from an improved digital representation of emergency situations through computers or more common technological devices, there is also the opportunity to make use of VR goggles and see a visual fly out of entire joint schemes of manoeuvre. Not necessarily always but sometimes a virtual involvement can make the decision-maker more involved in the scenario and feel the gravity of it, or simply serve as an inspiration that promotes better decision-making. Also, making use of drones to observe the different points of the emergency scenario can help enormously to see what is happening, where and how.

OP5.4.1-7: Improving visualization techniques in MCI and disasters.

Related gap: G5.4.1-12: Advanced visualization techniques required.

For data visualization, there are a variety of applications that allow you to do this, such as Kibana. Through these systems, you get a wide variety of ways to visualize the data, being able to adjust them to the type of data and the situation. In this way, knowing the status at first glance is simple and facilitates decision making.

OP5.4.1-8: On-the-fly generated data representations using advanced, cognitive loop enhancing techniques (dendrograms, stream graphs, hive plots...).

Related gap: G5.4.1-13: On-the-fly generated data representations when requested by users required.

There is a clear opportunity to design tools to generate, visualise and analyse relevant information live and reliably. Tableau, infogram, chartblocks, datawrapper, D3.js, FusionCharts, Chart.js, Grafana, Chartist.js and Sigma.js are some of the tools available that can serve as inspiration for ideas to represent information and do so in a visual and up-to-date way. Data visualizations should be useful, visually appealing and never misleading. Especially when working with very large data sets, developing a cohesive format is vital to creating visualizations

that are both useful and visually appealing. By turning complex numbers and other pieces of information into graphs, content becomes easier to understand and use.

OP5.4.1-9: Facilitating a COP through a common federated system.

Related gap: G5.4.1-10: Different weather prediction systems between countries.

A common COP, shared by all actors involved in disaster management through a common federated system, with common terminology, symbology, flows and sources, will facilitate the acquisition of a shared situational awareness. This will facilitate the coordination and effectiveness of the response as a whole.

In the particular example of weather prediction, it is a fact that it influences both the C2 decisions and the deployment of help to non-victims, are applicable between countries, following in some cases completely different models and algorithms.

There are two available opportunities for solving this gap:

- The use of satellite weather information provided by EU agents (such Copernicus or others) through available APIs
- Log all available weather-related information in the COP of the SIGRUN system, aka as a layer in the Hybrid Digital TWINS system.

Then, as this COP is shared between agents within a country or between countries, all agents involved in the incident will have a clearer picture of the weather conditions influencing their decision making of supportive systems (such as fire or oil spills prediction models etc).

OP5.4.1-10: Creating a unified COP for MCI and disasters.

Related gap: G5.4.1-8: Provide a shared data base of situational information/awareness is needed.

By creating a shared data base of situational information/awareness and a unified COP for all the partners involved, it is possible to share information and makes it easier for any of them to obtain it. In this way, in the event that a particular FR wants to obtain specific information on any element of the terrain, they could, without interfering with the rest of the queries.

In the military domain, one well-known shared database solution is the Multilateral Interoperability Program (MIP, Burita L)²¹.

The objective of the MIP is to achieve international interoperability of C2 Information Systems at all levels of the military hierarchy to support multinational, combined and joint operations and the advancement of digitization in international joint actions. The MIP solution enables the exchange of information between cooperating but separate national C2 systems. At its core, MIP is structured as a Relational Database Management System RDBMS with known Oracle and MySQL implementations. Data exchange in a multinational aspect is implemented according to the MIP Common Interface (MCI) specifications. The following figure shows an example part of the logical structure of the database:

²¹ Burita L. Multilateral Interoperability Programme, Published by Radioengineering Society, 2019, Online ISSN: 1210-2512, accessed Aug 2022.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228862161_Multilateral_Interoperability_Programme

Figure 4 - Fragment of logistic structure of data base MIP. Source (Burita, 2009)

One such possible solution for the purposes of VALKYRIES is suggested in OP 5.3-16 “Hybrid Digital TWINS”.

OP5.4.1-11: Pay special attention to the safety of first responders.

Related gap: G5.4.1-14: High risk exposure of first responders.

Security conditions during a large-scale crisis are unknown and unpredictable, making it difficult to fully ensure the safety of first responders.

Standard approaches to security management can fall short. In addition to providing adequate means and fostering an appropriate safety culture within the emergency services, it is essential to maintain adequate situational awareness at all times, paying particular attention to the risks that first responders may face during their intervention at the scene.

Opportunities			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.1-1	G5.4.1-1	Regulatory harmonisation	To encourage interoperability between cross-border C2. Information exchange technologies and platforms, EU countries should seek to develop legislation to encourage harmonisation.
OP5.4.1-2	G5.4.1-2 G5.4.1-3	Fostering a culture of information exchange	It is necessary to work on the individual, organisational and political culture to foster an attitude committed to the need to share all relevant information that allows for maintaining adequate situational awareness in disaster response. A culture of information sharing between institutions would facilitate the exchange of research results, organisational learning, and adaptation and improvisation.

Opportunities			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.1-3	G5.4.1-15	Taking volunteers into account	COP of the available data from the volunteers in a common system for the effective utilization of the volunteer human resources.
OP5.4.1-4	G5.4.1-5 G5.4.1-4 G5.4.1-6 G5.4.1-9	Standardisation of information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU.	Standardisation of the basic information to be exchanged between disaster managers is essential for the interoperability of emergency services and decision support systems. There is a need to improve C2 communication at inter-agency, cross-sectoral and cross-border levels. Harmonisation of standards at EU level would be desirable to create a unified basis that can be applied in each country. Deciding what information is relevant is a critical task for developers of information exchange systems between institutions.
OP5.4.1-5	G5.4.1-7	C2 applications	Integrate information from other agencies into command and control applications for each cross-border emergency service
OP5.4.1-6	G5.4.1-11	Improving Mission assessments by technological deployments	VR goggles and see a visual fly out of entire joint schemes of manoeuvre, war-gaming COAs real time while discussing them with the distributed planning staff who used the same environment to build the plans
OP5.4.1-7	G5.4.1-12	Improving visualization techniques in MCI and disasters	Study and learn from every advanced visualisation techniques used in other sectors of society and try to apply their usefulness to an emergency situation.
OP5.4.1-8	G5.4.1-13	On-the-fly generated data representations using advanced, cognitive loop enhancing techniques (dendograms, stream graphs, hive plots...)	In order for the image and information to be updated live, it is necessary that a person intervening in the emergency has the function of interacting with the system that provides the COP and constantly updates it with the data it receives. Some elements could be updated with the use of well positioned sensors, cameras and so on.
OP5.4.1-9	G5.4.1-10	Facilitating a COP through a common federated system	Use available satellite services monitoring weather and their results (such as Copernicus or Aratos Satellite), map the weather conditions as layers in COP/Hybrid Digital Twins and exchange

Opportunities			
Common Operational Picture			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			through a common federated system / COP
OP5.4.1-10	G5.4.1-8	Creating a unified COP for MCI and disasters	Creating a COP that provides realistic, situationally aware information, tailored so that its visualisation can be understood by agencies of different types, is essential. But it will also be necessary for the user to have options within the COP to access more specific information in their field.
OP5.4.1-11	G5.4.1-14	Pay special attention to the safety of first responders.	It is difficult to fully ensure the safety of first responders during a disaster, but in addition to providing adequate means and fostering an adequate safety culture in the emergency services, it is essential to maintain adequate situational awareness at all times.

Table 17 – Opportunities from Common Operational Picture

6.4.2 Alert and warning

OP5.4.2-1: Defining a common approach to disaster early warning.

Related gap: G5.4.2-1: Lack of a common approach in public early warning of disasters.

There are various standards, which can be used as opportunities to solve this gap. These are both technical and procedural. Moreover, hazard-specific early warning standards exist or are under development. The following table provides an indicative list:

Standardisation Body	Standard
ETSI	TR 103 273 V1.1.1 Emergency Communications (EMTEL); Recommendations for public warning making use of pre-defined libraries
	TS 102 900 V1.3.1 Emergency Communications (EMTEL); European Public Warning System (EU-ALERT) using the Cell Broadcast Service
	22322:2015 Societal security – Emergency management – Guidelines for public warning
	22324:2015 Societal security – Emergency management – Guidelines for colour-coded alerts
	22327:2018 Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system
	22328-1:2020 Security and resilience – Emergency management – Part 1: General guidelines for the implementation of a community-based disaster early warning system

ISO	22328-2 Security and resilience – Emergency management – Part 2: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based landslide early warning system (Under development)
	22328-3 Security and resilience – Emergency management – Part 3: Guidelines for the implementation of a community-based tsunami early warning system (Under development)
	22329:2021 Security and resilience – Emergency management – Guidelines for the use of social media in emergencies

Table 18 – Indicative standards relevant to early warning specifications and procedures.

These standards could be adopted either by first responders or by technological organisations involved in the development of relevant technologies. However, although standards exist, as repeatedly stated in the Deliverable, there seems to be a reluctance in the adoption of standards not only by the end users but also from technological providers. According to Tsaloukidis et al²² (2022) this hesitation is clearly depicted in the survey conducted under the framework of the H2020 FIRE-IN project and is related, on the first responders' side, to the lack of awareness of the existence of standards or of the implementation of standards in their procedures, and, on the technological providers' side, to the constraint standards pose to innovation and creativity, since they suggest a common framework for the development of technological solutions. Nevertheless, standardisation could prove an essential tool for the timely alert of exposed populations.

OP5.4.2-2: Identifying "high priority public warnings".

Related gap: G5.4.2-4: No definition of "High priority public warnings".

A warning message is most likely to be timely and effective if it creates the perception that a threat is certain and will lead to severe and immediate consequences for the recipients. It is important therefore, for warning messages to give clear details of the hazard, affected location and relevant timescales, as well as guidance about what to do. Clarity of these issues should avoid potential conflicts caused by different channels of warning that can result in, for example, information accurate for one geographical area being received and acted upon in another area, or differences in updating information by different sources causing reception of out-of-date information.

It is also important that the source of the warning message is perceived to be credible and trustworthy. Information from credible and reliable sources encourages believability and thus is more likely to result in action

To define "high priority public warnings" and create warning message is most likely be timely and effective if it creates the perception that a threat is certain and will lead to severe and immediate consequences for the recipients.

Education, test, and measurement for responding to high priority warning are necessary for early warning systems' success.

²² Tsaloukidis, I., Sakkas, G., Fresu, G., Pronto, L., Hybbeneth, N. "Results of the Request for Ideas: mapping RTOs and Industry potential, response and trends related to Fire-IN CCC/FCCCs #3", 2022, <https://www.fire-in.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/D3.4.-Results-of-the-Request-for-Ideas-mapping-RTOs-and-Industry-potential-response-and-trends-related-to-Fire-IN-CCC-FCCS-3.pdf>

OP5.4.2-3: Standarization of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe.

Related gap: G5.4.2-2: No standardized alerting procedure in National level, G5.4.2-5: Different command competencies in alerts.

The identified gaps are national, for the two countries, but we can assume it at the European level as well. This case is based on any incident that takes place on the cross border line and the citizens of both countries must be informed.

The alert of MCI incidents should be comprehended and common at the European level and subsequently at a national and local level. The notification must be common, as, in the case of an MCI incident that occurs at a cross-border point, the alert and notification procedure must be standardized for all stakeholders.

OP5.4.2-4: Standarization of alerts information and systems in Europe.

Related gap: G5.4.2-3: Technical and procedural issues in alert and warning.

A single emergency alert message standard is needed to communicate alerts over a variety of communications infrastructure (e.g., broadcast TV and radio, cellular, and wired media), thereby reaching the end user over variety of last-mile technologies (e.g., cellular, cable, DSL, WiFi, Bluetooth). Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) attempts to serve this purpose. CAP, which is used by U.S IPAWS, provides a standardized data profile that defines a consistent way for alert and warning messages to be distributed among the involved entities.

The EU supports its Member States in the assessment of hazards by complementing their national early warning and information systems in real-time. These tools contribute to early analysis and actions through early warnings.

Alerts allow the Emergency Response Coordination Centre to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide.

For example, the Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) is an open, non-proprietary digital message format that allows a consistent warning message to be disseminated simultaneously over many different systems. This increases warning effectiveness while simplifying warning systems. It should:

- Provide a specification for a simple, extensible format for digital representation of warning messages and notifications.
- Enable integration of diverse sensor and dissemination systems.
- Be usable over multiple transmission systems, including both TCP/IP-based networks and one-way "broadcast" channels.
- Support credible end-to-end authentication and validation of all messages.
- Provide a unique identifier (e.g., an ID number) for each warning message and for each message originator.
- Provide for multiple message types, such as:
 - Warnings
 - Acknowledgements
 - Expirations and cancellations
 - Updates and amendments

- Reports of results from dissemination systems
- Administrative and system messages
- Provide for multiple message types, such as:
 - Geographic targeting
 - Level of urgency
 - Level of certainty
 - Level of threat severity
- Provide a mechanism for referencing supplemental information (e.g., digital audio or image files, additional text)
- Use an established open-standard data representation.
- Be based on a program of real-world cross-platform testing and evaluation.
- Provide a clear basis for certification and further protocol evaluation and improvement.
- Provide a clear logical structure that is relevant and clearly applicable to the needs of emergency response and public safety users and warning system operators.

Finally, it is necessary to implement, standardize and develop warning systems, as well monitor warning services, based on international recommendations, in order to improve the effectiveness of warnings.

OP5.4.2-5: Technological upgrading of warning systems.

Related gap: G5.4.2-6: Outdated warning systems.

The EENA document "Public Warning Systems-Update"²³ listed the following means of distribution of messages from authorities and organisations to individuals, groups or the general public during emergencies:

- Mobile phones (cell broadcast (CB), location-based alerting using Short Message Service (LB-SMS), instant messages service (IMS), email, Push IP to smartphones, mobile apps...)
- Fixed phones
- TV, radio
- Sirens and long-range acoustic devices
- Variable-message signs and public address systems
- Internet (web, email, PC notification, social media...)

According to the BEREC (Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications) "Guidelines on how to assess the effectiveness of public warning systems transmitted by different means", published in 2020²⁴, in the near future EU Member States seem to have adopted different approaches in terms of the systems to be implemented; some of them are considering deploying several public warning systems using location-based SMS, others using cell broadcasting and others using mobile applications...

²³ Vivier B et al. Public Warning Systems: Update. European Emergency Number Association EENA. 2019. <https://eena.org/knowledge-hub/documents/public-warning-systems-2019-update/>

²⁴ Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications (BEREC). Guidelines on how to assess the effectiveness of public warning systems transmitted by different means. 2020. https://www.berec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/document_register_store/2020/6/BoR_%2820%29_115_BEREC_Guidelines_on_PWS.pdf

This BERE Guidelines are based on a qualitative assessment of the factors that define coverage and affect the ability to reach interested end-users of the alerts transmitted, and provides guidance to the respective EU Member States in assessing their degree of compliance with their obligations under Article 110 of the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC)²⁵.

An adequate upgrading of the technological resources of emergency services and emergency operations centres would help promote early warning and the appropriate issuance and dissemination of alerts.

OP5.4.2-6: Hybrid Digital Twins as an alert and warning harmonization tool.

Related gap: G5.4.2-7: Cross Border Alarms and Warnings gap.

Issued Alarms or Warnings in cross-border incidents are not available. This could create problems in their handling

To resolve this gap, the logging of issues alarms and warnings as “incidents” effective in specific geographical areas can be logged in the SIGRUN COP system (as a layer in the Hybrid Digital Twin). Then such information can be exchanged to the COPs of other agents within a country or between different countries following permission criteria or bi-lateral agreements between countries.

OP5.4.2-7: Creating and supporting initiatives that fight against misinformation in disasters.

Related gap: G5.4.2-8: Fight against misinformation and rumours or fake news.

Disinformation includes false or misleading information purposefully spread to mislead or confuse others—possibly for malicious purposes. Disinformation represents a particularly insidious threat, especially in connected information environments where malicious actors from outside of the affected area may try to interfere with response efforts or intentionally manipulate behaviour to put people in harm’s way.

Creating and supporting public or private initiatives to support administrations in the management of crises in a digital scenario, with the accounts of the emergency services on the monitoring of social networks to go viral prevention messages and the detection of hoaxes.

This requires a heavy mechanism monitoring and analysing social behaviour and people reactions from different sources (such as social media or special apps) as well as other ethics/professional practices of journalists that is out of the scope of the Valkyries project). Not only this, but a community effort to stop the spreading of fake news would be necessary, thus involving local bodies/government.

OP5.4.2-8: Social media analysis of citizens behaviour.

Related gap: G5.4.2-9: No follow up of alarms and warnings issued.

Even though social media and apps analysis of citizens behaviour/reactions/psychology monitoring and valuation after warnings or alarms are out of the scope of the Valkyries project,

²⁵ Directive (EU) 2018/1972 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2018 establishing the European Electronic Communications Code. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32018L1972>

its design has to allow any such future developments as an add-on to the supportive federated systems interconnection.

Opportunities			
Alert and warning			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
OP5.4.2-1	G5.4.2-1	Defining a common approach to disaster early warning	There is an opportunity for a common approach in alerting the citizens of disaster-susceptible areas before disasters occur.
OP5.4.2-2	G5.4.2-4	Identifying "high priority public warnings"	Documents and guides have been published in order to describe the technique for identifying "high priority public warnings". This refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property.
OP5.4.2-3	G5.4.2-2	Standardization of alerts procedures and responsibilities in Europe	The alert of MCI incidents should be comprehended and common at European level and subsequently at national and local level. The notification must be common, as, in the case of an MCI incident that occurs at a cross-border point, the alert and notification responsibilities and procedures must be standardized for all stakeholders.
OP5.4.2-4	G5.4.2-3	Standardization of alerts information and systems in Europe	A single emergency alert message standard is needed to communicate alerts over a variety of communications infrastructure (e.g., broadcast TV and radio, cellular, and wired media), thereby reaching the end user over variety of last-mile technologies (e.g., cellular, cable, DSL, Wi-Fi, Bluetooth). Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) attempts to serve this purpose. CAP, which is used by U.S IPAWS, provides a standardized data profile that defines a consistent way for alert and warning messages to be distributed among the involved entities. The EU supports its Member States in the assessment of hazards by complementing their national early warning and information systems in real-time. These tools contribute to early analysis and actions through early warnings. Alerts allow the Emergency Response

Opportunities			
Alert and warning			
ID	Gap ID	Opportunity name	Justification
			Coordination Centre to provide a comprehensive early assessment. It also enables early action within the framework of EU civil protection inside the EU and worldwide.
OP5.4.2-5	G5.4.2-6	Technological upgrading of warning systems	Adequate upgrading of the technological resources of emergency services and emergency operations centres would help promote early warning and the appropriate issuance and dissemination of alerts.
OP5.4.2-6	G5.4.2-7	Hybrid Digital Twins as an alert and warning harmonization tool	Map all digitized data, including alarms and warnings issued, into Hybrid Digital Twins of SIGRUN system and transfer a copy to all involved C2s (within a country or between countries) following permission criteria
OP5.4.2-7	G5.4.2-8	Creating and supporting initiatives that fight against misinformation in disasters	Currently, the main route of communication of emergencies are social networks, representing both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the great presence of hoaxes and false/fake news.
OP5.4.2-8	G5.4.2-9	Social media analysis of citizens behaviour	Social media and apps analysis of citizens behaviour. Out of the scope of the Valkyries project.

Table 19 – Opportunities from alert and warning

7. Conclusions

7.1 General conclusions of WP5 gaps and opportunities

At the end of this version of deliverable D5.6, a total of 78 gaps and 69 opportunities related to WP5 have been identified.

7.1.1 Classification of gaps and opportunities

For this deliverable D5, the gaps have been worked on following the different tasks set out in WP5. After their definition, and for their analysis, these identified gaps have been classified according to their typology in the following categories:

- Legislation
- Harmonization / standardization
- Review / updating
- Information sharing
- Technology
- Other means
- Training

In those cases where the gap could be included in several of the established types, it was decided to include the gap in the one most appropriate to its content.

The following table shows the gap codes grouped by type of gap and by task/field in which they are included.

TYPE OF GAP	TASK	FIELD	GAP CODES
LEGISLATION	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING	G5.1.1-3
		R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	G5.1.2-3
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	G5.3.1-6
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	G5.4.1-1 G5.4.2-5
HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING	G5.1.1-1, G5.1.1-2
		R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	G5.1.2-1, G5.1.2-2, G5.1.2-6, G5.1.2-9, G5.1.2-10, G5.1.2-14
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	G5.2.2-1, G5.2.2-2 G5.2.1-6
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	G5.3.1-8, G5.3.1-9, G5.3.1-10, G5.3.1-11, G5.3.1-18
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	G5.4.1-3, G5.4.1-5, G5.4.1-6, G5.4.1-8 G5.4.2-2, G5.4.2-3
REVIEW / UPDATING	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING	G5.1.1-4, G5.1.1-5
		R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	G5.1.2-12, G5.1.2-13
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	G5.2.1-8
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	G5.3.1-2, G5.3.1-3, G5.3.1-4, G5.3.1-7
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	G5.4.2-4, G5.4.2-8, G5.4.2-9
INFORMATION SHARING	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING	G5.1.1-6, G5.1.1-7
		R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	G5.1.2-8
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	G5.2.1-1
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	G5.3.1-1, G5.3.1-5, G5.3.1-12, G5.3.1-15, G5.3.1-16, G5.3.1-17
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	G5.4.1-2, G5.4.1-4, G5.4.1-9, G5.4.1-14, G5.4.1-15 G5.4.2-7

TYPE OF GAP	TASK	FIELD	GAP CODES
TECHNOLOGY	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	G5.1.2-7, G5.1.2-11
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	G5.2.1-3, G5.2.1-4, G5.2.1-5, G5.2.1-7, G5.2.1-9 G5.2.2-3, G5.2.1-2
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	G5.3.1-13, G5.3.1-14, G5.3.1-19
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	G5.4.1-7, G5.4.1-10, G5.4.1-11, G5.4.1-12, G5.4.1-13 G5.4.2-1, G5.4.2-6
OTHER MEANS	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	G5.2.2-4
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	
TRAINING	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	G5.1.2-4, G5.1.2-5
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	G5.2.2-5
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	

Table 20 - Classification of the Gaps of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES

Similar to the gaps, the opportunities identified in the WP5 tasks have been classified according to their typology into the following categories:

- Harmonisation / standardisation
- procedures revision / updating of procedures
- Technological opportunities
- Federation of systems
- Training

In those cases where the opportunity could be included in several of the established types, it was decided to include the opportunity in the one most appropriate to its content.

The following table shows the opportunities grouped by type of opportunity and by task/field in which they are included.

TYPE OF OPPORTUNITY	TASK	FIELD	OPPORTUNITY CODES
HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	OP5.1.1-2, OP5.1.1-1, OP5.1.1-3 OP5.1.2-1, OP5.1.2-2, OP5.1.2-3, OP5.1.2-4, OP5.1.2-5, OP5.1.2-6, OP5.1.2-7, OP5.1.2-14
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	OP5.2.2-1, OP5.2.2-2
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	OP5.3-1, OP5.3-5, OP5.3-6, OP5.3-7, OP5.3-8, OP5.3-9
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	OP5.4.1-1, OP5.4.1-4 OP5.4.2-1, OP5.4.2-2, OP5.4.2-3
PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	OP5.1.1-4 OP5.1.2-8
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	OP5.2.2-3
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	OP5.3-2, OP5.3-3, OP5.3-4
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	OP5.4.1-2, OP5.4.1-3, OP5.4.1-11 OP5.4.2-7, OP5.4.2-8

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

TYPE OF OPPORTUNITY	TASK	FIELD	OPPORTUNITY CODES
TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	OP5.1.1-7 OP5.1.2-10
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	OP5.2.1-2, OP5.2.1-3, OP5.2.1-4, OP5.2.1-5, OP5.2.1-6, OP5.2.1-7 OP5.2.2-4
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	OP5.3-10, OP5.3-12, OP5.3-16
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	OP5.4.1-5, OP5.4.1-6, OP5.4.1-7, OP5.4.1-8, OP5.4.1-10 OP5.4.2-5, OP5.4.2-6
FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	OP5.1.1-5, OP5.1.1-6 OP5.1.2-9, OP5.1.2-11
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	OP5.2.1-1
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	OP5.3-11, OP5.3-13, OP5.3-14, OP5.3-15
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	OP5.4.1-9 OP5.4.2-4
TRAINING	T5.1	C. R. PLANNING R. & T. OP. PROCEDURES	OP5.1.2-12, OP5.1.2-13
	T5.2	FR COMMUNICATIONS M., LOGISTICS AND D.	OP5.2.2-5
	T5.3	COMMAND AND CONTROL	
	T5.4	COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE ALERT & WARNING	

Table 21 - Classification of the OPPORTUNITIES of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES

7.1.2 Sources of the gaps

Several sources have been used in the gap identification work. These sources have been grouped into categories:

- Professional experience
- Literature
- Surveys, referring to questionnaires conducted among emergency services and experts in the field.

The following table shows the number of gaps classified by source of identification, and by WP5 task in which they are included.

	LITERATURE	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	SURVEY	Total
T5.1: RECONNAISSANCE, TRIAGE AND CRISIS RESPONSE PLANNING	6	10	5	21
T5.2: MAINTENANCE, LOGISTICS AND DEPLOYMENT	6	5	3	14
T5.3: COMMAND AND CONTROL AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING	5	6	8	19
T5.4: COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE AND WARNING	12	9	3	24
Total	29	30	19	78

Table 22 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES

Analysing the total number of gaps per task, the highest number of gaps have been identified within the task T5.4: COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE AND WARNING, While T5.2: MAINTENANCE, LOGISTICS AND DEPLOYMENT is the task where the least number of gaps have been identified.

The result shows that the origin of the GAPS identified in this deliverable D5.6, in relation to WP5 as a whole, lies mainly in 2 sources:

- The PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE of the researchers involved in the Valkyries project and its External Advisory Board.
- The review of the professional and scientific LITERATURE carried out in the work of the different tasks of WP5, to a large extent also used in the drafting of deliverable 5.1: Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid responders.

The third source, the SURVEYS carried out in the course of the WP5 work, has somewhat less weight as a source of gap identification. 7.1.3 Types of gaps

An analysis by gap type of all WP5 tasks shows the results of the table below.

	LEGISLATION	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	REVIEW / UPDATING	INFORMATION SHARING	TECHNOLOGY	OTHER MEANS	TRAINING	Total
T5.1: RECONNAISSANCE, TRIAGE AND CRISIS RESPONSE PLANNING	2	8	4	3	2		2	21
T5.2: MAINTENANCE, LOGISTICS AND DEPLOYMENT		3	1	1	7	1	1	14
T5.3: COMMAND AND CONTROL AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING	1	5	4	6	3			19
T5.4: COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE AND WARNING	2	6	3	6	7			24
Total	5	22	12	16	19	1	3	78

Table 23 - Type of GAP of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES

In terms of the types of gaps, HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION gaps predominate, followed by TECHNOLOGY and INFORMATION SHARING gaps.

At a greater distance are those of the REVIEW / UPDATING type, and the fewest are LEGISLATION, TRAINING and finally OTHER MEANS gaps.

7.1.4 Types of opportunities

An analysis by opportunities type of all WP5 tasks shows the results of the table below.

	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING	TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES	FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS	TRAINING	Total
T5.1: RECONNAISSANCE, TRIAGE AND CRISIS RESPONSE PLANNING	11	2	2	4	2	21
T5.2: MAINTENANCE, LOGISTICS AND DEPLOYMENT	3	1	7	1	1	13
T5.3: COMMAND AND CONTROL AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING	6	3	3	4		16
T5.4: COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE AND WARNING	5	5	7	2		19
Total	25	11	19	11	3	69

Table 24 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the WP5: COMMON PRACTICES, AND OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES FOR FIRST AID RESPONSES

If we focus on the opportunities, they follow a very similar distribution to that seen in the gaps.

HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION opportunities clearly predominate, followed at a certain distance by TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES.

The opportunities of the FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS and PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING types appear, completely evenly matched, next.

Lastly, there are the TRAINING type.

7.2 Conclusions of T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning

7.2.1 Sources of the gaps

A total of 21 gaps have been identified in the field of recognition, triage and crisis response plans. The table below (Table 23) shows the different sources of gap identification (literature, professional experience or questionnaire) and their distribution according to whether they correspond to planning or procedures.

It is noteworthy that most of the gaps identified (two thirds of the total) correspond to recognition and triage procedures, as well as the fact that the main source is the professionals' own experience.

	LITERATURE	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	SURVEY	Total
CRISIS RESPONSE PLANNING	3	1	3	7
RECONNAISSANCE & TRIAGE OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES	3	9	2	14
Total	6	10	5	21

Table 25 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning

7.2.2 Type of gaps

Regarding the types of gaps, as can be seen in the table below (Table 24), most of them refer to a lack of harmonisation/standardisation. While it is true that at EU level there are guidelines and best practice procedures to facilitate harmonisation between civil protection systems, there is a relevant gap in terms of harmonisation of operational procedures of the different institutions involved in MCI and disaster management.

Apart from the need for harmonisation/standardisation, other gaps include the need to develop specific regulations or to review/update plans and procedures. It should also be noted that gaps have been identified in the fields of technology and education and training in the area of recognition and triage.

	LEGISLATION	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	REVIEW / UPDATING	INFORMATION SHARING	TECHNOLOGY	OTHER MEANS	TRAINING	Total
CRISIS RESPONSE PLANNING	1	2	2	2				7
RECONNAISSANCE & TRIAGE OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES	1	6	2	1	2		2	14
Total	2	8	4	3	2		2	21

Table 26 - Type of GAP of the T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning

7.2.2.1 Types of gaps related to crisis response planning

These gaps are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (2 gaps)

To facilitate collaboration and coordination between various first response agencies, a common process of interpretation of data and information exchanged in MCI and disaster situations is needed (G5.1.1-1). EU civil protection tools and guidelines should also be used to improve interoperability between the different federated systems (G5.1.1-2).

REVIEW/UPDATING (2 gaps)

Crisis response plans are essential in MCI and disaster management. But these plans need to be reviewed and updated to reflect the actual situation of response systems (G5.1.1-4). The plans

also need to be disseminated to first responders and the population to ensure their proper implementation and effectiveness (G5.1.1-5).

INFORMATION SHARING (2 gaps)

In MCIs and disasters, especially if they are cross-border, there may be different criteria for activation of rescue plans (G5.1.1-6), which makes it difficult to have a common operational picture and data exchange. It is equally relevant to have a system that allows for the inclusion of roles and workflows/responsibilities of the agencies involved in the response (G5.1.1-7).

LEGISLATION (1 gap)

There is no standardization of the operational procedures of the different disaster management systems at the European level (G5.1.1-3), especially at the health level. Differences in the structure and organisation of emergency systems hinder interoperability between agencies in cross-border incidents.

7.2.2.2 Types of gaps related to reconnaissance and triage operational procedures

These gaps are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (6 gaps)

At the European level, there is great variability in emergency medical services, not only in structure but also in the designation of roles for first responders (G5.1.2-1). This fact also leads to great diversity in emergency plans and operating procedures (G5.1.2-2). Key aspects of MCI and disaster management such as zoning are not standardized (G5.1.2-6), nor are triage standards and practices (G5.1.2-9), casualty labelling (G5.1.2-10) or debriefing (G5.1.2-14).

REVIEW/UPDATING (2 gaps)

The decision on the evacuation of patients in MCI and disasters, which must take into account both the hospital of destination and the means of evacuation, should be based on recommendations and consensus to ensure quality of care (G5.1.2-12). Furthermore, the effectiveness of the response would be improved if hospitals were more involved in the planning of this type of incident, so that there is better integration between the out-of-hospital and in-hospital levels (G5.1.2-13).

TECHNOLOGY (2 gaps)

From a technological point of view, it is essential to have tools that allow the tracking and recording of the emergency vehicles involved in the incident (G.1.2-7), as well as to be able to share information on the victims (G5.1.2-11). These aspects will ensure that information is shared between the different emergency services and that decision-makers can make decisions in real time.

TRAINING (2 gaps)

First responders must have the necessary knowledge and preparation to intervene in MCIs and disasters. Ideally, there should be a common certification, so that all first responders at European level have the same level of training (G5.1.2-5). Nowadays, there are tools that can facilitate the tasks of first responders in this type of situation, but responders must be familiar with them for them to be really useful (G5.1.2-4).

LEGISLATION (1 gap)

The specific regulations of each country establish which professional profile should provide health care at the scene of the incident, but there is no homogeneity in the professional competencies of first responders (G5.1.2-3).

INFORMATION SHARING (1 gap)

In order to ensure the traceability of victims in MCI and disasters, standardization of the registration and affiliation of victims is necessary (G5.1.2-8).

7.2.3 Type of opportunities

In relation to the opportunities, as can be seen in the table below (Table 25) a total of 21 have been described, of which two thirds (14 of the total) refer to recognition and operational procedures. In the total set of opportunities, those related to harmonisation/standardisation of plans and procedures stand out, followed at a distance by the federation of systems, the updating or revision of plans and procedures, the use of technological tools or the education and training of professionals.

	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING	TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES	FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS	TRAINING	Total
CRISIS RESPONSE PLANNING	3	1	1	2		7
RECONNAISSANCE & TRIAGE OPERATIONAL PROCEDURES	8	1	1	2	2	14
Total	11	2	2	4	2	21

Table 27 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.1: Reconnaissance, Triage and Crisis Response Planning

7.2.3.1 Types of opportunities related to crisis response planning

These opportunities are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (3 opportunities)

Opportunities have been identified in the field of harmonization and standardization, the regulations to be applied in MCI and disasters (OP5.1.1-1), the standardization of terms and symbols for a common understanding of the situation (OP5.1.1-2), as well as an adequate revision and updating of emergency plans (OP5.1.1-3).

FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS (2 opportunities)

In the area of the federation of systems, opportunities have been identified to follow the EU civil protection guidelines (OP5.1.1-5), as well as to facilitate harmonization between the different countries and emergency systems through a common federal system (OP5.1.1-6).

REVIEW/UPDATING (1 opportunity)

It is also considered an opportunity to establish programmes to ensure adequate dissemination and training in relation to emergency plans (OP5.1.1-4).

TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES (1 opportunity)

From a technological point of view, the development of the SIGRUN system will allow the sharing of tactical information of the common corporate image between the different countries, activating the command and control system through a common federated system (OP5.1.1-7).

7.2.3.2 Types of opportunities related to reconnaissance and triage operational procedures

These opportunities are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (8 opportunities)

In the area of recognition and triage, a number of opportunities have been identified in the field of harmonisation and standardisation. It is considered relevant to harmonise the structure of emergency services (OP5.1.2-1), as well as to standardise professional competencies in emergencies (OP5.1.2-29) or that operational plans and procedures for MCI action are integrated at pre-hospital and hospital level (OP5.1.2-3). Furthermore, it is essential to standardise terminology and criteria (OP5.1.2-4) and to standardise the information to be exchanged between disaster managers in the EU (OP5.1.2-5), the means of triage labelling (OP5.1.2-6), triage procedures (OP5.1.2-7) and debriefing and evaluation (OP5.1.2-14).

FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS (2 opportunities)

A common federated system could facilitate the harmonisation of procedures (OP5.1.2-9) as well as the monitoring of emergency vehicles (OP5.1.2-11).

TRAINING (2 opportunities)

In the field of training and coaching, the training of first responders can be improved (OP5.1.2-12) through the development of training programmes and the use of platforms, as well as standardising the training of first responders at European level (OP5.1.2-13).

REVIEW/UPDATING (1 opportunity)

It is also considered an opportunity for professional and scientific societies in the field of emergency medicine to issue consensus and recommendations on health management in MCIs and disasters (OP5.1.2-8).

TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES (1 opportunity)

The main objective in the health management of MCIs and disasters is to achieve the greatest benefit for the majority. To achieve this, it is necessary that all professionals involved in the healthcare of victims have access to their clinical information in real time. Technological tools are now available to enable this (OP5.1.2-10).

Among the opportunities, some of the most relevant are described below:

- Standardisation of terms used in MCI and disaster management. In this sense, Valkyries' proposal is the implementation of the D2.2 Terminology and Semantics: a unified glossary and map of joint terminologies and semantic representations, which will be continuously expanded, revised and updated throughout the life cycle of the Valkyries project, but also after the end of the project, through TASSICA in collaboration with different members of the project and the EAB involved in this task.
- Definition of a minimum set of data to ensure interoperability between services and to ensure that they have the necessary information for decision-making.

- Development of the SIGRUN platform that allows the federation of systems, which may include a tool for victims traceability. This tool will include the minimum information on victims related to registration, filiation and health care, which in turn encompasses the first triage, stabilisation, second triage, evacuation and transfer to the health centre.
- Implementation of the METHANE model, proposed by the Advanced Life Support Group (ALSG) in its Major Incident Medical Management and Support (MIMMS)²⁶ for the notification of events and the subsequent activation of crisis management plans.
- Development of a database that allows the recording and analysis of real MCI to obtain contrasted and useful information that can be shared by the institutions and organisations involved, especially results on the triage methods used.
- Triage system unification proposal by Khorram-Manesh et al²⁷, in their article "A translational triage research development tool: standardising prehospital triage decision-making systems in mass casualty incidents".
- Triage priority categories and tagging unification: Along the lines of the experience developed in Spain with the TASSICA- triage tag²⁸ (see OP5.1.2-6 Standardisation of means of triage tagging in MCI, OP5.1.2-7 Standardisation of triage procedures in MCI).

7.3 Conclusions of T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment

There have been 14 identified gaps in T5.2 in Logistics, Maintenance and Deployment.

7.3.1 Sources of the gaps

The gaps come mainly from 3 sources: literature, professional experience and questionnaire. Most of the sources were provided by professional experience and literature.

In addition, a questionnaire shared with both Valkyries project experts and discussion with external professionals was used as a research source.

	LITERATURE	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	SURVEY	Total
FIRST RESPONDERS COMMUNICATIONS	4	4	1	9
MAINTENANCE, LOGISTICS AND DEPLOYMENT	2	1	2	5
Total	6	5	3	14

Table 28 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment

²⁶ Mackway-Jones K et al. Major Incident Medical Management and Support: The Practical Approach at the Scene. Advanced Life Support Group. 2012 Blackwell Publishing Ltd. Online ISBN:9781444398236. DOI:10.1002/9781444398236. <http://dickyricky.com/Medicine/Books/ALSG%20-%20Major%20Incident%20Medical%20Management%20and%20Support%20-%20Scene.pdf>

²⁷ Khorram- Manesh et al. A translational triage research development tool: standardizing prehospital triage decision-making systems in mass casualty incidents. Scand J Trauma Resusc Emerg Med (2021) 29:119. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13049-021-00932-z>

²⁸ Montarelo A et al. Tarjeta de Triage Tassica 2: evaluación práctica de su funcionalidad operativa en incidentes con múltiples víctimas. Puesta al día en urgencias, emergencias y catástrofes (2010). 10 (3) 123-132. ISSN 1576-0316.

7.3.2 Type of gaps

Some of the identified gaps are technical. Emergency services and disaster management operational procedures include a section on communications. In many cases, these communication systems are outdated and not up to date, which limits the procedures themselves.

Rescue, triage and basic emergency treatment are carried out at the disaster site using traditional methods. Rescue and emergency treatment are carried out at the disaster site using transport technology. A mobile emergency medical centre is then reached by ambulance and patients. The use of cellular and internet-based transport is limited by the fact that many roads are impassable and the internet or mobile phone network may fail.

During a crisis, all existing communication networks are down and different responders use different equipment. The urgency of the situation requires the rapid establishment of a reliable, easily adaptable, resilient, interoperable, cost-effective and secure network. At all levels of a disaster, including the command centre and rescue teams, wireless networks offer a promising communications infrastructure. The logistical disaster management capabilities of different countries and agencies vary widely.

	LEGISLATION	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	REVIEW / UPDATING	INFORMATION SHARING	TECHNOLOGY	OTHER MEANS	TRAINING	Total
FIRST RESPONDERS COMMUNICATIONS		1	1	1	6			9
MAINTENANCE, LOGISTICS AND DEPLOYMENT		2			1	1	1	5
Total		3	1	1	7	1	1	14

Table 29 - Type of GAP of the T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment

7.3.2.2 Types of gaps related to first responders communications

These gaps are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

TECHNOLOGY (6 gaps)

Some of the shortcomings identified are of a technical nature, such as the lack of portability (G5.2.1-3), the overuse of radio communication (G5.2.1-4,) or the use of sub-optimal alternative communication channels in ICMs or disasters (G5.2.1-5). On the other hand, the limited use of e-health options in ICMs and disasters (G5.2.1-7) is also considered a gap, as is the fact that information has to be recorded, which sometimes hinders the work of first responders (G5.2.1-9). This is compounded by the fact that the technology and systems used in the management of these incidents are sometimes outdated (G5.2.1-2).

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (1 gap)

The use of different software in the emergency services (G5.2.1-6), calls for a process of harmonisation in this regard.

REVIEW/UPDATING (1 gap)

Emergency services and disaster management operational procedures include a section on communications. In many cases, these communication systems are outdated and not up to date, which limits the procedures themselves (G5.2.1-8)

INFORMATION SHARING (1 gap)

During a crisis, existing communication networks may fail and different response teams may not use the same equipment. The urgency of the situation demands the rapid establishment of a reliable, easily adaptable, resilient, interoperable, cost-effective and secure network. At all levels of a disaster, including the command centre and rescue teams, wireless networks offer a promising communications infrastructure (G5.2.1-1).

7.3.2.3 Types of gaps related to maintenance, logistics and deployment

These gaps are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (2 gaps)

With regard to gaps concerning harmonisation and standardisation, the lack of standardisation of logistical procedures (G5.2.2-1) as well as the lack of inter-agency logistical procedures (G5.2.2-2) have been identified.

TECHNOLOGY (1 gap)

At the logistical level, the tools available at the national level may be insufficient for the management of an MCI or disaster (G5.2.2-3),

TRAINING (1 gap)

The fact that emergency services do not receive sufficient and standardised training in disaster logistics is also considered relevant. (G5.2.2-5)

OTHER MEANS (1 gap)

The logistical disaster management capabilities of different countries and agencies vary widely. (G5.2.2-4)

7.3.3 Type of opportunities

As noted in the table below there have been a total of 13 opportunities described merged from 14 gaps detected. Professional organizations with knowledge of EU emergency response should reach agreement and offer suggestions for the organization of the emergency services' preparation and logistical response to an MCI or catastrophe. EU nations should work on establishing uniform protocols among the services engaged in preparing and logistical response to an MCI or catastrophe that impacts several nations in addition to creating strategies for cross-border collaboration. The obsolete ICT used by emergency services has an impact on how they operate in the case of an MCI or catastrophe. Additionally, each service makes use of a distinct piece of software that may be combined. In particular for cross-sectoral and cross-border events, modernizing these ICT resources will substantially facilitate operations during such events and allow for the modification of processes to make them more efficient and increase interoperability

	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING	TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES	FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS	TRAINING	Total
FIRST RESPONDERS COMMUNICATIONS	1		6	1		8
MAINTENANCE, LOGISTICS AND DEPLOYMENT	2	1	1		1	5
Total	3	1	7	1	1	13

Table 30 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.2: Maintenance, Logistics and Deployment

7.3.3.1 Types of opportunities related to first responders communications

These opportunities are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

TECHNOLOGY (6 opportunities)

In the technological field, it is considered necessary to update the emergency services (OP5.2.1-2, OP5.2.1-3, OP5.2.1-4, OP5.2.1-6), as well as improving portability (OP5.2.1-5) and finding simple and usable solutions to facilitate the work of first responders (OP5.2.1-7).

FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS (1 opportunity)

For proper emergency management, it is necessary to have a communications system that ensures the exchange of information in real time (OP5.2.1-1).

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (1 opportunity)

Among the different aspects to be standardised in disaster response, logistical resources should also be included (OP5.2.2-2).

7.3.3.2 Types of opportunities related to maintenance, logistics and deployment

These gaps are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

TECHNOLOGY (1 opportunity)

National logistical tools for disaster planning and response need to be improved to respond effectively to cross-border incidents, ensuring communications in remote or isolated areas (OP5.2.2-4).

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (1 opportunity)

In terms of harmonisation/standardisation, the need to establish cross-border operational plans and procedures is relevant (OP5.2.2-1), as is the need to homogenise logistical resources in disaster response (OP5.2.2-2).

REVIEW/UPDATING (1 opportunity)

At EU level, consensus and recommendations should be issued on planning and logistics response to MCIs and disasters (OP5.2.2-3).

TRAINING (1 opportunity)

It is advisable to develop training programmes that enable emergency services professionals to strengthen their logistical skills (OP5.2.2-5).

7.4 Conclusions of T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making

There have been 19 identified gaps in T5.3 Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making.

7.4.1 Sources of the gaps

Table 29 summarizes these gaps, which come either from literature, professional experience or survey. Survey data were collected in the first round of the questionnaire within WP5, other rounds are going to come in following months.

Most of the gaps have been collected from the survey, afterwards from professional experience and at the last place from literature sources. There is a strong linkage between survey and professional experience, because questionnaire was fulfilled by professionals from various fields of emergency management.

	LITERATURE	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	SURVEY	Total
COMMAND AND CONTROL AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING	5	6	8	19

Table 31 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making

7.4.2 Type of gaps

Most the gaps refer to better information sharing and not sufficient harmonization/standardization.

This lack of harmonization/standardization comes from the necessity of revision and updating plans and procedures. Gaps in technology and one gap related to legislation have been identified under this chapter.

	LEGISLATION	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	REVIEW / UPDATING	INFORMATION SHARING	TECHNOLOGY	OTHER MEANS	TRAINING	Total
COMMAND AND CONTROL AND SUPPORT TO OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING	1	5	4	6	3			19

Table 32 - Type of GAP of the T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making

7.4.2.1 Type of gaps related to Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making

These gaps are, from highest to lowest, as follows:

INFORMATION SHARING (6 gap)

In the area of information exchange between countries and emergency services, gaps have been identified such as the fact that there is no single C2 emergency operations centre operational in all countries (G5.3.1-1) or that emergency systems are heterogeneous in different territories (G5.3.1-5). This is compounded by the complexity of C2 information flows (G5.3.1-12), communication delays between emergency responders (G5.3.1-15), the loss of communications and their records (G5.3.1-16), and the high level of time synchronisation (G5.3.1-17).

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (5 gaps)

In relation to harmonisation and standardisation, gaps have been observed on who has overall incident command at the emergency operations centre (G5.3.1-8), or on-scene (G5.3.1-9), as well as on hazard control and zoning command (G5.3.1-10), or rescue command (G5.3.1-11).

There is also a lack of C2 education and training (G5.3.1-18).

REVIEW/UPDATING (4 gap)

This section includes gaps related to the fact that there are different locations of emergency operations centres (G5.3.1-2), or that certain emergency services are not integrated in them (G5.3.1-3). On the other hand, municipal support officers are excluded from C2 (5.3.1-4).

Current C2 systems are not flexible in multidisciplinary environments and are very susceptible to changes due to complex situations.

(G5.3.1-7).

TECHNOLOGY (3 gaps)

In this area, there are still obsolete technology and systems (G5.3.1-13), and there are problems of C2 interoperability problems (G5.3.1-14). On the other hand, there is a very limited capacity for ex-post analysis in C2 (G5.3.1-19) due to the amount of information recorded and the fact that it is not recorded in real time.

LEGISLATION (1 gap)

There are different criteria for assigning roles depending on the regulations applicable in different territories (G5.3.1-6).

7.4.3 Type of opportunities

Reviewing opportunities under T5.3 a total amount of 16 have been identifies out of 19 gaps. The most importance has been given to harmonization/standardization of plans, procedures and processes in command and control. One fourth have been opportunities with linkage to federation of systems. Revision and updating of plans and procedures and technological opportunities are at the same level of importance in this field of command and control.

	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING	TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES	FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS	TRAINING	Total
COMMAND AND CONTROL AND SUPPORT TO	6	3	3	4		16

	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING	TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES	FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS	TRAINING	Total
OPERATIONAL DECISION-MAKING						

Table 33 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.3: Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making

7.4.3.1 Type of opportunities related to Command and Control and Support to Operational Decision-making

HARMONIZATION/STANDARDIZATION (6)

Harmonisation of command competencies (OP5.3-1) and the command and control system (OP5.3-7) of the emergency services between EU countries, as well as procedures (OP5.3-6), is necessary. Furthermore, criteria for the location of C2 facilities should be defined (OP5.3-5), the flow of information should be simplified (OP5.3-8), and the information to be exchanged between EU disaster managers should be standardised (OP5.3-9).

REVIEW/UPDATING (3)

This includes the existence of a self-adaptive C2 network environment (OP5.3-2), as well as the need for all emergency services to be integrated into a single emergency operations centre (OP5.3-3) and the engagement of municipal support actors (OP5.3-4).

FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS (4)

Regarding the federation of systems, interoperability, as well as synchronisation and C2 research should be facilitated by a common federated system (OP5.3-11; OP5.3-14; OP5.3-14), and Blockchain-based systems "logbooks" should be used for the recording of metadata and transactions (OP5.3-13).

TECHNOLOGY (3)

Both technology and communications of emergency services should be improved (OP5.3-10; OP5.3-12), and hybrid digital twins should be used as a C2 tool (OP5.3-16).

A summary of opportunities in T5.3 is presented below:

- Harmonization* of command and control system and of emergency services command competencies within different EU countries, establishment of basic interoperability standards.
- Standardization* of information and type of information to be shared and exchanged between disaster managers in the EU and use simple way of information flow.
- Development of common *operational procedures* at least between organisations, determination of the minimum data set exchanged between commanders.
- Establishment of *single emergency operations centre* for ensuring unity of action in C2.
- Sharing *information between systems* in a supranational environment, update systems, integrate new and create an action plan for purchasing new equipment.
- Ensure real-time communication in MCI.
- SIGRUN system for synchronization through a *common federated system*, for research and mapping all digitized data into Hybrid Digital Twins with transferring a copy to all involved C2 (in country/between countries).

7.5 Conclusions of T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning

A total of 15 gaps have been identified in relation to the COP, and 9 related to alert and warning.

7.5.1 Sources of the gaps

The following table shows the number of gaps classified by source of identification

	LITERATURE	PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE	SURVEY	Total
COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE	7	7	1	15
ALERT & WARNING	5	2	2	9
Total	12	9	3	24

Table 34 - Source of identification of the GAPS of the T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning

7.5.1.1 Sources of the gaps related to COP

The result shows that the origin of the gaps identified in this deliverable D5.2, in relation to COP, lies mainly in 2 sources:

- The PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE of the researchers involved in the Valkyries project and its External Advisory Board (7 gaps identified).
- The review of the professional and scientific LITERATURE carried out in the work of the different tasks of WP5, to a large extent also used in the drafting of deliverable 5.1: Landscape of emerging operational and procedural opportunities for first aid responders (7 gaps identified).

Both sources offer, in this case, a relatively aligned view in relation to the types of gaps identified.

The third source, the SURVEY carried out in the course of the work of FP5, provided a single gap that perhaps sums up the perception of need of the experts consulted: There is insufficient awareness of the need for information sharing between agencies and territories responding together to a MCI or disaster, probably due to political factors or those associated with the organisational culture. (G5.4.1-2)

7.5.1.2 Sources of the gaps related to alert and warning

9 GAPS related to Alert and Warning have been identified, most of them (5) coming from the review of the LITERATURE carried out during the WP5 work.

This identification of gaps was completed with 2 more from the SURVEY of experts carried out during WP5, and with 2 others based on the PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE of researchers and members of the EAB of the Valkyries project.

7.5.2 Type of gaps

Regarding COP and regarding alert and warning, an analysis by gap type shows the results in the table below.

Doc title: Harmonization opportunities on the operational and procedural landscape for first aid response on multi-casualty disasters M18

	LEGISLATION	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	REVIEW / UPDATING	INFORMATION SHARING	TECHNOLOGY	OTHER MEANS	TRAINING	Total
COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE	1	4		5	5			15
ALERT & WARNING	1	2	3	1	2			9
Total	2	6	3	6	7			24

Table 35 - Type of GAP of the T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning

7.5.2.1 Type of gaps related to COP

Regarding COP gaps, their types from highest to lowest are as follows:

INFORMATION SHARING (5 gaps):

There are different information needs for decision-making between different emergency services in MCI or disaster response (G5.4.1-4). These differences are probably smaller between fire and security forces than between fire and security forces and first responders.

But, in any case, there is still insufficient awareness of the need for information exchange between all of them for a more effective response (G5.4.1-2). Some first responders, and this is particularly noted in relation to volunteers, are even excluded from the authorities' information system. Thus, the emergency operations centre cannot have information on the situation of the volunteers involved in the incident (G5.4.1-15).

In other cases, information exchange is not selective, it does not take into account the aspects that are really decisive for other services when making their decisions in response to MCIs and disasters. In these cases, there is often an overload of information that complicates decision-making and creates simplified mental models (G5.4.1-9).

Deficiencies in information sharing in these contexts obviously condition the effectiveness of response, but also too often severely compromise the safety of the first responders deployed to the scene (G5.4.1-14).

TECHNOLOGY (5 gaps):

Commanders in MCI or disaster response must base their decisions, at present, on very limited information and on the advice of certain expert advisors or other participants. There are no technological capabilities to improve decision-making support according to comprehensive joint schemes of manoeuvre. (G5.4.1-11).

There are very few tools available to achieve common visualisation of the emergency, and those that do exist offer information using techniques that can be improved (G5.4.1-12). These tools currently use different forecasting systems (G5.4.1-10), do not allow live updating of information or do not do so in a visually simple and understandable way when users need it (G5.4.1-13).

As a consequence of these inadequate systems for recording, storing and interpreting C2-relevant data, limited situational awareness and awareness of their scope sometimes leads to delays in dispatching equipment and, generally speaking, delays in decision-making (G5.4.1-7).

HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION (4 gaps):

From the COPs-related gaps discussed above, it can be understood that, in order to make the right decisions, emergency response organisations must necessarily share accurate and relevant information in a timely and seamless manner, providing them with a common operational picture that allows them to understand what is happening at any given moment.

This requires a better understanding of the needs of other emergency services: capturing all critical data while being aware of and adequately meeting the needs of other agencies is currently a challenge (G5.4.1-3).

There is a need to develop a common knowledge base of the different competencies of emergency services, from which to understand how the different actors in the response interpret each other's needs and coordination requirements and interact with each other.

The problem is that there are no agreed common criteria for identifying what is, in this context, relevant information for C2 data analysis, let alone for sharing between agencies or territories (G5.4.1-5). Nor, in general terms, are there standardised procedures for the exchange of specific information between the commanders of different agencies or different countries in disaster response (G5.4.1-6).

In this regard, there is a lack of a unified COP for MCI and disasters providing the relevant information shared by all stakeholders (G5.4.1-8).

LEGISLATION (1 gap):

There is just one identified gap related to legislation: there are legal barriers that substantially constrain interoperability between technologies and information exchange platforms in C2. Different jurisdictions and different countries are likely to have different legislation, and even different interpretations of the same laws, on privacy and data protection (G5.4.1-1).

No gap regarding COP was identified related to REVIEW / UPDATING, OTHER MEANS nor TRAINING.

7.5.2.2 Type of gaps related to Alert and warning

Regarding alert and warning gaps, their types from highest to lowest are as follows:

REVIEW / UPDATING (3 gaps)

There is no definition of high priority public alert (G5.4.2-4). These warnings are sent in situations where people must act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. However, recipients of warning messages rarely respond to the initial message.

Fighting disinformation and rumors or fake news (G5.4.2-8) is of great importance, as they represent a major threat to the usefulness of social media and other online tools during disasters. This is a great concern and a barrier in the adoption of social networks for alert issuing.

Alarms or warnings issued by the corresponding authorities are distributed through different physical or telecommunication channels. They are aimed at a specific audience to raise public awareness or to give instructions. However, so far the response of the public after its broadcast has not been followed (G5.4.2-9).

HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION (2 gaps)

According to the questionnaire responses, there is no standardized crisis alert and warning procedure (G5.4.2-2) across the EU. In some countries, the responsibility for triggering the process is held by different agencies.

There is no homogeneity in the management of procedures, techniques and contents related to warning and early warning systems (G5.4.2-3). The effectiveness of warnings needs to be improved, as well as alert monitoring and alert systems.

TECHNOLOGY (2 gaps)

There is a lack of common focus on early public warning of disasters (G5.4.2-1). Timely and prompt issue of warnings and alerts to the public is essential. These must simultaneously reach millions of people. Some serious measures have been taken with the use of the European emergency service line 112. eg to report an emergency, to issue alerts, early warnings and evacuation routes, among others. The poorly receiving of messages from the vulnerable and exposed population are yet to be resolved, in addition to considering the elderly, who do not have confidence in the use of smartphones and PCs.

Public warning systems are outdated (G5.4.2-6). Article 110 of the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) establishes obligations for all Member States of the European Union regarding the Public Alert system. This can serve as a guide in updating such systems. There is a wide diversity of practices in Europe regarding public warning systems, and many of them are based on legacy resources. The technologies deployed are not very homogeneous.

LEGISLATION (1 gap)

There are different command competencies in alerts (G5.4.2-5). The European Code of Electronic Communications (EECC), establishes that it is of national competence. However, there are national and regional laws on the responsibility to issue alert messages that show differences as to which agency is responsible for warning and alerting the population.

INFORMATION SHARING (1 gap)

There are gaps of Cross-Border Alarms and Warnings (G5.4.2-7). Alarms or Warnings issued in cross-border incidents are not available, with negative consequences on the effectiveness of FR C2 commands or public awareness.

7.5.3 Type of opportunities

An analysis by opportunities type regarding COP and regarding alert and warning shows the results in the table below.

	HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION	PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING	TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES	FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS	TRAINING	Total
COMMON OPERATIONAL PICTURE	2	3	5	1		11
ALERT & WARNING	3	2	2	1		8
Total	5	5	7	2		19

Table 36 - Type of OPPORTUNITIES of the T5.4: Common Operational Picture and Warning

7.5.3.1 Type of opportunities related to COP

If we focus on the opportunities regarding COP, their types from highest to lowest would be as follows:

TECHNOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES (5 opportunities):

Without losing sight of the fact that there will be situations that will have to be managed under similar or even more precarious conditions than usual up to date, there is a clear technological opportunity for C2 support solutions that facilitate the exchange of information, the centralisation of decisions and, therefore, their speed and coherence.

Based on the reality that emergency response will involve different agencies and institutions, each with their own tools and even their own C2 centres, solutions need to be developed to integrate information from other agencies into the command and control tools of each regional, national or cross-border emergency service, without disrupting the authority and normal functioning of each of them (OP5.4.1-5).

In this context, it is essential to create a unified COP for MCI and disasters that provides realistic and situation-aware information, adapted so that its visualisation can be understood by different types of organisations. But it will also be necessary for the user to have options within the COP to access more specific information in their domain (OP5.4.1-10).

In MCI and disasters, in order to improve visualisation techniques that facilitate decision making, there is an opportunity to study and learn how to apply those advanced visualisation techniques used in other sectors of society so that a wide variety of ways of visualising data can be obtained and adjusted to the type of data and the situation (OP5.4.1-7).

Data representations, updated live, would be generated on the fly using advanced techniques that would enhance the cognitive OODA loop.

To support not only the recording of information, but also for example mission assessments or situational awareness, there is a need to be open to adapting and deploying new technological opportunities such as cameras, sensors, drones to observe different points of the emergency scene, virtual reality goggles to capture information, communicate, consult operational procedures on the scene in real time or virtually immerse oneself in the scene to increase situational awareness (OP5.4.1-6).

PROCEDURES REVIEW / UPDATING (3 opportunities):

Individual, organisational and political cultures need to be worked on to foster a committed attitude to the need to share all relevant information to maintain adequate situational awareness in disaster response. Each organisation should review and update its culture of information sharing between institutions to facilitate the exchange of research results, organisational learning and adaptation and improvisation (OP5.4.1-2).

In this regard, whenever appropriate, the participation of volunteers should be specifically acknowledged and considered. This will enable the central coordinator to use them more effectively (OP5.4.1-3).

Moreover, special attention should be paid to the safety of first responders. To this end, in addition to providing adequate means and fostering an appropriate safety culture within the emergency services, it is essential to maintain adequate situational awareness at all times,

paying particular attention to the risks that first responders may face during their intervention at the scene (OP5.4.1-11).

HARMONIZATION / STANDARDIZATION (2 opportunities):

The development of information exchange capabilities between agencies or countries is a difficult task that requires a legislative framework that favours interoperability between technologies and platforms for cross-border exchange of C2-related information, and even favours synergies in the use of technological resources between organisations.

This requires improving the ability to integrate strategic data in a standard format to increase the use of information from different data sources (OP5.4.1-1).

Awareness of this fact opens up the possibility of establishing rules and regulations at EU level indicating the information to be exchanged between agencies or territories in emergency situations, as well as the mechanisms for this exchange. In this line, the Valkyries project constitutes an opportunity by working, among other lines, on the establishment of a minimum data set or on the definition of a federation of systems, in order to facilitate the tasks of the developers of information exchange systems between institutions (OP5.4.1-4).

FEDERATION OF SYSTEMS (1 opportunity):

Facilitating a COP through Valkyries would allow using available satellite services that monitor aspects such as weather and its results, map these or other data as layers in the COP/Hybrid digital twins and exchange them through a common federated system / COP (OP5.4.1-9).

No COP opportunity was identified related to TRAINING.

7.5.3.2 Type of opportunities related to alert and warning

There is no homogeneity in relation to procedures, techniques and content related to alerts and early warning systems. A standard method should be developed to collect and relay instantaneously and automatically all types of hazard warnings and reports locally, regionally, and nationally for input into a wide variety of dissemination systems. There is an opportunity to harmonize and standardize alerts and warning system in all EU countries.

We can summarize the opportunities, extracted from the literature, as well as from professional experience or expert opinion:

- There is an opportunity to define a common approach to disaster early warning in alerting the citizens of disaster-susceptible areas before disasters occur. There are various standards, which can be used as opportunities to solve this gap. These are both technical and procedural. Moreover, hazard-specific early warning standards exist or are under development. These standards should be adopted either by first responders or by technological organisations involved in the development of relevant technologies.
- A single emergency alert message standard is needed to communicate alerts over a variety of communications infrastructure (e.g., broadcast TV and radio, cellular, and wired media), thereby reaching the end user over variety of last-mile technologies (e.g., cellular, cable, DSL, WiFi, Bluetooth). Common Alerting Protocol (CAP) attempts to serve this purpose. CAP provides a standardized data profile that defines a consistent way for alert and warning messages to be distributed among the involved entities.

- A technological approach is the great advantage in the development of alerts and warning systems. Adequate upgrading of the technological resources of emergency services and emergency operations centres would help promote early warning and the appropriate issuance and dissemination of alerts. Mapping all digitized data, including alarms and warnings issued, into Hybrid Digital Twins of SIGRUN system and transfer a copy to all involved C2s, within a country or between countries (fundamentally in cross border incident), as an alert and warning harmonization tool.
- We should define and describe the technique for identifying "high priority public warnings". This refers to alerts for situations in which people need to act immediately or within the next hour, in response to an extraordinary or significant threat that is already observed or is likely to occur. Although these are less than one percent of the alert messages typically accessible to the public, such high priority messages are crucial to enabling people to preserve life and protect property.
- The alert of MCI incidents should be comprehended and common at the European level and subsequently at a national and local level. The notification must be common, as, in the case of an MCI incident that occurs at a cross-border point, the alert and notification procedure must be standardized for all stakeholders. An Integrated Public Alert and Warning System is designed to provide rapid, reliable and effective communication to the public in case of major emergencies such as natural disasters. A federated system could facilitate harmonization and activation of EU Civil Protection Mechanism.
- In digital "Era", communication management in crisis situations is key in an interconnected society. Social networks representing both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a problem due to the great presence of hoaxes and false/fake news. Governments and Agencies should fight against misinformation and create and support public or private initiatives in the management of crises in a digital scenario, with the accounts of the emergency services on the monitoring of social networks to go viral prevention messages and the detection of hoaxes.
- Finally, education, testing and measurement of the response to warning are necessary for early warning systems' success. That include analysis of citizens behaviour/reactions/psychology monitoring and valuation after warnings or alarms, its design has to allow any such future developments as an add-on to the supportive federated systems interconnection.

8. Annex A – References and bibliography

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9. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
ACS	Acute coronary syndrome
ALS	Advanced Life Support
ALSG	Advanced Life Support Group
AMP	Advanced Medical Post
AMS	Automated Manifest System
APA	Advanced Preparedness Actions
API	Application Programming Interface
ASTM	American Society for Testing and Materials
BEREC	Body of European Regulators for Electronic Communications
BLS	Basic life support
C2	Command and Control
CAP	Common Alerting Protocol
CB	Cell broadcast
CEN	European Committee for Standardization
CLC	CELENEC, European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization
COP	Common operational picture
CP	Contingency Planning
DSL	Digital Subscriber Line
EAB	External Advisory Board
EECC	European Electronic Communications Code
EENA	European Emergency Number Association
EMS	Emergency Medical Service
EOC	Emergency Operational Centre
ERP	Emergency Response Preparedness
EU	European Union
EUCPM	EU Civil Protection Mechanism
FR	First Responder
GDAL	Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic information system
GPS	Global Positioning System
GSM	Global System for Mobile communication
HC	Humanitarian Coordinator
HCT	Humanitarian Country Team
IASC	Inter-Agency Standing Committee
IC	Incident Commander
ICP	Incident Command Post
ICS	Incident Command System
ICT	Information and communications technologies
IMS	Instant messages service
IPAWS	Integrated Public Alert and Warning System
IRS	Integrated Rescue System

Acronym	Description
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
ITU-T	ITU Telecommunication Standardization Sector
MCI	Mass Casualty Incident
METHANE	MIMMS acronym to build a report for alerting others about a major incident.
MIMMS	Major Incident Medical Management and Support
MIP	Multilateral Interoperability Program
MIT License	A type of license of copyright
MPA	Minimum preparedness actions
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
OODA	Cycle observe – orient – decide - act, developed by John Boyd.
PC	Personal Computer
PPE	EPI
RDBMS	Relational Database Management System
SA	Situational awareness
SIGRUN	Solution proposed by VALKYRIES to provide a cognitive communications platform and federation of resources for FR and C2 in MCI.
SMS	Short Message Service
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission
STANAG	NATO Standardization Agreement
TETRA	Terrestrial Trunked Radio
TV	Television
UN	United Nations
UN OCHA	UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
WFS	Web Feature Service
WHO	World Health Organisation
WMS	Web Map Service
WP	Work package

Table 37 - Glossary